

CRUISE SUMMARY REPORT

MoMARSAT 2021

WORKING AREA - LUCKY STRIKE
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE– EMSO-AÇORES
RESEARCH VESSEL L'ATALANTE
SUBMERSIBLE NAUTILE

MOMARSAT chief scientist: Marjolaine MATABOS, Ifremer

Co-chief scientist : Jozée SARRAZIN, Ifremer

Infrastructure lead : Laurent GAUTIER

Project lead : Mathilde CANNAT, IPGP- CNRS

Mobilisation : 15/05/2021
Harbour : LA SEYNE / MER

Demobilisation : 21/06/20
Harbour : BREST

Nb of days
37

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This document presents the operations carried out and lists the samples taken during the MoMARSAT 2021 campaign.

1. Autorisations

Copies of the documents are presented in annex.

Ref 52109/2021	Ministerio dos Negocios Estrangeiros	Nota Verbal (traduction française en end de document)
AMP / 2021 / 005	REGIAO AUTONOMA DOS AÇORES Secretaria Regional do Mar Ciência e Tecnologia Direcao Regional Dos Assuntos do Mar	<i>AUTHORIZATION AREA FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN MARINE PROTECTED AREA</i>
5 mars 2021	REGIAO AUTONOMA DOS AÇORES Secretaria Regional do Mar Ciência e Tecnologia	Declaracao de Conforidade
20/01/2021		Mail to the national focal point ABS
742301822 Jan 1, 2021	Secretaria Regional dos recursos Naturais – Governo dos Azores	Request for Authorization to Access / Sampling for Scientific Purposes, http://www.formstack.com/forms/GRA-Request_Access_Sampling_Scientific_Purposes

2. Objectives et description of work

The MoMARSAT cruise series (<https://doi.org/10.18142/130>) ensures the annual maintenance of the EMSO-Azores observatory on the Lucky Strike vent field. This seabed observatory has been operating since 2010 and aims to acquire long time-series data (≥ 10 years) on hydrothermal, tectonic, volcanic processes and the associated ecosystems of an active hydrothermal field located on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. EMSO-Azores is part of the European network EMSO ERIC (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory - <http://emso.eu/>), supported in France by the Research Infrastructure (MESR) EMSO-FR whose management is ensured by a collaboration Ifremer-CNRS.

The array includes an observatory infrastructure that comprises a surface buoy (BOREL) ensuring the transfer of data by satellite to a server on land. Two junction boxes (SEAMON) deployed on the bottom communicate acoustically with BOREL and through a cable to the connected instruments. In its current configuration (after MOMARSAT 2020 maintenance), the "connected" part of the observatory includes a surface weather station, a seismometer (OBS), a bottom pressure gauge, a biological observation module (TEMPO- with an HDTV camera and 4 projectors, temperature sensors, oxygen, dissolved iron), an autonomous temperature sensor, two oxygen sensor and a turbidity sensor, a thermistor chain and three hydrophones. During the next cruise, two additional sensors will be deployed: the autonomous sequential hydrothermal fluid sampler (DEAFS) and a generic environmental measurement module (EGIM) that will replace the COSTOF currently servicing SEAMON West.

The infrastructure also includes autonomous instruments which store their data internally: 4 OBS, 2 pressure gauges placed on the bottom, 40 autonomous temperature probes deployed within smokers and on diffusion zones, 7 autonomous current meters placed on the bottom, 4 microbiological colonizers and an oceanographic mooring. Five additional small autonomous cameras will be deployed as part of an experiment to study the restoration of the *Bathymodiolus azoricus* mussel assemblages after a small-scale disturbance initiated in 2017 on the Montségur edifice. These "unconnected" elements contribute to extend the spatial coverage of the area studied during each maintenance cruise.

3. Coordinates of the infrastructure components

Table 1 : Coordinates of the different components of the infrastructure after the 2021 Momarsat maintenance cruise.

Name	Site	Deployment date	Dive	Latitude	Longitude	Depth	Description
Biolucky	Montsegur	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Microbial coloniser
BOREL	Lucky Strike	07/06/2021		N 37 18.072	W 032 16.730	1668	Surface buoy
BT11	Tour Eiffel	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	Autonomous temperature probe
BT12	Tour Eiffel	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.536	1697	Autonomous temperature probe
BT13	Tour Eiffel	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	Autonomous temperature probe
CISICS	AISICS	11/06/2021	2003	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.531	1694	Connected microbial coloniser
Colonisateur LSL1	Lucky strike	08/06/2021	2000	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.784	1748	Microbial coloniser
Colonisateur LSTE9	Tour Eiffel	11/06/2021	2003	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.530	1694	Microbial coloniser
DEAFS	Montsegur	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1703	Fluid sampler
DEEP-SEEDS	Lucky strike	02/06/2021	1996	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1669	Faunal coloniser
EGIM	Lucky strike	08/06/2021	2000	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.791	1739	Generic module EGIM
HTNKE29006	Montsegur	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.296	W 032 16.532	1744	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29008	Tour Eiffel	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29009	Lucky strike	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29012	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.541	1693	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29016	Cyprès	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.456	W 032 16.848	1744	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE29017	South Crystal	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30001	Tour Eiffel	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.516	1706	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30002	Lucky strike	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30005	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.531	1691	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30007	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30014	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1702	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE30015	Lucky strike	04/06/2021	1997	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.496	1620	Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE38002	Lucky strike	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTNKE38003	White Castle	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTW04	Tour Eiffel	11/06/2021	2003	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.523	1687	Autonomous temperature probe
HTW005	White Castle	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTW019	Capelinhos	02/06/2021	1996	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.832	1663	Autonomous temperature probe
HTW08	South Crystal	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.925	1726	Autonomous temperature probe
HTWN013	Montsegur	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.534	1703	Autonomous temperature probe
HTWN019	South Crystal	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
HTWN021	Tour Eiffel	11/06/2021	2003	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.526	1693	Autonomous temperature probe
LSCAP5	Capelinhos	02/06/2021	1996	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.829	1670	Microbial coloniser
LTgrad1	Tour Eiffel	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.518	1708	Autonomous temperature probe

LTgrad10	Lucky strike	14/06/2021	2006	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.519	1704	Autonomous temperature probe
LTGrad12	Tour Eiffel	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.544	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
LTGrad13	Tour Eiffel	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.543	1698	Autonomous temperature probe
LTGrad14	Tour Eiffel	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.550	1699	Autonomous temperature probe
LTGrad15	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad2	Tour Eiffel	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.515	1706	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad5	Tour Eiffel	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.519	1693	Autonomous temperature probe
LTgrad9	Tour Eiffel	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.530	1694	Autonomous temperature probe
LTi1	Tour Eiffel	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.546	1701	Autonomous temperature probe
LTNKE26004	Tour Eiffel	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1697	Autonomous temperature probe
LTW017	Lucky Strike	30/05/2021	1993	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Autonomous temperature probe
LTW018	Tour Eiffel	06/06/2021	1999	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.517	1695	Autonomous temperature probe
LTW040	Tour Eiffel	14/06/2021	2006	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.548	1696	Autonomous temperature probe
Mésocosme	Montsegur	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.533		
Mooring	Lucky Strike	03/06/2021		N 37 17.964	W 032 16.586	1685	Physical oceanography mooring
Pyramide POMME R1	Montsegur	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.537	1704	Autonomous camera
Pyramide POMME C1bcg	Montsegur	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.527	1708	Autonomous camera
Pyramide POMME C2bcg	Montsegur	09/06/2021	2001	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.530	1706	Autonomous camera
Pyramide POMME P1	Lucky strike	13/06/2021	2005	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.520	1707	Autonomous camera
Pyramide POMME sur quadrat I2	Sintra	14/06/2021	2006	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.540	1655	Autonomous camera
Seamon est	Tour Eiffel	10/06/2021	2002	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.532	1696	Seafloor station
Seamon west	Lucky strike	08/06/2021	2000	N 37 17.473	W 032 16.791	1739	Seafloor station
OBS Seamon West	Lucky strike	08/06/2021	2000	N 37 17.482	W 032 16.780	1743	OBS
OBS-LSVWO	Lucky strike	25/05/2021		N 37 17.950	W 032 19.528	2037	OBS
OBS-LSVSO	Lucky strike	25/05/2021		N 37 15.643	W 032 17.884	1925	OBS
OBS-LSVEO	Lucky strike	28/05/2021		N 37 16.799	W 032 14.516	1883	OBS
OBS-LSVNO	Lucky strike	31/05/2021		N 37 19.139	W 032 16.851	1800	OBS
TEMPO	Tour Eiffel	10/06/2021	2002	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.537	1699	Observation module
TCM3-1	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.538	1704	Current meter
TCM3-3	South Crystal	11/06/2021	2003	N 37 17.447	W 032 16.898	1730	Current meter
TCM3-A	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.511	1693	Current meter (in a hole)
TCM3-B	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.547	1694	Current meter
TCM3-C	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1693	Current meter
TCM3-D	Tour Eiffel	12/06/2021	2004	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1692	Current meter

4. Working area and maps

Localisation of moorings, the Capelinhos vent site and the 4 OBS

Localisation of study sites and moorings at Lucky Strike (zoom of map 1)

Maximum extension of work using CTD et the Vertical Microstructure Profiler (VMP) at night

5. On board scientific and technical personnel

The MoMARSAT 2021 participants are from the following institutes: IFREMER, CNRS-IPGP, CNRS-GET, CNRS-MIO and CNRS-UBO. It is a multidisciplinary team composed of both engineers and technicians who designed the observing infrastructure and its various components, and user scientists in charge of the connected and unconnected instruments and the long-term monitoring of the environment of the area.

The 2021 campaign was led by M. Matabos and J. Sarrazin.

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Sarrazin	Jozée	F	Ecologie	Ifremer	X				X						
Gautier	Laurent	M	Electronique	Ifremer	X					X					
Castillo	Alain	M	Mécanique	CNRS/GET	X					X					
Artigue	Lise	F	Géochimie	CNRS/GET	X				X						
Drigo	Loïc	M	Electronique	CNRS/GET	X					X					
Dumouch	Tom	M	Electronique	IPGP	X					X					
Cannat	Mathilde	F	Géophysique	IPGP	X				X						
Mahato	Souradeep	M	Géophysique	IPGP				X			X				
Lesongeur	Françoise	F	Microbiologie	Ifremer	X					X					
Gayet	Nicolas	M	Chimie/instrumentation	Ifremer	X					X					
Hubert	Morgane	F	Chimie	Ifremer	X					X					
Fuchs	Sandra	F	Biologie	Ifremer	X					X					

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Rosazza	Franck	M	Pilote/électronicien	Genavir									X	
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Fauvin	Olivier	M	Pilote/électronicien	Genavir									X	
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Harreau	Rémi	M	Mécanicien	Genavir									X	
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- (1) **H/F** : Gender.
- (2) **Discipline** : Geology, physics, chemistry, biology, mechanics, electronics, computer science, etc.
- (3) **Institute/Affiliation** where the scientist is employed: **F** : France, **UE** : European Union, **E** : Europe outside of EU, **A** : Other countries
- (4) **CH.** : Researcher, **I/T** : Engineer / Technicians, **D** : PhD candidate, **ET** : Student, **P. S** : Sedentary Personnel from the operator Genavir (exclusive of vessel crew), **A** : Journalists, Observers, technicians from the scientific team...

6. Operations timeline

This table lists the chronology of surface and dive operations carried out during the campaign (extracted from Casino and SEALOG software).

Date	Hour	Latitude	Longitude	Instrument	Instrument code	Operation label	Operation ID	Observations
14/05/2021								Mobilisation
15/05/2021								Departure from Toulon, France
15-24/05/2021								Transit
24/05/2021	16:00:00	N 37 18.031	W 032 16.665	microRIO mooring	MICRORIO	Deployment	MOM_MICRORIO	
24/05/2021	21:12:00	N 37 17.724	W 032 16.768	microRIO mooring	MICRORIO	Release	MOM_MICRORIO	
24/05/2021	21:23:00	N 37 17.723	W 032 16.737	microRIO mooring	MICRORIO	End of deployment	MOM_MICRORIO	
25/05/2021	05:41:00	N 37 17.793	W 032 19.450	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release 1	MOM_OBS_LSVWN	Recovery OBS LSVWN
25/05/2021	07:10:00	N 37 18.170	W 032 19.480	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Surface	MOM_OBS_LSVWN	
25/05/2021	07:21:00	N 37 17.982	W 032 19.467	Autonomous OBS	OBS	On board	MOM_OBS_LSVWN	
25/05/2021	09:47:00	N 37 17.933	W 032 19.510	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Deployment	MOM_OBS_LSVWO	Deployment OBS LSVWO
25/05/2021	11:27:00	N 37 17.954	W 032 19.514	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release	MOM_OBS_LSVWO	
25/05/2021	12:07:00	N 37 17.958	W 032 19.530	Autonomous OBS	OBS	BUC onboard	MOM_OBS_LSVWO	
25/05/2021	12:46:00	N 37 15.874	W 032 17.667	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release 1	MOM_OBS_LVSSN	Recovery OBS LSVSN
25/05/2021	13:49:00	N 37 15.866	W 032 17.682	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Surface	MOM_OBS_LVSSN	
25/05/2021	14:17:00	N 37 15.926	W 032 17.223	Autonomous OBS	OBS	On board	MOM_OBS_LVSSN	
25/05/2021	15:22:00	N 37 15.643	W 032 17.881	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Deployment	MOM_OBS_LSVSO	Deployment OBS LSVSO
25/05/2021	17:11:00	N 37 15.627	W 032 17.880	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release	MOM_OBS_LSVSO	
25/05/2021	17:50:00	N 37 15.613	W 032 17.873	Autonomous OBS	OBS	BUC on board	MOM_OBS_LSVSO	
25/05/2021	19:24:00	N 37 16.866	W 032 14.277	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Release 1	MOM_OBS_LSVEN	Recovery OBS LSVEN
25/05/2021	20:38:00	N 37 16.977	W 032 14.227	Autonomous OBS	OBS	Surface	MOM_OBS_LSVEN	
25/05/2021	20:47:00	N 37 16.897	W 032 14.390	Autonomous OBS	OBS	On board	MOM_OBS_LSVEN	
26/05/2021	07:00:00	N 37 17.431	W 032 16.753	Flottabilité SEAMON W	FLOTTAREC UP	Deployment	MOM_FLOTTARECU PW	Deployment flotta Seamon W

26/05/2021	08:38:00	N 37 17.483	W 032 16.799	Flottabilité SEAMON W	FLOTTAREC UP	End of wiring	MOM_FLOTTARECU PW	
26/05/2021	08:45:00	N 37 17.498	W 032 16.793	Flottabilité SEAMON W	FLOTTAREC UP	Deep cable release	MOM_FLOTTARECU PW	
26/05/2021	09:30:01	N 37 17.494	W 032 17.018	Flottabilité SEAMON W	FLOTTAREC UP	Deep cable onboard	MOM_FLOTTARECU PW4	
26/05/2021	10:27:00	N 37 17.481	W 032 17.141	NAUTILE	NAUT	PL1989 start	MOM_NAUT	PL1989-start
26/05/2021	15:33:00	N 37 16.848	W 032 17.179	NAUTILE	NAUT	PL1989 surface	MOM_NAUT	
26/05/2021	16:00:00	N 37 17.203	W 032 17.657	NAUTILE	NAUT	PL1989 on board	MOM_NAUT	PL1989-end
26/05/2021	18:16:03	N 37 17.579	W 032 17.213	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD1
26/05/2021	18:59:01	N 37 17.657	W 032 17.238	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
26/05/2021	19:35:05	N 37 17.601	W 032 17.429	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
26/05/2021	19:37:04	N 37 17.581	W 032 17.452	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
27/05/2021	07:52:00	N 37 17.423	W 032 16.454	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE1
27/05/2021	09:29:00	N 37 17.453	W 032 17.210	NAUTILE	NAUT	PL1990 Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL 1990-start
27/05/2021	10:29:00	N 37 17.244	W 032 17.267	NAUTILE	NAUT	PL1990 at the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
27/05/2021	13:27:00	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.773	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Release of the station	MOM_SEAMONW	Recovery Seamon W
27/05/2021	14:16:00	N/A	N/A	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Buoyancy on board	MOM_SEAMONW	
27/05/2021	14:52:00	N/A	N/A	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Deep cable on board	MOM_SEAMONW	
27/05/2021	16:51:00	N 37 17.195	W 032 16.871	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
27/05/2021	17:22:00	N 37 17.263	W 032 17.298	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL 1990-end
27/05/2021	20:19:02	N 37 17.801	W 032 16.779	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP1
27/05/2021	20:49:02	N 37 17.538	W 032 16.720	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD2
27/05/2021	21:30:01	N 37 17.537	W 032 16.719	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
27/05/2021	21:37:02	N 37 17.537	W 032 16.720	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	
27/05/2021	22:06:05	N 37 17.538	W 032 16.720	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
27/05/2021	22:09:00	N 37 17.538	W 032 16.720	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
27/05/2021	22:50:00	N 37 17.912	W 032 15.857	VMP	VMP	On board	MOM_VMP	VMP1
28/05/2021	07:29:00	N 37 17.299	W 032 16.428	Flottabilité SEAMON E	FLOTTAREC UP	Deployment	MOM_FLOTTARECU PE	DEPLOYMENT flotta Seamon E
28/05/2021	09:20:00	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.600	Flottabilité SEAMON E	FLOTTAREC UP	Buoyancy at the bottom	MOM_FLOTTARECU PE	
28/05/2021	09:57:00	N 37 17.493	W 032 16.668	Flottabilité SEAMON E	FLOTTAREC UP	Release system on board	MOM_FLOTTARECU PE	

28/05/2021	11:08:00	N 37 17.211	W 032 16.635	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1991-start
28/05/2021	12:04:00	N 37 16.886	W 032 16.505	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
28/05/2021	16:11:00	N 37 17.234	W 032 16.079	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	At the bottom Elevator released	MOM_ASCE	
28/05/2021	16:55:00	N 37 17.423	W 032 16.234	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface	MOM_ASCE	
28/05/2021	17:21:04	N 37 17.764	W 032 16.555	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE1
28/05/2021	18:10:00	N 37 17.007	W 032 16.603	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
28/05/2021	18:30:00	N 37 17.460	W 032 17.130	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL1991-end
28/05/2021	20:32:00	N 37 16.790	W 032 14.518	OBS autonome	OBS	Deployment	MOM_OBS_LSVEO	Deployment OBS LSVEO
28/05/2021	22:15:00	N 37 16.790	W 032 14.518	OBS autonome	OBS	Release	MOM_OBS_LSVEO	
28/05/2021	23:00:00	N 37 16.791	W 032 14.517	OBS autonome	OBS	BUC on board	MOM_OBS_LSVEO	
29/05/2021	08:07:00	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.472	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE2
29/05/2021	09:55:00	N 37 17.141	W 032 16.521	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1992-start
29/05/2021	12:02:00	N 37 16.984	W 032 16.275	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface - electronic issues on the Nautile, dive cancelled	MOM_NAUT	
29/05/2021	12:26:00	N 999 00.000	E 999 00.000	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL1992-end
29/05/2021	13:53:00	N 37 17.953	W 032 15.978	BOREL	BOREL	Release of the ballast	MOM_BOREL	Recovery BOREL
29/05/2021	14:24:00	N 37 18.178	W 032 16.341	BOREL	BOREL	Buoy hooked	MOM_BOREL	
29/05/2021	15:20:00	N 37 18.473	W 032 16.847	BOREL	BOREL	Buoy on board	MOM_BOREL	
29/05/2021	15:47:00	N 37 18.806	W 032 17.271	BOREL	BOREL	Recovery of the line	MOM_BOREL	
29/05/2021	17:18:00	N 37 20.118	W 032 18.939	BOREL	BOREL	Buoy on board	MOM_BOREL	
29/05/2021	20:25:04	N 37 17.821	W 032 16.861	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP2
29/05/2021	20:44:01	N 37 17.562	W 032 16.771	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD3
29/05/2021	21:26:00	N 37 17.563	W 032 16.771	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
29/05/2021	22:06:00	N 37 17.563	W 032 16.771	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
29/05/2021	22:30:00	N 37 17.565	W 032 16.787	ADCP coque	NAV	Transit hull ADCP profiles	MOM_NAV	
30/05/2021	03:00:00	N 37 19.208	W 032 15.827	VMP	VMP	Deployment – VMP did not surface during the night	MOM_VMP	
30/05/2021	07:22:00	N 37 18.619	W 032 16.615	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP2

30/05/2021	07:41:00	N 37 18.284	W 032 16.375	Deployment océano	OCEANO	Release	MOM_OCEANO	Recovery Deployment océano
30/05/2021	07:52:00	N 37 17.904	W 032 16.168	Deployment océano	OCEANO	Surface	MOM_OCEANO	
30/05/2021	09:19:00	N 37 19.081	W 032 16.732	Deployment océano	OCEANO	On board	MOM_OCEANO	
30/05/2021	10:19:00	N 37 17.154	W 032 16.600	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1993-start
30/05/2021	11:08:00	N 37 16.842	W 032 16.732	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
30/05/2021	14:12:00	N 37 17.173	W 032 16.458	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Release of SEAMON E	MOM_SEAMONE	
30/05/2021	14:58:00	N 37 17.191	W 032 16.383	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Surface	MOM_SEAMONE	
30/05/2021	15:37:00	N 37 17.759	W 032 17.229	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Buoyancy on board	MOM_SEAMONE	
30/05/2021	16:05:00	N 37 18.186	W 032 17.849	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Deep cable on board SEAMON Est on board	MOM_SEAMONE	Recovery Seamon E
30/05/2021	17:32:00	N 37 17.258	W 032 16.815	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	PL1993-end
30/05/2021	20:11:03	N 37 17.717	W 032 16.776	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP3
30/05/2021	20:27:00	N 37 17.578	W 032 16.751	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD4
30/05/2021	21:07:00	N 37 17.580	W 032 16.748	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
30/05/2021	21:27:01	N 37 17.580	W 032 16.747	VMP	VMP	Surface 50 m starboard, vessel heading 323°	MOM_VMP	
30/05/2021	21:43:02	N 37 17.581	W 032 16.747	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
30/05/2021	21:44:03	N 37 17.579	W 032 16.746	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
30/05/2021	22:05:00	N 37 17.529	W 032 16.460	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP3
31/05/2021	06:03:00	N 37 19.077	W 032 16.737	OBS autonome	OBS	Release	MOM_OBS_LSVNN	Recovery OBS LSVNN
31/05/2021	07:09:00	N 37 19.087	W 032 16.439	OBS autonome	OBS	Surface	MOM_OBS_LSVNN	
31/05/2021	07:27:00	N 37 19.159	W 032 16.519	OBS autonome	OBS	OBS on board	MOM_OBS_LSVNN	
31/05/2021	09:39:00	N 37 17.142	W 032 16.777	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1994-start
31/05/2021	10:33:00	N 37 16.782	W 032 16.673	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
31/05/2021	14:46:00	N 37 16.977	W 032 16.237	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	At the bottom - release	MOM_ASCE	
31/05/2021	15:21:00	N 37 17.067	W 032 16.317	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface	MOM_ASCE	
31/05/2021	15:48:00	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.602	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	on board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE2
31/05/2021	16:31:00	N 37 17.116	W 032 16.768	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom - release	MOM_NAUT	PL1994-end
31/05/2021	17:04:00	N 37 17.011	W 032 16.693	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
31/05/2021	17:32:00	N 37 17.454	W 032 16.969	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	
31/05/2021	20:38:00	N 37 19.154	W 032 16.848	OBS autonome	OBS	Deployment	MOM_OBS_LSVNO	Deployment OBS LSVNO

31/05/2021	22:10:00	N 37 19.157	W 032 16.860	OBS autonome	OBS	Release	MOM_OBS_LSVNO	
31/05/2021	22:20:00	N 37 19.164	W 032 16.848	OBS autonome	OBS	Second release	MOM_OBS_LSVNO	
01/06/2021	08:02:00	N 37 17.313	W 032 16.489	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE3
01/06/2021	09:50:00	N 37 17.158	W 032 16.691	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1995-start
01/06/2021	10:45:00	N 37 16.816	W 032 16.461	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
01/06/2021	14:00:00	N 37 16.954	W 032 16.613	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	At the bottom - release	MOM_ASCE	
01/06/2021	14:30:00	N 37 16.981	W 032 16.429	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface	MOM_ASCE	
01/06/2021	15:05:00	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.269	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE3
01/06/2021	16:45:00	N 37 17.038	W 032 16.981	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom - release	MOM_NAUT	PL1995-end
01/06/2021	17:20:00	N 37 17.220	W 032 17.065	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
01/06/2021	17:40:00	N 37 17.606	W 032 16.946	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	
01/06/2021	20:07:02	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.848	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment sage for 20 mn at 600 m	MOM_CTD	CTD5 Station intercomparaison capteurs RBR
01/06/2021	20:25:00	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.850	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
01/06/2021	20:56:04	N 37 17.508	W 032 16.853	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
01/06/2021	20:58:01	N 37 17.504	W 032 16.855	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
01/06/2021	21:03:04	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.854	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD6	CTD6
01/06/2021	21:46:00	N 37 17.504	W 032 16.856	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD6	
01/06/2021	22:23:05	N 37 17.504	W 032 16.854	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
01/06/2021	22:25:02	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.854	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	on board	MOM_CTD	
02/06/2021	08:00:00	N 37 17.346	W 032 15.805	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE4
02/06/2021	09:35:00	N 37 17.352	W 032 15.937	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1996-start
02/06/2021	10:28:00	N 37 16.945	W 032 16.064	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
02/06/2021	13:58:00	N 37 17.012	W 032 15.820	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	At the bottom - release	MOM_ASCE	
02/06/2021	14:41:00	N 37 17.258	W 032 15.749	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface	MOM_ASCE	
02/06/2021	14:54:00	N 37 17.558	W 032 15.859	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE4
02/06/2021	16:28:00	N 37 17.151	W 032 15.909	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom - release	MOM_NAUT	
02/06/2021	16:57:00	N 37 17.152	W 032 15.822	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
02/06/2021	17:21:00	N 37 17.707	W 032 15.886	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL1996-end
02/06/2021	18:03:02	N 37 17.739	W 032 16.790	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP4
02/06/2021	19:36:00	N 37 17.491	W 032 16.976	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	
02/06/2021	20:35:00	N 37 17.754	W 032 16.846	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP5

02/06/2021	20:54:02	N 37 17.559	W 032 16.860	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD7
02/06/2021	21:35:00	N 37 17.564	W 032 16.859	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
02/06/2021	21:48:01	N 37 17.563	W 032 16.860	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP5
02/06/2021	22:11:00	N 37 17.562	W 032 16.861	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
02/06/2021	22:12:00	N 37 17.564	W 032 16.860	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
03/06/2021	07:52:00	N 37 17.359	W 032 15.487	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE5
03/06/2021	08:46:00	N 999 00.000	E 999 00.000	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface Problem positioning the elevator, going back up	MOM_ASCE	
03/06/2021	08:53:00	N 37 17.526	W 032 15.363	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE5
03/06/2021	09:47:00	N 37 17.431	W 032 16.534	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Second Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE5
03/06/2021	13:43:03	N 37 17.736	W 032 16.791	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP6
03/06/2021	14:56:03	N 37 18.216	W 032 16.707	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP6
03/06/2021	16:22:00	N 37 16.025	W 032 15.506	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Deployment	MOM_OCEANO	Mise à l'eau Deployment océano
03/06/2021	17:42:00	N 37 17.952	W 032 16.660	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	End of Deployment	MOM_OCEANO	
03/06/2021	17:42:00	N 37 17.952	W 032 16.660	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Deployment	MOM_OCEANO	
03/06/2021	20:43:00	N 37 17.771	W 032 16.786	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP7
03/06/2021	21:13:03	N 37 17.548	W 032 16.810	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD8
03/06/2021	21:50:00	N 37 17.548	W 032 16.811	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
03/06/2021	21:58:00	N 37 17.548	W 032 16.811	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP7
03/06/2021	22:25:03	N 37 17.548	W 032 16.810	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
03/06/2021	22:27:01	N 37 17.548	W 032 16.811	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
04/06/2021	09:35:00	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.374	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1997-start
04/06/2021	10:40:00	N 37 17.439	W 032 15.891	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
04/06/2021	14:30:00	N 37 17.558	W 032 16.190	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface released at 14H02	MOM_ASCE	
04/06/2021	15:01:00	N 37 16.863	W 032 16.370	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE5
04/06/2021	17:10:00	N 37 17.727	W 032 15.925	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface – released at 16H42	MOM_NAUT	
04/06/2021	17:37:00	N 37 17.458	W 032 16.377	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL1997-end
04/06/2021	20:07:00	N 37 17.738	W 032 16.815	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP8
04/06/2021	20:22:05	N 37 17.543	W 032 16.773	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD9

04/06/2021	20:59:03	N 37 17.546	W 032 16.770	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
04/06/2021	21:23:01	N 37 17.546	W 032 16.769	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP8
04/06/2021	21:34:00	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.770	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
04/06/2021	21:35:02	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.770	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
05/06/2021	08:01:00	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.619	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE6
05/06/2021	09:40:00	N 37 17.160	W 032 16.703	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1998-start
05/06/2021	10:38:00	N 37 17.432	W 032 16.256	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
05/06/2021	15:00:00	N 37 17.424	W 032 16.442	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface Largage 14H30	MOM_ASCE	
05/06/2021	15:26:00	N 37 17.007	W 032 16.855	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE6
05/06/2021	16:50:00	N 37 17.780	W 032 16.336	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface Largage 16H21	MOM_NAUT	
05/06/2021	17:15:00	N 37 17.452	W 032 16.717	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL1998-end
05/06/2021	18:08:05	N 37 17.726	W 032 16.809	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP9
05/06/2021	20:02:00	N 37 17.912	W 032 16.652	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP9
05/06/2021	20:35:03	N 37 17.697	W 032 16.834	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP10
05/06/2021	20:48:01	N 37 17.559	W 032 16.799	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD10
05/06/2021	21:27:00	N 37 17.558	W 032 16.800	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
05/06/2021	21:46:03	N 37 17.558	W 032 16.799	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	
05/06/2021	22:01:03	N 37 17.558	W 032 16.800	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
05/06/2021	22:02:05	N 37 17.558	W 032 16.799	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
05/06/2021	22:35:03	N 37 17.879	W 032 16.633	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP10
06/06/2021	07:19:00	N 37 17.785	W 032 16.413	Deployment microRIO	MICRORIO	Mooring release	MOM_MICRORIO	Recovery Deployment microryo
06/06/2021	09:42:00	N 37 16.652	W 032 17.557	Deployment microRIO	MICRORIO	Mooring on board end on the deck at 10H15	MOM_MICRORIO	
06/06/2021	10:48:00	N 37 17.443	W 032 17.151	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL1999-start
06/06/2021	11:47:00	N 37 17.441	W 032 16.633	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
06/06/2021	17:57:00	N 37 17.426	W 032 16.007	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface release 17H28	MOM_NAUT	
06/06/2021	18:20:00	N 37 17.142	W 032 16.564	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL1999-end
06/06/2021	20:07:02	N 37 17.733	W 032 16.808	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP11
06/06/2021	20:22:03	N 37 17.538	W 032 16.775	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD11
06/06/2021	21:11:01	N 37 17.537	W 032 16.776	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
06/06/2021	21:20:05	N 37 17.538	W 032 16.776	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP11
06/06/2021	21:47:02	N 37 17.535	W 032 16.778	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	

06/06/2021	21:48:05	N 37 17.536	W 032 16.778	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
06/06/2021	22:10:05	N 37 17.691	W 032 16.686	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP11
07/06/2021	07:20:00	N 37 17.624	W 032 16.436	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Deployment of the station	MOM_SEAMONW	Mise à l'eau Seamon Ouest
07/06/2021	09:23:00	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.826	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Release of the station	MOM_SEAMONW	
07/06/2021	10:05:00	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.826	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Deep cable on board	MOM_SEAMONW	
07/06/2021	14:33:02	N 37 18.165	W 032 16.130	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 1	MOM_OCEANO	Surface triangulation for the mooring
07/06/2021	14:39:04	N 37 18.358	W 032 16.567	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 2	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	14:43:05	N 37 18.299	W 032 16.906	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 3	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	14:49:00	N 37 18.062	W 032 17.174	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 4	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	14:54:00	N 37 17.724	W 032 17.183	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 5	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	14:59:00	N 37 17.462	W 032 16.925	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 6	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	15:04:00	N 37 17.402	W 032 16.537	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 7	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	15:09:01	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.197	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 8	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	15:14:02	N 37 17.803	W 032 16.029	Deployment Océano	OCEANO	Surface triangulation 9	MOM_OCEANO	
07/06/2021	18:23:00	N 37 18.204	W 032 14.850	BOREL	BOREL	Deployment	MOM_BOREL	Mise à l'eau de BOREL
07/06/2021	19:00:00	N 37 18.154	W 032 15.635	BOREL	BOREL	Wiring	MOM_BOREL	
07/06/2021	20:05:00	N 37 18.070	W 032 16.827	BOREL	BOREL	Release	MOM_BOREL	
08/06/2021	07:59:00	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.640	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE7
08/06/2021	09:27:00	N 37 17.498	W 032 17.156	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2000-start
08/06/2021	10:26:00	N 37 17.447	W 032 16.691	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
08/06/2021	12:32:00	N 37 17.610	W 032 16.455	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Release of the buoyancy	MOM_SEAMONW	
08/06/2021	12:49:00	N 37 17.635	W 032 16.470	SEAMON Ouest	SEAMONW	Buoyancy on board	MOM_SEAMONW	
08/06/2021	16:00:00	N 37 17.502	W 032 16.558	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface Release 15H30	MOM_ASCE	ASCE7
08/06/2021	16:50:00	N 37 17.187	W 032 16.273	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface Release 16H31	MOM_NAUT	
08/06/2021	17:25:00	N 37 16.959	W 032 17.050	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2000-end
08/06/2021	20:06:00	N 37 17.555	W 032 16.828	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP12
08/06/2021	20:22:02	N 37 17.751	W 032 16.768	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD12
08/06/2021	20:59:03	N 37 17.752	W 032 16.766	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
08/06/2021	21:32:05	N 37 17.753	W 032 16.766	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	

08/06/2021	21:35:05	N 37 17.753	W 032 16.765	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
09/06/2021	08:08:00	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.653	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE8 -recup?
09/06/2021	10:17:00	N 37 17.145	W 032 16.650	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2001-start
09/06/2021	11:15:00	N 37 17.172	W 032 16.149	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
09/06/2021	17:38:00	N 37 17.183	W 032 16.350	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
09/06/2021	18:05:00	N 37 17.095	W 032 16.904	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2001-end
09/06/2021	20:01:00	N 37 17.548	W 032 16.873	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP13
09/06/2021	20:15:02	N 37 17.744	W 032 16.740	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD13
09/06/2021	20:50:02	N 37 17.744	W 032 16.741	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
09/06/2021	21:13:00	N 37 17.745	W 032 16.739	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	
09/06/2021	21:24:02	N 37 17.745	W 032 16.740	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD1	
09/06/2021	21:25:04	N 37 17.746	W 032 16.741	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD1	
09/06/2021	21:43:01	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.538	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP13
10/06/2021	06:51:00	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.175	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Deployment	MOM_SEAMONE	Mise à l'eau de Seamon E
10/06/2021	09:00:00	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.594	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Relaese of SEAMON E	MOM_SEAMONE	
10/06/2021	09:41:00	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.594	SEAMON Est	SEAMONE	Deep cable on board	MOM_SEAMONE	
10/06/2021	10:20:00	N 37 17.119	W 032 16.648	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2002-start
10/06/2021	11:15:00	N 37 17.038	W 032 16.220	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
10/06/2021	17:40:00	N 37 17.168	W 032 16.295	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
10/06/2021	18:06:00	N 37 17.044	W 032 17.002	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2002-end
10/06/2021	20:04:00	N 37 19.207	W 032 19.461	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP14
10/06/2021	20:21:03	N 37 19.190	W 032 19.610	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD14
10/06/2021	21:00:05	N 37 19.190	W 032 19.610	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
10/06/2021	21:32:00	N 37 19.191	W 032 19.609	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP14
10/06/2021	21:40:05	N 37 19.190	W 032 19.611	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
10/06/2021	21:42:04	N 37 19.191	W 032 19.610	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
10/06/2021	22:36:02	N 37 18.738	W 032 18.730	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP14
11/06/2021	07:49:00	N 37 17.266	W 032 16.618	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE9
11/06/2021	09:25:00	N 37 17.154	W 032 16.644	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2003-start
11/06/2021	10:21:00	N 37 17.184	W 032 16.279	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
11/06/2021	14:07:00	N 37 17.554	W 032 16.318	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	
11/06/2021	14:38:00	N 37 17.304	W 032 16.348	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE9
11/06/2021	16:49:00	N 37 17.530	W 032 16.692	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	

11/06/2021	17:14:00	N 37 17.365	W 032 17.108	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2003-end
11/06/2021	20:05:00	N 37 19.200	W 032 19.455	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP15
11/06/2021	20:16:00	N 37 19.158	W 032 19.643	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment without LADCP; test nois 1 Hz on SBE3F of the SBE25	MOM_CTD	CTD15
11/06/2021	20:58:02	N 37 19.154	W 032 19.643	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
11/06/2021	21:39:00	N 37 19.150	W 032 19.646	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
11/06/2021	21:40:02	N 37 19.150	W 032 19.644	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
11/06/2021	22:02:00	N 37 19.179	W 032 19.380	VMP	VMP	VMP on bord	MOM_VMP	VMP15
12/06/2021	07:55:00	N 37 17.296	W 032 16.630	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE10
12/06/2021	09:43:00	N 37 17.135	W 032 16.641	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2004-start
12/06/2021	10:39:00	N 37 16.790	W 032 16.856	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
12/06/2021	14:50:00	N 37 17.290	W 032 16.244	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface	MOM_ASCE	
12/06/2021	15:08:00	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.843	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	On board	MOM_ASCE	ASCE10
12/06/2021	17:00:00	N 37 17.255	W 032 16.439	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
12/06/2021	17:47:00	N 37 16.898	W 032 16.995	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2004-end
12/06/2021	19:56:00	N 37 17.540	W 032 16.852	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP16
12/06/2021	20:15:01	N 37 17.505	W 032 16.588	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD16
12/06/2021	20:51:05	N 37 17.490	W 032 16.606	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
12/06/2021	21:09:05	N 37 17.491	W 032 16.619	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	
12/06/2021	21:25:03	N 37 17.476	W 032 16.610	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
12/06/2021	21:26:02	N 37 17.474	W 032 16.614	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
12/06/2021	21:48:04	N 37 16.995	W 032 17.238	VMP	VMP	VMP on board	MOM_VMP	VMP16
13/06/2021	07:48:00	N 37 17.259	W 032 16.666	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Deployment	MOM_ASCE	ASCE11
13/06/2021	10:05:00	N 37 17.152	W 032 16.658	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2005-start
13/06/2021	10:59:00	N 37 16.834	W 032 16.815	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
13/06/2021	14:49:00	N 37 17.116	W 032 16.297	ASCENSEUR NAUTILE	ASCE	Surface	MOM_ASCE	ASCE11
13/06/2021	17:26:00	N 37 17.072	W 032 16.715	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
13/06/2021	17:59:00	N 37 17.222	W 032 17.609	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2005-end
13/06/2021	20:03:02	N 37 17.540	W 032 16.882	VMP	VMP	Deployment	MOM_VMP	VMP17
13/06/2021	20:19:01	N 37 17.748	W 032 16.769	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Deployment	MOM_CTD	CTD17
13/06/2021	20:54:05	N 37 17.739	W 032 16.768	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	At the bottom	MOM_CTD	
13/06/2021	21:17:04	N 37 17.736	W 032 16.767	VMP	VMP	Surface	MOM_VMP	VMP17

13/06/2021	21:28:05	N 37 17.738	W 032 16.761	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	Surface	MOM_CTD	
13/06/2021	21:30:02	N 37 17.739	W 032 16.762	Bathysonde Seabird	CTD	On board	MOM_CTD	
14/06/2021	09:34:00	N 37 17.130	W 032 16.671	NAUTILE	NAUT	Deployment	MOM_NAUT	PL2006-start
14/06/2021	10:34:00	N 37 16.768	W 032 16.506	NAUTILE	NAUT	At the bottom	MOM_NAUT	
14/06/2021	17:06:00	N 37 17.266	W 032 16.402	NAUTILE	NAUT	Surface	MOM_NAUT	
14/06/2021	17:32:00	N 37 17.513	W 032 17.106	NAUTILE	NAUT	On board	MOM_NAUT	PL2006-end
14/06/2021	18:00:00	N 37 18.713	W 032 16.162	Navire	NAV	Transit to Brest	MOM_NAV	

7. Dives summaries

7.1. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1989-1

Wednesday May 26, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.5295	W32 ° 17.2632	
Target Flotta SEAMON W	N32 ° 17.4838	W32 ° 16.7699	
Launch time	10:30	Time of arrival at the bottom	11:21
Time of departure from the bottom	15:33	Nautile time on board	16:00
Pilot	Franck Rosazza	Duration of operations on the bottom	3h48
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Marjolaine Matabos		

7.1.1. Objectives

Seamon W storage, start of Seamon East storage, recovery of button chains and chimney measurements of the TEMPO area, survey of the DEAFS area

Useful contact details:

SEAMON W	N 37° 17.476	W 32 ° 16.786	1741
SEAMON E	N 37° 17.306	W 32 ° 16.539	1705
TEMPO	N 37 17.329	W 32 16.533	1697
DEAFS	N 37 17.283	W 32 16.539	1697

Victor configuration

Descent basket

4 button chains	Mathilde blue basket		

Mounted basket

4 button chains	5 probes in blue basket (1 Ltgrad, 4 HTNKE)		

Instrumentation

CHEMINI S + Fe + Optode	WIRELESS	PEP 3 pockets 5 L	ASPI 3 bowls
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NAVI Elevator configuration

Instrumentation

PIF / CHEMINI	PLUME - 4 bags of 2L	Aspi Bowls	
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7.1.2. Summary of operations

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/26/2021	11:52	Seamon W	N 37 17,476	W 032 16.787	1736	OBS storage - Seamon W
05/26/2021	11:53	Seamon W	N 37 17,469	W 032 16.782	1739	PLUMES sampling
05/26/2021	11:53	Seamon W	N 37 17,469	W 032 16.782	1738	Photo face OBS at 11:43 cap 84
05/26/2021	11:55	Seamon W	N 37 17,467	W 032 16.794	1738	OBS stored on Seamon W
05/26/2021	11:55	Seamon W	N 37 17,468	W 032 16.792	1736	Checking the integrity of the structure
05/26/2021	12:09	Seamon W	N 37 17,471	W 032 16.787	1736	Transit to the Seamon W recovery float to confirm the anchorage point

05/26/2021	12:14	Seamon W	N 37 17,472	W 032 16.777	1726	Seamon W salvage fleet
05/26/2021	12:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17,474	W 032 16.776	1725	Transit to Seamon E
05/26/2021	12:33	Seamon E	N 37 17.346	W 032 16.550	1687	Arrival at the Eiffel Tower
05/26/2021	12:38	Seamon E	N 37 17.367	W 032 16.205	1688	Station integrity check
05/26/2021	12:44	Seamon E	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.531	1695	Opening of the TEMPO location
05/26/2021	12:50	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.531	1695	Clear TEMPO location
05/26/2021	12:57	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.532	1695	TEMPO zone
05/26/2021	12:58	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1694	TEMPO environmental module recovery
05/26/2021	13:04	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.533	1695	Slatted cabanage
05/26/2021	13:12	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.530	1693	TEMPO posed next to Seamon
05/26/2021	13:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.532	1692	BT6 recovery
05/26/2021	13:28	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1693	BT7 recovery
05/26/2021	13:32	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1693	BT5 recovery
05/26/2021	13:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.536	1694	BT11 recovery
05/26/2021	13:44	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.532	1691	BT11 in shopping cart
05/26/2021	13:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.531	1692	Transit Montsegur DEAFS
05/26/2021	13:54	Montsegur	N 37 17.318	W 032 16.529	1689	Hydroctopus
05/26/2021	13:59	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.536	1697	DEAFS fireplace
05/26/2021	14:02	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.551	1702	DEAFS zone and HTNKE38003 probe
05/26/2021	14:05	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.552	1702	DEAFS chimney and HTWN0019 probe
05/26/2021	14:07	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.552	1700	Recovery HTNKE38003
05/26/2021	14:13	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.539	1700	Recovery HTWN0019
05/26/2021	14:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.272	W 032 16.539	1701	DEAFs slatted displacement
05/26/2021	14:26	Montsegur	N 37 17.272	W 032 16.539	1700	Grating installed
05/26/2021	14:27	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.539	1700	Repositioning of bags
05/26/2021	14:32	Montsegur	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.540	1699	2nd bag deposit
05/26/2021	14:38	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.540	1701	New smoker for DEAFS?
05/26/2021	14:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17,271	W 032 16.540	1699	PIF syringe test
05/26/2021	14:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.639	1673	PIF Syringe 1 start unfiltered
05/26/2021	14:52	Lucky strike	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.709	1649	PIF Syringe 2 unfiltered
05/26/2021	14:53	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.732	1639	End of the dive, drive to the drop point

7.1.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/26/2021	14:07	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.552	1700	Recovery HTNKE38003
05/26/2021	14:13	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.539	1700	Recovery HTWN0019
05/26/2021	13:12	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.530	1693	TEMPO posed next to Seamon
05/26/2021	13:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.532	1692	BT6 recovery
05/26/2021	13:28	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1693	BT7 recovery
05/26/2021	13:32	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1693	BT5 recovery
05/26/2021	13:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.536	1694	BT11 recovery

7.1.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/26/2021	11:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17,469	W 032 16.782	1700	PLUME 1 - bottom water
05/26/2021	11:32	Lucky strike	N 37 17,469	W 032 16.782	1700	PLUME 2 - bottom water
05/26/2021	11:40	Lucky strike	N 37 17,469	W 032 16.782	1693	PLUME 3 - bottom water
05/26/2021	11:53	Lucky strike	N 37 17,469	W 032 16.782	1700	PLUME 4 - bottom water
05/26/2021	14:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.639	1700	PIF Syringe 1 start unfiltered
05/26/2021	14:52	Lucky strike	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.709	1693	PIF Syringe 2 unfiltered

7.1.5. 4K video footage

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1989-1	20210526T114217.013	00:00:21	Seamon W
PL1989-1	20210526T114248.403	00:00:41	Seamon W
PL1989-1	20210526T114329.987	00:00:11	Seamon W

PL1989-1	20210526T115122.522	00:00:57	Seamon W
PL1989-1	20210526T120350.801	00:01:00	Seamon W
PL1989-1	20210526T125628.933	00:00:09	TEMPO
PL1989-1	20210526T125827.598	00:04:11	TEMPO
PL1989-1	20210526T132309.317	00:02:10	TEMPO
PL1989-1	20210526T132631.541	00:02:02	TEMPO
PL1989-1	20210526T133034.164	00:00:21	TEMPO
PL1989-1	20210526T133714.941	00:00:51	TEMPO
PL1989-1	20210526T134053.493	00:00:51	TEMPO </td
PL1989-1	20210526T140424.085	00:01:39	Smoker DEAFs
PL1989-1	20210526T141204.934	00:00:18	Montsegur
PL1989-1	20210526T141425.67	00:04:05	Montsegur

7.1.6. Navigation

7.2. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1990-2

Thursday May 27

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.5295	W32 ° 17.2632	
ASC anchor position	N37 ° 17.4362	W32 ° 16.5594	
Launch time	09:33	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:30
Time of departure from the bottom	16:23	Nautile time on board	17:50
Pilot	Julien Fenouil	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h53
Co-pilot	Olivier Fauvin		
Observer	Damien Saliou		

7.2.1. Objectives

Objectives: SEAMON W lockpicking, SEAMON Est storage (TEMPO, hydroctopus, chain)

Useful contact details:

SEAMON E	N 37 ° 17.306	W 32 ° 16.539	1705
TEMPO	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.533	1697
TCM3-A - TE	N37 ° 17.343	W32 ° 16.540	1694
TCM3-B - TE	N37 ° 17.340	W32 ° 16.534	1689
TCM3-C - TE	N37 ° 17.347	W32 ° 16.533	1692
TCM3-D - TE	N37 ° 17.345	W32 ° 16.530	1691
TCM3-1 - TE North	N 37 ° 17.373	W 32 ° 16.544	1688
TCM3-2 - TE South	N37 ° 17.302	W32 ° 16.538	1704
LSTE08	N37 ° 17.338	W32 ° 16.530	1692

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

PBT1, PBT2	Blue basket		
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Mounted basket

PBT2	5 probes in blue basket	Biolucky	
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Instrumentation

Aspi bowls			

ASC1 configuration

ASC lowering basket	LTI probe (outdoor-test)	Reversal thermometer	
Ascended basket	2 current meters	4 current meters	(Released the next day)

7.2.2. Summary of operations

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/27/2021	10:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.502	W 032 17.161		Arrival at the bottom
05/27/2021	11:00	Seamon W	N 37 17,463	W 032 16.779	1737	Arrival on SEAMON W
05/27/2021	11:06	Seamon W	N 37 17,468	W 032 16.784	1743	Bag of pellets removed and placed next to it
05/27/2021	11:12	Seamon W	N 37 17,475	W 032 16.772	1735	Arrival on float SEAMON W
05/27/2021	11:16	Seamon W	N 37 17,480	W 032 16.772	1733	Recovery of a bag of pellets
05/27/2021	11:54	Seamon W	N 37 17,475	W 032 16.789	1741	SEAMON W crocheted

05/27/2021	12:06	Seamon W	N 37 17,484	W 032 16.770	1745	Line clearance
05/27/2021	12:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17.407	W 032 16.587	1670	Transit to SEAMON E
05/27/2021	12:29	Seamon E	N 37 17.378	W 032 16.552	1693	TCM current meter in view (TCM3-1)
05/27/2021	12:31	Seamon E	N 37 17.378	W 032 16.555	1692	TCM 3-1 Recovery
05/27/2021	12:38	Seamon E	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.532	1694	TCM3-C recovery
05/27/2021	12:42	Seamon E	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.529	1695	TCM-3D recovery
05/27/2021	13:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17.411	W 032 16.440	1647	Arrival at the elevator
05/27/2021	13:22	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.521	1690	SEAMON is in sight
05/27/2021	13:25	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.527	1687	PBT1 deposit at the foot of the Eiffel Tower
05/27/2021	13:27	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.527	1678	SEAMON is, TEMPO and its slatted floor
05/27/2021	13:43	Seamon E	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.542	1699	Entering TEMPO
05/27/2021	13:55	Seamon E	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.533	1699	Hydroctopus disconnection
05/27/2021	13:55	Seamon E	N 37 17.321	W 032 16.532	1698	Hydroctopus disconnected
05/27/2021	14:14	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.536	1695	Storage of TEMPO on SEAMON and
05/27/2021	14:18	Seamon E	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.538	1695	Locking one side TEMPO
05/27/2021	14:19	Seamon E	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.538	1694	Environment module recovered and installed in the gray grating of SEAMON is
05/27/2021	14:23	Seamon E	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.536	1685	TCM in sight at the base of the Eiffel Tower
05/27/2021	14:27	Seamon E	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1678	Clearance of the thermometer chain
05/27/2021	14:41	Seamon E	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.527	1685	Retrieving the end of the thermometer chain
05/27/2021	15:49	Seamon E	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.539	1699	Successful hooking up of the end of the thermometer chain
05/27/2021	15:49	Seamon E	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.539	1696	TEMPO on SEAMON is
05/27/2021	15:54	Seamon E	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.531	1692	AISICS summit view
05/27/2021	15:57	Seamon E	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.533	1694	LSTE8 microbial colonizer recovery
05/27/2021	16:07	Seamon E	N 37 17.315	W 032 16.525	1707	PBT1 deposit next to Hydroctopus
05/27/2021	16:10	Seamon E	N 37 17.307	W 032 16.546	1699	End of dive

7.2.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/27/2021	11:05	Seamon W	N 37 17,468	W 032 16.783	1744	SEAMON W station off
05/27/2021	12:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.378	W 032 16.555	1692	TCM3-1 recovery
05/27/2021	12:38	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.532	1694	TCM3-C recovery
05/27/2021	12:42	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.529	1695	TCM3-D recovery
05/27/2021	14:27	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.535	1678	Clearance of the thermometer chain
05/27/2021	15:57	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.533	1694	LSTE8 microbial colonizer recovery

7.2.4. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1990-2	20210527T102512.851	00:16:26	Lucky strike
PL1990-2	20210527T110317.916	00:03:23	Seamon W
PL1990-2	20210527T120925.053	00:00:09	Seamon W
PL1990-2	20210527T123818.181	00:21:19	Eiffel Tower
PL1990-2	20210527T140618.213	00:29:59	Seamon E
PL1990-2	20210527T143618.219	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL1990-2	20210527T150618.227	00:29:58	Eiffel Tower
PL1990-2	20210527T153618.224	00:27:22	Eiffel Tower

7.2.5. Navigation

7.3. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1991-3

Friday, May 28, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	
DEPLOYMENT floated Seamon E	N37 ° 17.3277	W32 ° 16.5594	
Launch time	11:08	Time of arrival at the bottom	12:06
Time of departure from the bottom	17:42	Nautile time on board	18:34
Pilot	Franck Rosazza	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h36
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Celine Rommevaux		

7.3.1. Objectives

Objectives: CISICS storage, Seamon E lockpicking, Eiffel Tower north iron mat

Useful contact details:

SEAMON E	N 37 ° 17.306	W 32 ° 16.539	1705
AISICS	N 37 ° 17.338	W 32 ° 16.531	1692
BIOLUCKY	N 37 ° 17.352	W 32 ° 16.538	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

PBT2, PBT3, PBT4	Blue basket	3Tis	
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Mounted basket

PBT1, PBT2	Nautile basket HTWN probe	3Tis	Probes in blue basket
Biolucky			

Instrumentation

PIF / CHEMINI	PLUME - 4 bags of 2L	Aspi bowls	
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ASC2 configuration

ASC lowering basket			Already at the bottom
Ascended basket	2 current meters, Biolucky, PBT3 and PBT4	4 current meters	

7.3.2. Summary of operations

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/28/2021	12:02	Lucky strike	N 37 17,187	W 032 16.550		DIVE 1991-3
05/28/2021	12:03	Lucky strike	N 37 17,185	W 032 16.550		PLUME start-up, drain channel 1
05/28/2021	12:07	Lucky strike	N 37 17.160	W 032 16.539	1684	PLUME sampling Pocket 2 for 4 min
05/28/2021	12:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17,192	W 032 16.556	1675	End of PLUME sampling pocket 2
05/28/2021	12:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.199	W 032 16.551	1680	Beginning of PLUME sampling Pocket 3
05/28/2021	12:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.232	W 032 16.538	1705	End of PLUME sampling Pocket 3
05/28/2021	12:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.232	W 032 16.538	1705	Approaching Seamon Est and CISICS
05/28/2021	12:42	AISICS	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.527	1695	HTWN011 probe in Nautile basket

05/28/2021	12:52	AISICS	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.530	1696	CISICS colonizer module recovery
05/28/2021	13:12	Seamon E	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.529	1700	CISICS depot at Seamon Est station
05/28/2021	13:40	AISICS	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.520	1693	Arrival on AISICS
05/28/2021	13:50	AISICS	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.519	1695	Chimney sample 1:54 p.m. in PBT4
05/28/2021	13:53	AISICS	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.522	1696	sampling chimney young the first we had not taken anything
05/28/2021	14:03	AISICS	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.526	1694	Old chimney sample in PBT3
05/28/2021	14:09	AISICS	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.525	1695	Temperature measurement in the chimney: max temperature 304 ° C
05/28/2021	14:15	AISICS	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.524	1695	Ti3 syringe withdrawal
05/28/2021	14:19	AISICS	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.524	1695	Ti2 sampling
05/28/2021	14:28	AISICS	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.523	1696	Ti1 sample
05/28/2021	14:38	Seamon E	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.525	1703	deposit bags of shot around the station to locate its position
05/28/2021	14:53	Seamon E	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.545	1695	Arrival on the float, release beacon
05/28/2021	15:30	Seamon E	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.526	1702	Lockpicking at the floating station
05/28/2021	15:31	Lucky strike	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.525	1699	We go to the elevator to drop off the two boxes PBT3 and PBT4
05/28/2021	16:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 16.449	1650	Asc dropped
05/28/2021	16:32	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.535	1684	Arrival on the NTE-FeOx iron mat area
05/28/2021	16:34	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.539	1685	and seen on Biolucky
05/28/2021	16:36	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.540	1688	PLUME purge
05/28/2021	16:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.533	1692	Temperature outlet 4,70 ° C
05/28/2021	16:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.534	1692	PLUME Sampling Pocket 5 for 4 min
05/28/2021	16:48	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.530	1693	End of PLUME sampling Pocket 5
05/28/2021	16:56	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.529	1693	NTE-FeOx carpet sampling in PBT2
05/28/2021	17:12	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.533	1689	Biolucky Recovery
05/28/2021	17:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.534	1686	HTNKE 30015 probe recovery
05/28/2021	17:16	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.533	1686	HTNKE 30015 probe in basket
05/28/2021	17:17	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.534	1686	End of the dive we put our arms in and we will reach the release position for ascent

7.3.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/28/2021	12:52	AISICS	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.530	1696	CISICS colonizer module recovery
05/28/2021	12:42	AISICS	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.527	1686	HTWN011 probe in Nautilie basket
05/28/2021	17:12	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.533	1689	Biolucky Recovery
05/28/2021	17:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.534	1686	HTNKE 30015 probe recovery

7.3.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/28/2021	13:50	AISICS	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.519	1686	Chimney sample 1:54 p.m. PBT4
05/28/2021	14:03	AISICS	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.526	1694	Old chimney sample PBT3
05/28/2021	16:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.534	1692	PLUME Sampling Pocket 5 for 4 min
05/28/2021	16:56	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.529	1693	NTE-FeOx PBT2 carpet sampling

7.3.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1991-3	20210528T114141.81	00:00:05	Water column
PL1991-3	20210528T124804.312	00:01:16	AISICS
PL1991-3	20210528T134705.531	00:00:51	AISICS

PL1991-3	20210528T164748.141	01:00:08	TE North iron mat
PL1991-3	20210528T170618.172	00:00:36	Eiffel Tower North
PL1991-3	20210528T171045.025	00:01:25	Eiffel Tower North

7.3.6. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - Optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/28/2021	16:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.533	1692	Temperature outlet 4,70 ° C

7.3.7. Navigation

7.4. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1992-4

Saturday May 29, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.4833	W32 ° 17.1883	
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.3085	W32 ° 16.4845	
Launch time	09:58	Time of arrival at the bottom	
Time of departure from the bottom	11:36	Nautile time on board	12:31
Pilot	Julien Fenouil	Duration of operations on the bottom	0h
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Mathilde Cannat		

7.4.1. Objectives

Objectives: Recovery of temperature sensors White Castle, South Crystal, Cypress

Useful contact details:

South crystal	37 ° 17.43531	32 ° 16.93107	1724
Cypress	37 ° 17.43915	32 ° 16.86419	1742
White castle	37 ° 17.38747	32 ° 16.863879	1710

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

3 tis	Blue basket (empty) and green basket (6 or 7 small probes) + marker	Large probes HTW005 + HTWN019	PBT1

Mounted basket

3 tis	Blue basket (5 small probes) and green basket (empty)	Large probes HTWN021, HTW010 + HTWXX?	PBT1
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ASC3 configuration

Basket 1 ASC descent	PBT3	3 Tis	Reversal thermometer
Basket 1 ASC mounted	PBT1	3 Tis	
Basket 2 ASC descent (board)	DEAFS		
Basket 2 ASC mounted (board)	Gratings	TCM3-3?	

7.4.2. DIVE schedule:

Time	Site	Operations
		Technical problem Nautile - canceled dive

7.5. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1993-5

DIVE RECORDING PROBLEM

Sunday May 30, 2021

Nautilie mooring position	N37 ° 17.4833	W32 ° 17.1883	
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.3085	W32 ° 16.4845	
Launch time	10:22	Time of arrival at the bottom	11:08
Time of departure from the bottom	17:05	Nautilie time on board	18:00
Pilot	Julien Fenouil	Duration of operations on the bottom	5:57
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Mathilde Cannat		

7.5.1. Objectives

Objectives: Recovery of temperature sensors White Castle, South Crystal, Cypress

Useful contact details:

South crystal	37 ° 17.43531	32 ° 16.93107	1724	
Cypress	37 ° 17.43915	32 ° 16.86419	1742	
White castle	37 ° 17.38747	32 ° 16.863879	1710	

Nautilie configuration

Descent basket

3 tis	Blue basket (empty) and green basket (6 small probes) + marker	Large probes HTW005 + HTWN019	PBT1
Shot bag			

Mounted basket

3 tis	Blue basket and green basket (empty) - 9 small probes	Large probes HTWN021, HTW010	PBT1
		+ HTW019?	

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls			
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7.5.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/30/2021	08:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17,296	W 032 16.554		
05/30/2021	11:08	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Basically
05/30/2021	11:23	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Arrival on Seamon East
05/30/2021	11:25	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Shot bag 1 removed
05/30/2021	11:29	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		shot bag 2 removed
05/30/2021	11:30	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		shot bag 3 removed
05/30/2021	11:30	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		shot bag 4 removed
05/30/2021	11:37	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTnke 30005 removed
05/30/2021	11:38	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		LTgrad12 removed
05/30/2021	11:42	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Overview for Seamon E float cable tracking
05/30/2021	11:45	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Departure for White Castle
05/30/2021	12:08	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		The WC smoking building
05/30/2021	12:10	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Cracked slab to the west of the site
05/30/2021	12:23	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTW010 removed

05/30/2021	12:33	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Nautilie temperature measurement
05/30/2021	12:34	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		The maximum temperature is 310 ° C
05/30/2021	12:43	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti1 triggered
05/30/2021	12:54	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti 2 triggered
05/30/2021	13:00	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti 3 released
05/30/2021	13:12	White Castel	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTW005 posed
05/30/2021	13:31	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTnke 29008 fallen out of its crack
05/30/2021	13:33	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTnke 29008 recovered and in shopping cart
05/30/2021	13:38	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Mold cracks just a little lower
05/30/2021	13:40	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Zoom in on these cracks
05/30/2021	13:43	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Clearly visible moire outputs
05/30/2021	13:43	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Zoom with crab
05/30/2021	13:44	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		And prawns
05/30/2021	13:46	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTnke 29009 probe installed but not ideal positioning
05/30/2021	13:49	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Taken MOM21-193-5 fragment of hydrothermal deposit
05/30/2021	13:54	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Repositioning HTnke 29009 zoom
05/30/2021	13:59	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE29009 asked
05/30/2021	14:12	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTWN021 cannula, bacterial mats and small molds
05/30/2021	14:16	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTWN021 retrieved
05/30/2021	14:26	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Future HTWN019 installation site, detail
05/30/2021	14:29	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Installation of HTWN019 not endal ...
05/30/2021	14:53	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE38003 asked
05/30/2021	14:54	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTWN019 replaced
05/30/2021	15:07	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Arrival under the top of the site
05/30/2021	15:07	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		View of the White Castle building
05/30/2021	15:24	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		T NAUT socket 5.3 ° C
05/30/2021	15:26	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		End measure T Nautilie
05/30/2021	15:30	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Installation HTNKE38002
05/30/2021	15:41	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		South Crystal, HTW019 has fallen. The PA4 colonization module is visible just to the west
05/30/2021	16:04	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		South crystal
05/30/2021	16:04	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		South Crystal view
05/30/2021	16:10	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE29006 in shopping cart
05/30/2021	16:11	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Retrieve LTW013
05/30/2021	16:15	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		LTW017 posed
05/30/2021	16:21	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE 30002 posed
05/30/2021	16:37	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE 29017 is near one of those mold cracks, under the bulge

7.5.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/30/2021	11:37	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE 30005 Recovery
05/30/2021	11:38	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		LTgrad12 Recovery
05/30/2021	12:23	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Recovery HTW010
05/30/2021	13:12	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTW005 posed
05/30/2021	13:33	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE 29008 Recovery
05/30/2021	13:54	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Installation HTNKE 29009
05/30/2021	14:16	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Recovery HTWN021
05/30/2021	14:53	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE38003 probe installation
05/30/2021	14:54	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTWN019 replaced
05/30/2021	15:30	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Installation HTNKE38002
05/30/2021	15:41	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Recovery HTW019
05/30/2021	16:10	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Recovery HTNKE29006
05/30/2021	16:11	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		LTW013 Recovery

05/30/2021	16:15	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Installation LTW017
05/30/2021	16:21	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Installation HTNKE 30002
05/30/2021	16:37	South crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		HTNKE 29017 Recovery

7.5.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/30/2021	12:43	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti1 triggered
05/30/2021	12:54	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti2 triggered
05/30/2021	13:00	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti3 released

7.5.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1993-5	20210530T112350.321	00:08:50	Seamon E
PL1993-5	20210530T113505.267	00:20:04	Eiffel Tower
PL1993-5	20210530T120721.459	00:29:59	Lucky Strike West
PL1993-5	20210530T123721.46	00:13:04	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T125155.261	00:03:25	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T130003.152	00:03:51	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T130837.204	00:10:49	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T132402.348	00:17:00	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T134106.364	00:10:41	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T142152.63	00:11:18	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T143319.296	00:29:59	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T150319.304	00:05:52	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T151051.655	00:12:27	White castle
PL1993-5	20210530T152322.741	00:14:59	Lucky strike
PL1993-5	20210530T153955.556	00:16:57	Lucky strike
PL1993-5	20210530T155700.199	00:24:59	South crystal
PL1993-5	20210530T162202.247	00:01:21	South crystal
PL1993-5	20210530T162332.344	00:01:24	South crystal
PL1993-5	20210530T162625.689	00:02:04	South crystal
PL1993-5	20210530T163306.432	00:07:52	South crystal
PL1993-5	20210530T164858.387	00:09:52	South crystal

7.5.6. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - Optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
05/30/2021	12:33	White castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Nautilie temperature measurement
05/30/2021	15:24	Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		T NAUT socket 5.3 ° C

7.5.7. Navigation

7.6. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1994-6

Monday, May 31, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	
Launch time	09:39	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:33
Time of departure from the bottom	16:31	Nautile time on board	17:33
Pilot	Olivier Fauvin	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h58
Co-pilot	Franck Rosazza		
Observer	Alain Castillo		

7.6.1. Objectives

Objectives: Short DEAFS deployment, probe recovery and sampling

Useful contact details:

DEAFS	37 ° 17.531N	32 ° 16.539W		
CL PA3 position	37 ° 17.344N	32 ° 16.556W	1697	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

PBT2	3 tis		2 core barrels

Mounted basket

PBT1, PBT2	3 tis	big probe	2 core barrels

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls			
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ASC3 configuration (bottom)

Basket 1 ASC descent	PBT3	3 Tis
Basket 1 ASC mounted	PBT3	3 Tis
Basket 2 ASC descent (board)	DEAFS	
Basket 2 ASC mounted (board)	Gratings	DEAFS

7.6.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm.	Operations
05/31/2021	10:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17,271	W 032 16.564	1695	Get to the bottom
05/31/2021	10:48	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.552	1696	Approaching Montségur for spotting
05/31/2021	10:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.294	W 032 16.535	1700	Recalibration request by Nautile, difficulty in locating.
05/31/2021	11:09	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.536	1702	Arrival on Montségur.
05/31/2021	11:20	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.536	1703	The spotting is endished, we agree on where to put DEAFS.
05/31/2021	11:20	Montsegur	N 37 17.274	W 032 16.540	1702	Grating and bags of shot on the former DEAFS site: ExDEAFS.
05/31/2021	11:26	Hydroctopus	N 37 17.318	W 032 16.522	1705	PBT1 picked up on the ground.
05/31/2021	11:28	Lucky strike	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.518	1704	Transit Lift to take DEAFS.
05/31/2021	11:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17.308	W 032 16.483	1682	Lift.

05/31/2021	11:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.540	1700	Return to Montségur.
05/31/2021	11:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.540	1700	Grating on ExDEAFS.
05/31/2021	12:05	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.536	1705	DEAFS posed.
05/31/2021	12:10	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.537	1705	DEAFS in place on its site.
05/31/2021	12:12	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.536	1705	Shot bag laid.
05/31/2021	12:15	Montsegur	N 37 17,273	W 032 16.536	1703	The position is validated, we continue operations.
05/31/2021	12:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1704	Start of Temperature measurement with TNaut Probe.
05/31/2021	12:32	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.534	1704	Temperature measured with TNaut probe: 260 ° C. We are below the values measured by the IPGP T ° probes, undoubtedly hampered by the bell.
05/31/2021	12:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.534	1705	Ti syringe trigger n ° 3: M21FLU07
05/31/2021	12:38	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.534	1705	Adjusted bell.
05/31/2021	12:39	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1705	DEAFS is in place.
05/31/2021	12:51	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.534	1704	Top of the chimney in PBT1.
05/31/2021	12:55	Montsegur	N 37 17.327	W 032 15.084	1705	Nautile repositioned itself in order to take the lower part of the chimney in PBT2
05/31/2021	13:00	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.537	1705	Croc "lower part" of the chimney in PBT2.
05/31/2021	13:07	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.537	1706	Temperature measurement with TNaut probe on exDEAFS
05/31/2021	13:10	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.536	1706	Temperature measured by TNaut probe: 273 ° C.
05/31/2021	13:14	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.538	1705	Ti syringe withdrawal n ° 2: M21FLU08.
05/31/2021	13:19	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.536	1706	Ti sample n ° 1 M21FLU09 carried out.
05/31/2021	14:10	Lucky strike	N 37 17.306	W 032 16.472	1704	DEAFS in elevator.
05/31/2021	14:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17.302	W 032 16.474	1683	Elevator dropped.
05/31/2021	14:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17.302	W 032 16.474	1683	Transit to Eiffel Tower north.
05/31/2021	14:55	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.525	1687	Arrived on Eiffel Tower North.
05/31/2021	15:03	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.526	1687	HTW008 probe extracted from the smoker.
05/31/2021	15:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.529	1685	Measured temperature: 320 ° C.
05/31/2021	15:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.525	1686	Ti syringe trigger n ° 5: M21FLU10
05/31/2021	15:29	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.529	1685	Ti syringe trigger n ° 6: M21FLU11
05/31/2021	15:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.529	1684	Ti syringe trigger n ° 4: M21FLU12
05/31/2021	15:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.546	1696	LTgrad2 recovery.
05/31/2021	15:46	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.545	1696	LTW018 recovery.
05/31/2021	15:54	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.552	1701	Marker placed on site LTgrad10.
05/31/2021	15:55	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.552	1702	LTgrad10 probe recovery.
05/31/2021	16:06	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.554	1701	LTnke26004 recovery.
05/31/2021	16:07	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1700	LTgrad9 probe recovery.
05/31/2021	16:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.550	1684	End of dive 1994-6.

7.6.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm.	Operations
05/31/2021	12:10	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.537	1701	DEAFS in place on its site.
05/31/2021	14:10	Lucky strike	N 37 17.306	W 032 16.472	1704	DEAFS in elevator.
05/31/2021	15:03	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.526	1687	HTW008 probe extracted from the smoker.
05/31/2021	15:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.546	1696	LTgrad2 recovery.
05/31/2021	15:46	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.545	1696	LTW018 recovery.
05/31/2021	15:55	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.552	1702	LTgrad10 probe recovery.
05/31/2021	16:06	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.554	1701	LTnke26004 recovery.
05/31/2021	16:07	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1700	LTgrad9 probe recovery.

7.6.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm.	Operations
05/31/2021	12:35	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.534	1705	Ti syringe n ° 3: M21FLU07
05/31/2021	13:14	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.538	1705	Ti syringe n ° 2: M21FLU08

05/31/2021	13:19	Montsegur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.536	1706	Ti syringe n ° 1 M21FLU09
05/31/2021	15:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.525	1686	Ti syringe n ° 5: M21FLU10
05/31/2021	15:29	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.529	1685	Ti syringe n ° 6: M21FLU11
05/31/2021	15:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.529	1684	Ti syringe n ° 4: M21FLU12
05/31/2021	12:51	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.534	1704	Top of the chimney in PBT1.
05/31/2021	13:00	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.537	1705	Croc "lower part" of the chimney in PBT2.

7.6.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1994-6	20210531T111914.529	00:18:46	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T113809.44	00:00:08	Lift
PL1994-6	20210531T115609.247	00:13:19	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T121027.186	00:09:22	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T122721.022	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T125721.043	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T132721.05	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T135721.053	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1994-6	20210531T142721.06	00:23:23	Lift
PL1994-6	20210531T145716.573	00:05:32	Eiffel Tower
PL1994-6	20210531T151627.628	00:01:25	Eiffel Tower
PL1994-6	20210531T154327.137	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL1994-6	20210531T161327.144	00:29:58	Eiffel Tower
PL1994-6	20210531T164327.157	00:04:57	Nautile

7.6.6. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm.	Operations
05/31/2021	12:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1705	Temperature measurement with TNaut probe.
05/31/2021	13:07	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.537	1706	Temperature measurement with TNaut probe on exDEAFS
05/31/2021	15:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.529	1685	Measured temperature: 320 ° C.

7.6.7. Navigation

7.7. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1995-7

Tuesday June 1, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.3085	W32 ° 16.4845	Eiffel Tower
Launch time	09:51	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:45
Time of departure from the bottom	16:46	Nautile time on board	17:40
Pilot	Julien Fenouil	Duration of operations on the bottom	6:01
Co-pilot	Loïc Bonnet		
Observer	Morgane Hubert		

7.7.1. Objectives

Objectives: Current recovery + TE probes, MERCES Montsegur manipulation

Useful contact details:

MONTSEGUR	N37 ° 17.28	W32 ° 16.534		
TCM3-2	N37 ° 17.302	W32 ° 16.538	1704	
TCM3-A	N37 ° 17.343	W32 ° 16.540	1694	
TCM3-B	N37 ° 17.34	W32 ° 16.534	1689	
CL PA1	N37 ° 17.296	W32 ° 16.524	1712	Two corers in the same place
TE probes is Itgrad4	N37 ° 17.444	W32 ° 16.927	1704	At the base of the Eiffel Tower site along the Hydroctopus cable
TE probes is Itgrad8	N37 ° 17.444	W32 ° 16.926	1704	
TE probes is degraded	N37 ° 17.342	W32 ° 16.545	1703	
TE probes is Itgrad7	N37 ° 17.340	W32 ° 16.522	1698	At the base of the building

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

2 Corers-Blades	Niskin	1 marker	

Mounted basket

2 Corers-Blades	3 HTNKE probes (average)	4 stake probes	1 LTW (small)

ASC4 configuration

ASC lowering basket	Reversal thermometer		
Ascended basket	TCM3-A & B and 2	Niskin	

7.7.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm	Operations
06/01/2021	10:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17.054	W 032 16.664		Arrival at the bottom
06/01/2021	11:08	Seamon E	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.535	1697	Niskin slammed
06/01/2021	11:15	Seamon E	N 37 17.321	W 032 16.543	1699	Retrieved HTNKE30014 probe
06/01/2021	11:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.540	1697	Retrieved HTNKE30012 probe
06/01/2021	11:24	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.536	1697	End of CHEMINIS calibration
06/01/2021	11:27	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.538	1691	TCM3-B recovered
06/01/2021	11:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.544	1692	TCM3-A recovered
06/01/2021	11:42	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,300	W 032 16.542	1701	TCM3-2 recovered

06/01/2021	11:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17,296	W 032 16.521	1701	Transit to elevator
06/01/2021	12:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.406	1701	Niskin in elevator
06/01/2021	12:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.410	1701	Triggering reversal thermometer
06/01/2021	12:18	Lucky strike	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.403	1701	Transit to Montségur
06/01/2021	12:55	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.533	1702	Manip MERCES
06/01/2021	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.538	1702	Beginning of Cheminis for PLUME A.LAES
06/01/2021	16:03	Montsegur	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.540	1702	PLUME 2 A. LAES
06/01/2021	16:18	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.537	1702	Start Cheminis for PLUME smoker A.LAES
06/01/2021	16:20	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.540	1702	Start PLUME3
06/01/2021	16:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.546	1702	Beginning of PLUME4, end of DIVE

7.7.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm	Operations
06/01/2021	11:15	Seamon E	N 37 17.321	W 032 16.543	1699	Retrieved HTNKE30014 probe
06/01/2021	11:21	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.540	1697	Retrieved HTNKE30012 probe
06/01/2021	11:27	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.538	1691	TCM3-B recovered
06/01/2021	11:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.544	1692	TCM3-A recovered
06/01/2021	11:42	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,300	W 032 16.542	1701	TCM3-2 recovered

7.7.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm	Operations
06/01/2021	11:08	Seamon E	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.535	1697	Niskin slammed
06/01/2021	12:57	Montsegur	N 37 17,254	W 032 16.527	1702	PIF sample C2a medium -4.690 ° C
06/01/2021	13:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.536	1702	PIF sample C2bcg medium
06/01/2021	13:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.532	1702	PIF sample R0 medium
06/01/2021	13:46	Montsegur	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.531	1702	PIF sample R1 medium
06/01/2021	14:06	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.531	1702	PIF sample R2cg medium
06/01/2021	14:21	Montsegur	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.532	1702	PIF sample C2acg medium
06/01/2021	14:32	Montsegur	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.530	1702	PIF sample C2b medium
06/01/2021	14:51	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.532	1702	PIF sample C1b medium
06/01/2021	15:09	Montsegur	N 37 17,293	W 032 16.535	1702	PIF sample C1bcg medium
06/01/2021	15:21	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.529	1702	PIF sample C1acg medium
06/01/2021	15:40	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.538	1702	PIF sample C1a medium
06/01/2021	16:03	Montsegur	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.540	1702	PLUME 2 A. LAES
06/01/2021	16:20	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.540	1702	PLUME3

7.7.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1995-7	20210601T110521.396	00:00:25	Seamon E
PL1995-7	20210601T110649.199	00:02:45	Seamon E
PL1995-7	20210601T114859.82	00:00:06	Transit
PL1995-7	20210601T122911.909	00:00:40	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T123437.012	00:00:56	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T123618.067	00:27:33	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T130356.915	00:13:35	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T131803.57	00:08:55	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T132805.621	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T135805.638	00:00:10	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T140550.86	00:11:24	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T145444.081	00:12:22	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T153328.103	00:00:01	Montsegur

PL1995-7	20210601T153330.561	00:29:56	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T160328.107	00:02:54	Montsegur
PL1995-7	20210601T161335.185	00:29:59	Montsegur

7.7.6. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat	Long	Imm	Operations
06/01/2021	12:57	Montsegur	N 37 17,254	W 032 16.527	1707	Chemini middle C2a
06/01/2021	13:05	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.534	1706	Chemini corner 1 C2a
06/01/2021	13:09	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.535	1706	Chemini corner 2 C2a
06/01/2021	13:14	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.536	1705	Chemini middle C2bcg
06/01/2021	13:20	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.536	1706	Chemini coin 1 C2bcg
06/01/2021	13:24	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.534	1703	Chemini coin 2 C2bcg
06/01/2021	13:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.532	1707	Chemini middle R0
06/01/2021	13:34	Montsegur	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.524	1706	Chemini corner 1 R0
06/01/2021	13:39	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1706	Chemini corner 2 R0
06/01/2021	13:47	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.530	1707	R1 middle rail
06/01/2021	13:52	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.528	1708	Corner rail 1 R1
06/01/2021	13:56	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.534	1709	Corner rail 2 R1
06/01/2021	14:06	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.531	1705	R2cg middle rail
06/01/2021	14:11	Montsegur	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.520	1704	Chemini corner 1 R2cg
06/01/2021	14:15	Montsegur	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.532	1705	Chemini corner 2 R2cg
06/01/2021	14:21	Montsegur	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.532	1705	C2acg middle track
06/01/2021	14:26	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.534	1704	Chemini corner 1 C2acg
06/01/2021	14:30	Montsegur	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.533	1703	Chemini corner 2 C2acg
06/01/2021	14:34	Montsegur	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.529	1705	C2b pathways
06/01/2021	14:39	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.531	1704	Chemini corner 1 C2b
06/01/2021	14:43	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.531	1704	Chemini corner 2 C2b
06/01/2021	14:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.532	1702	C1b middle path
06/01/2021	14:57	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.531	1702	Chemini corner 1 C1b
06/01/2021	15:01	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.533	1702	Chemini corner 2 C1b
06/01/2021	15:09	Montsegur	N 37 17,293	W 032 16.535	1703	C1bcg middle path
06/01/2021	15:13	Montsegur	N 37 17.295	W 032 16.530	1701	Chemini corner 1 C1bcg
06/01/2021	15:17	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.526	1704	Chemini corner 2 C1bcg
06/01/2021	15:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.528	1707	C1acg middle path
06/01/2021	15:27	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.528	1707	Chemini corner 1 C1acg
06/01/2021	15:31	Montsegur	N 37 17.299	W 032 16.528	1706	Chemini corner 2 C1acg
06/01/2021	15:40	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.538	1704	Middle path C1a
06/01/2021	15:44	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.546	1705	Chemini corner 1 C1a
06/01/2021	15:48	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.540	1706	Chemini corner 2 C1a
06/01/2021	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.538	1705	Chemini for PLUME A.LAES

7.7.7. Navigation

7.8. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1996-8

Wednesday, June 2, 2021

Nautilie mooring position	N37 ° 17.245	W32 ° 15.845	Capelinhos
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.313	W32 ° 15.736	Capelinhos
Launch time	09:35	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:30
Time of departure from the bottom	16:28	Nautilie time on board	17:21
Pilot	Franck Rosazza	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h58
Co-pilot	Olivier Fauvin		
Observer	Jozée Sarrazin		

7.8.1. Objectives

Objectives: Capelinhos sampling: chimney, iron mat, fluid and corer. Exchange of HTW probe and colonizer

Useful contact details:

T ° C probe position HTW004	N37 ° 17.357	W32 ° 15.833	1660	
CL PA2 position	N37 17.415	W32 15.806	1684	
Position iron rich carpet	N37 ° 17.360	W32 ° 15.829	1669	Cap 264
Colonizing position	N37 ° 17.371	W32 ° 15.831	1668	Cap 243
Mold position	N37 ° 17.369	W32 ° 15.843	1663	Cap 48

Nautilie configuration

Descent basket

PBT1 & PBT2	3 tis	Big probe HTW019	2 Core sampler

Mounted basket

PBT3 & PBT4 (LSCap4)	3 tis	Large probe HTW004	2 Core sampler
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Instrumentation

3 PLUME pockets of 2L	Aspi Bowls		
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ASC5 configuration

Basket 1 descent: PBT3 & PBT4 (LSCap5)	Basket 2 descent: DEEP SEEDS module
Basket 1 mounted: PBT1 & PBT2	Basket 2 ascent:

7.8.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/02/2021	10:28	Lucky strike	N 37 17,192	W 032 15.898	1687	Arrival at the bottom! 1687m
06/02/2021	10:29	Lucky strike	N 37 17,192	W 032 15.899	1690	Plume purge and sample, channel 2. T ° C 4.5
06/02/2021	10:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17,230	W 032 15.895	1690	PLUME sample, channel 3. T ° C 4.5. Purge 4.
06/02/2021	10:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17,241	W 032 15.891	1688	Transit Capelinhos
06/02/2021	10:45	Capelinhos	N 37 17.352	W 032 15.843	1668	Arrival Capelinhos
06/02/2021	10:58	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.831	1662	PBT2 chimney sampling
06/02/2021	11:13	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.829	1663	Temperature measurement in the small smoker. 102.9 ° C
06/02/2021	11:18	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.833	1663	Ti3 tripping at 11:18 a.m.
06/02/2021	11:20	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.833	1663	Ti2 trigger
06/02/2021	11:24	Capelinhos	N 37 17.360	W 032 15.828	1663	Ti1 trip
06/02/2021	11:36	Capelinhos	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.831	1664	Sample small flange covered with anhydrite in PBT1
06/02/2021	11:51	Capelinhos	N 37 17.361	W 032 15.833	1665	Insertion of the HTW019 probe
06/02/2021	11:58	Capelinhos	N 37 17.364	W 032 15.832	1663	Retrieving the HTW004

06/02/2021	12:10	Lucky strike	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.826	1668	Start of transit to PA2 core drilling site
06/02/2021	12:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17.413	W 032 15.809	1690	We decide to do the corers without having found the PA2 site
06/02/2021	12:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 15.812	1689	CL7 performed
06/02/2021	12:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 15.812	1689	CL6 performed
06/02/2021	12:58	Lucky strike	N 37 17.413	W 032 15.813	1683	Transit to ASC
06/02/2021	13:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17.286	W 032 15.737	1680	Launch of the reversal thermometer. Bottom T ° C 4.57
06/02/2021	13:44	Lucky strike	N 37 17.292	W 032 15.741	1677	ASC ready to drop
06/02/2021	13:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17.294	W 032 15.745	1679	Transit to Capelinhos
06/02/2021	13:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.825	1671	Arrival Capelinhos
06/02/2021	14:18	Capelinhos	N 37 17.365	W 032 15.827	1674	T ° C measurement and PLUME sampling 5. T ° C measured start of sampling 4.61 ° C, end of sampling 4.74
06/02/2021	14:32	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.828	1672	First bite iron mat in PBT3
06/02/2021	14:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.370	W 032 15.829	1670	3rd bite iron mat in PBT3
06/02/2021	14:42	Lucky strike	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.826	1670	4th bite iron mat in PBT3
06/02/2021	14:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.823	1676	PBT4 recovery in Nautilé basket with LSCAP5 microbial colonizer to deploy
06/02/2021	15:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1672	Beautiful view of the LSCAP4 colonizer before recovery
06/02/2021	15:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.830	1671	LSCAP4 recovery
06/02/2021	15:05	Lucky strike	N 37 17.369	W 032 15.831	1670	LSCAP5 deployment
06/02/2021	15:07	Lucky strike	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.829	1670	LSCAP 5 in place
06/02/2021	15:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.367	W 032 15.828	1673	We take DEEP SEEDS back to deploy it
06/02/2021	15:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.365	W 032 15.827	1671	We go in search of a mussel bed
06/02/2021	15:41	Lucky strike	N 37 17.374	W 032 15.835	1666	Fireplace covered with iron carpet
06/02/2021	15:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17.375	W 032 15.837	1662	Small dish with live mussels
06/02/2021	15:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.377	W 032 15.844	1663	** Future Jozée sampling area
06/02/2021	15:56	Lucky strike	N 37 17.370	W 032 15.832	1672	DEEP SEEDS deployment
06/02/2021	15:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.831	1671	Opening the larvae trap
06/02/2021	15:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1669	DEEP SEEDS in position
06/02/2021	16:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.839	1660	Aspi bowl 1 shrimp
06/02/2021	16:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.840	1660	Aspi bowl 2
06/02/2021	16:12	Lucky strike	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.839	1660	Aspi bowl 3
06/02/2021	16:22	Lucky strike	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.789	1640	End of dive

7.8.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/02/2021	11:58	Capelinhos	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.832	1663	HTW019 probe installation
06/02/2021	11:58	Capelinhos	N 37 17.364	W 032 15.832	1663	Retrieving the HTW004
06/02/2021	15:04	Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.830	1671	LSCAP4 recovery
06/02/2021	15:07	Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.829	1670	LSCAP 5 in place
06/02/2021	15:59	Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1669	DEEP SEEDS in position

7.8.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/02/2021	10:29	Lucky strike	N 37 17,192	W 032 15.899	1691	PLUME, channel 2. T ° C 4.5
06/02/2021	10:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17,230	W 032 15.895	1691	PLUME, channel 3. T ° C 4.5.
06/02/2021	10:58	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.831	1663	PBT2 chimney sampling
06/02/2021	11:18	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.833	1663	Ti3 tripping at 11:18 a.m.
06/02/2021	11:20	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.833	1663	Ti2 trigger
06/02/2021	11:24	Capelinhos	N 37 17.360	W 032 15.828	1663	Ti1 trip
06/02/2021	11:36	Capelinhos	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.831	1664	Small "flange" sample covered with anhydrite in the PBT1
06/02/2021	12:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 15.812	1689	CL7 core sampler completed
06/02/2021	12:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 15.812	1689	CL6 core sampler completed

06/02/2021	14:32	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.828	1672	Iron mat sampling in PBT3
06/02/2021	16:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.839	1660	Aspi bowl 1 shrimp
06/02/2021	16:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.840	1660	Aspi bowl 2
06/02/2021	16:12	Lucky strike	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.839	1660	Aspi bowl 3

7.8.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1996-8	20210602T101004.997	00:00:04	Pump
PL1996-8	20210602T104140.236	00:29:59	Transit
PL1996-8	20210602T111140.241	00:29:59	Capelinhos
PL1996-8	20210602T114140.259	00:01:04	Capelinhos
PL1996-8	20210602T114250.531	00:28:32	Capelinhos
PL1996-8	20210602T135835.19	00:29:59	Capelinhos
PL1996-8	20210602T142835.192	00:21:12	Capelinhos iron carpet
PL1996-8	20210602T152443.592	00:04:57	Capelinhos
PL1996-8	20210602T153224.149	00:29:59	Capelinhos
PL1996-8	20210602T160224.162	00:08:05	Capelinhos

7.8.6. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/02/2021	11:13	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.829	1663	Temperature measurement in the small smoker. 102.9 ° C
06/02/2021	13:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17.286	W 032 15.737	1680	Launch of the reversal thermometer. Bottom T ° C 4.57

7.8.7. Navigation

7.9. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1997-9

Thursday June 3, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.344	W32 ° 16.3396	North
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.435	W32 ° 16.514	Y3 / Sintra
Launch time	09:38	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:40
Time of departure from the bottom	16:42	Nautile time on board	17:37
Pilot	Franck Rosazza	Duration of operations on the bottom	6:02
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Lise Artigue		

7.9.1. Objectives

Objectives: Chimney / iron mat / titanium sample Y3 and Sintra, MERCES inactive

Useful contact details:

Y3	N37 ° 17.52	W32 ° 16.665	1729	
Sintra HTNKE30011	N37 ° 17.3412	W32 ° 16.529	1614	
Sintra inactive (I1 & I2)	N37 ° 17.475 '	W32 ° 16.503	1642	
Y3 iron mat	N37 ° 17.518	W32 ° 16.663	1725	
West Sintra Iron Carpet	N37 ° 17.533	W32 ° 16.507	1700	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

3ti	PBT1, PBT2, PBT3	HTNK30015	

Mounted basket

3ti	PBT2, PBT3, PBT4	HTNKE30011	

Instrumentation

PLUME 2 pockets	Aspi Bowls	Chemini / PIF	
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Configuration ASC6

Basket 1 descent: 3ti, PBT4	Basket 2 descent:
Basket 1 ascent: 3ti, PBT1	Basket 2 ascent:

7.9.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Locality	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/04/2021	10:41	Lucky strike	N 37 17,276	W 032 16.322	1696	Arrival at the bottom
06/04/2021	11:06	Y3	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.659	1727	Arrival on Y3
06/04/2021	11:16	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.662	1733	Sampling upper part of the Y3 chimney
06/04/2021	11:33	Y3	N 37 17.505	W 032 16.663	1730	Sampling of the lower part (sulphide) of the Y3 chimney
06/04/2021	11:41	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.673	1729	Temperature measurement with the Nautile temperature probe
06/04/2021	11:43	Y3	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.671	1729	Temperature measured at 319 ° C
06/04/2021	11:52	Y3	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.666	1732	Ti syringe trigger n ° 1 at 11:52:17
06/04/2021	12:03	Y3	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.674	1729	Ti syringe trigger n ° 2 at 12:03:23
06/04/2021	12:07	Y3	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.668	1731	Ti syringe trigger n ° 3 at 12:07:18
06/04/2021	12:14	Y3	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.659	1733	Arrival on FeOx Y3 microbial mat at 12:14:58

06/04/2021	12:40	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.665	1735	Chemini (the voucher) sample starts at 12:40:15
06/04/2021	12:44	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.666	1731	Beginning of PLUME sampling 2 bags of 2L for 4min30s from 12:44:37. Temperature = 4.940 ° C.
06/04/2021	12:51	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.673	1736	Start of sample handling microbial mat Y3 in PBT3 at 12:51:01
06/04/2021	13:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.655	1714	Transit to elevator
06/04/2021	13:20	Lucky strike	N 37 17,423	W 032 16.508	1665	Arrival Lift at 13:20:42
06/04/2021	13:28	Lucky strike	N 37 17,425	W 032 16.500	1666	Exchanges of Ti 1,2, and 3 syringes with 4, 5 and 6.
06/04/2021	13:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17,422	W 032 16.500	1665	Exchange PBT1 with PBT4
06/04/2021	13:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17,426	W 032 16.502	1664	End of Elevator. Departure. Transit to Sintra inactive.
06/04/2021	14:12	Sintra	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.548	1657	Arrival of inactive quadrats at 14:12:00.
06/04/2021	14:25	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.544	1656	MANip MERCES on I1 and I2 quadrats, Sintra inactive
06/04/2021	15:00	Sintra	N 37 17.519	W 032 16.538	1641	Transit to Sintra active.
06/04/2021	15:10	Sintra	N 37 17.528	W 032 16.513	1627	Arrival in active Sintra.
06/04/2021	15:16	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.506	1622	HTNKE 30011 probe recovery.
06/04/2021	15:24	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.502	1620	Temperature measurement where the HTNKE 30011 probe was. Temperature = 5.9 ° C. Not high enough for titanium syringes or to replace a temperature probe.
06/04/2021	15:37	Sintra	N 37 17.533	W 032 16.494	1622	Temperature measurement with T Naut probe from 15:37:10. Maximum temperature measured = 221 ° C.
06/04/2021	15:40	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.496	1621	Trigger Ti syringe n ° 4 at 15:40:21.
06/04/2021	15:41	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Ti syringe sampling trigger n ° 5 at 15:41:58.
06/04/2021	15:43	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Triggering Ti syringe n ° 6 at 15:43:47.
06/04/2021	15:47	Sintra	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.496	1620	HTNKE 30015 probe removed. End of manip.
06/04/2021	15:52	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Aspi bowl 1 current shrimp.
06/04/2021	16:09	Sintra	N 37 17.505	W 032 16.575	1667	Arrival on Sintra West microbial mat.
06/04/2021	16:16	Sintra	N 37 17,498	W 032 16.571	1668	Temperature measurement with TNaut probe. Max temperature = 7.160 ° C.
06/04/2021	16:18	Sintra	N 37 17,499	W 032 16.571	1668	Start of Chemini measurement at 4:18 p.m. with purge 1 min then Fe and S measurements.
06/04/2021	16:20	Sintra	N 37 17,499	W 032 16.571	1669	Beginning of PLUME 4 bag sampling. Purge 3, PLUME 4 bag sampling for 4min30s. Purge 5. Temperature during sampling = 5.160 ° C.
06/04/2021	16:29	Sintra	N 37 17,500	W 032 16.570	1669	Sampling of microbial mats placed in PBT4.
06/04/2021	16:34	Lucky strike	N 37 17,497	W 032 16.570	1661	End of DIVE PL-1997-9. Planning operations carried out in full. Result: no particular problems except the front PIF / Chemini sampling pump turns jerkily.

7.9.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Locality	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/04/2021	15:16	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.506	1622	HTNKE 30011 probe recovery.
06/04/2021	15:47	Sintra	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.496	1620	HTNKE 30015 probe removed. End of manip.

7.9.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Locality	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/04/2021	11:16	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.662	1733	Sampling upper part of the Y3 chimney
06/04/2021	11:33	Y3	N 37 17.505	W 032 16.663	1731	Sampling of the lower part (sulphide) of the Y3 chimney
06/04/2021	11:52	Y3	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.666	1732	Ti syringe trigger n ° 1 at 11:52:17

06/04/2021	12:03	Y3	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.674	1729	Ti syringe trigger n ° 2 at 12:03:23
06/04/2021	12:07	Y3	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.668	1731	Ti syringe trigger n ° 3 at 12:07:18
06/04/2021	12:40	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.665	1730	Chemini (the good) sample at 12:40:15
06/04/2021	12:44	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.666	1731	PLUME 2 sample - 4.940 ° C.
06/04/2021	12:51	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.673	1735	Sampling microbial mat Y3 in PBT3
06/04/2021	14:25	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.544	1655	PIF syringe n ° 1 filtered on the central point of I1. Temperature = 4.670 ° C.
06/04/2021	14:29	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.542	1656	PIF syringe n ° 2 unfiltered on the central point of I1.
06/04/2021	14:43	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.540	1653	PIF sample on syringe n ° 3 with filter at the central point of I2. Temperature = 4.630 ° C. Parallel launch of chemini Fe and S measurements.
06/04/2021	14:46	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.541	1653	PIF syringe n ° 4 sample without filter on central point of I2. Temperature = 4.620 ° C.
06/04/2021	15:40	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.496	1621	Trigger Ti syringe n ° 4.
06/04/2021	15:41	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1620	Ti n ° 5 syringe withdrawal trigger
06/04/2021	15:43	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Triggering Ti syringe n ° 6 at 15:43:47.
06/04/2021	15:52	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Aspi bowl 1 shrimp
06/04/2021	16:20	Sintra	N 37 17,499	W 032 16.571	1667	Beginning of the PLUME 4 bag sampling - 5.160 ° C.
06/04/2021	16:29	Sintra	N 37 17,500	W 032 16.570	1669	Sampling of microbial mats placed in PBT4.

7.9.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1997-9	20210604T110806.962	00:01:22	Y3
PL1997-9	20210604T110956.13	00:01:09	Y3
PL1997-9	20210604T111412.548	00: 04: 01	Y3
PL1997-9	20210604T111957.884	00: 03: 11	Y3
PL1997-9	20210604T113901.167	00:01:38	Y3
PL1997-9	20210604T121304.761	00: 13: 54	Y3
PL1997-9	20210604T122703.6	00: 04: 04	Isabel iron rug
PL1997-9	20210604T124059.408	00: 02: 29	Isabel iron rug
PL1997-9	20210604T125202.409	00:01:34	Isabel iron rug
PL1997-9	20210604T125400.517	00:01:21	Isabel iron rug
PL1997-9	20210604T125709.46	00: 01: 30	Isabel iron rug
PL1997-9	20210604T141331.464	00: 20: 39	Sintra inactive
PL1997-9	20210604T153455.925	00: 03: 34	Sintra
PL1997-9	20210604T153929.286	00:05:36	Sintra
PL1997-9	20210604T154547.868	00:01:48	Sintra
PL1997-9	20210604T155129.157	00:01:38	Sintra
PL1997-9	20210604T161042.207	00: 00: 48	Sintra iron mat
PL1997-9	20210604T161222.289	00:07:04	Sintra iron mat
PL1997-9	20210604T162931.328	00: 02: 43	Sintra iron mat

7.9.6. CHEMINI measurements - temperature

Dated	Time	Locality	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/04/2021	11:41	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.673	1729	Temperature measurement with the Nautile temperature probe
06/04/2021	14:26	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.543	1655	Chemini Fe and S on central point of i1.
06/04/2021	14:31	Sintra	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.541	1657	Chemini Fe and S on corner 1 of i1
06/04/2021	14:35	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.541	1656	Chemini point corner 2 from I1- 4.660 ° C.
06/04/2021	14:43	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.540	1653	Chemini Fe and S at the central point of i2 - 4.630 ° C.

06/04/2021	14:47	Sintra	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.539	1651	Chemini on corner 1 of I2
06/04/2021	14:52	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.537	1650	Chimney on corner 2 of I2 - 4.640 ° C.
06/04/2021	15:24	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.502	1620	Temperature measurement where the HTNKE 30011 probe was. Temperature = 5.9 ° C.
06/04/2021	15:37	Sintra	N 37 17.533	W 032 16.494	1622	Temperature measurement with T Nautical probe. Maximum temperature measured = 221 ° C.
06/04/2021	16:16	Sintra	N 37 17,498	W 032 16.571	1668	Temperature measurement with TNaut probe. Max temperature = 7.160 ° C.
06/04/2021	16:18	Sintra	N 37 17,499	W 032 16.571	1668	Start mesures Cheminis Fe & S

7.9.7. Navigation

7.10. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1998-10

Friday, June 4, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.3085	W32 ° 16.4845	Eiffel Tower
Launch time	09:42	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:39
Time of departure from the bottom	16:21	Nautile time on board	17:15
Pilot	Julien Fenouil	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h42
Co-pilot	Yoann Fremont		
Observer	Sandra fuchs		

7.10.1. Objectives

Objectives: Organic samples: Ana mussels (iAtlantic), Océanopolis shrimps and crabs, sponges, ELFES test, colonizer verification

Useful contact details:

Montsegur	N37 ° 17.283	W32 ° 16.553	1701	
PA1 (Montsegur)	N37 ° 17.296	W32 ° 16.524	1703	
Isabel	N37 ° 17.379	W32 ° 16.636	1686	
Feox Isabel rug	N37 ° 17.336	W32 ° 16.634	1700	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

ELVES	PBT1 + PBT2	ELFES cell	

Mounted basket

ELVES	PBT1 + PBT2		

Instrumentation

4 PLUME pockets	Aspi Bowls		
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ASC7 configuration

Basket 1 descent: 2 blade corers + an ELFES cell	Basket 2 descent:
Basket 1 mounted: 2 core barrels + one or two ELFES cell (s)	Basket 2 ascent:

7.10.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/05/2021	10:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.207	W 032 16.924		Arrival at the bottom
06/05/2021	10:42	Lucky strike	N 37 17,161	W 032 16.547	1677	Nautile isolation problem. Projector test.
06/05/2021	10:45	Lucky strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 16.172	1683	Nautile isolation tests ok. Problem solved.
06/05/2021	10:49	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.534	1698	Arrival on Montségur.
06/05/2021	10:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1703	TNaut probe measurement: 5.8 ° C on a mold mold.
06/05/2021	10:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1703	Beginning of purge PLUME 1.
06/05/2021	10:58	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1706	Beginning of sampling PLUME 2 pocket on the mold. TNaut probe = 6.23 ° C.
06/05/2021	11:11	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.523	1707	BMP mold sampling in PBT4.
06/05/2021	11:31	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.527	1706	TNaut probe measurement = 5.40 ° C on molds.
06/05/2021	11:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.529	1705	Beginning of PLUME 3 sampling on mussel beds.

06/05/2021	11:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.522	1708	Beginning of sampling in the ELFES 1 cartridge on the mussel bed.
06/05/2021	12:12	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.521	1708	Beginning of aspiration in the ELFES 3 cartridge on the mold previously scraped by the ELFES claw.
06/05/2021	12:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.526	1708	Start aspiration of molds in Aspi bowl 1.
06/05/2021	12:43	Lucky strike	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.694	1646	Arrival on the ASC.
06/05/2021	12:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17.259	W 032 16.705	1646	Route to point of substrate PA1.
06/05/2021	13:13	Lucky strike	N 37 17.305	W 032 16.526	1707	CL6 planted on the place where the PA1 substrate was placed. CL6 locked.
06/05/2021	13:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.517	1710	View on PA1 substrate and the coring mark left by the CL6 produced.
06/05/2021	13:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17.262	W 032 16.692	1650	Arrival on ASC.
06/05/2021	13:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.257	W 032 16.705	1648	TNaut probe measurement = 4.620 ° C. For setting with a reversal thermometer on the ASC.
06/05/2021	13:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17,258	W 032 16.709	1647	Reversal thermometer triggered.
06/05/2021	14:07	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.544	1698	Arrival at the Eiffel Tower. TEMPO gratings in sight.
06/05/2021	14:11	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.540	1698	Photos taken of Ana's colonizers. Of the 9 colonizers, 3 returned. None are closed. Colonizers are colonized by mussels.
06/05/2021	14:15	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.540	1698	Mussel spot spotted for a last sample of mussel beds for Ana C.
06/05/2021	14:17	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.538	1699	TNaut probe measurement = 4.610 ° C on molds. Beginning of purge PLUME 1.
06/05/2021	14:18	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.539	1699	Start of PLUME sampling 4.
06/05/2021	14:27	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.539	1699	Beginning of mussel collection in Aspi bowl 2.
06/05/2021	14:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.539	1699	Beginning of shrimp sampling in Aspi bowl 3.
06/05/2021	14:35	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.538	1700	Beginning of shrimp sampling in Aspi bowl 4.
06/05/2021	14:41	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.540	1699	Beginning of shrimp sampling in Aspi bowl 5.
06/05/2021	14:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.539	1698	Collection of 2 crabs in Aspi bowl 5.
06/05/2021	14:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.540	1698	Beginning of taking a pebble.
06/05/2021	15:02	Isabel	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.628	1700	Arrival on IsaFeOX.
06/05/2021	15:08	Isabel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.633	1704	TNaut probe measurement = 4.600 ° C.
06/05/2021	15:09	Isabel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.634	1703	Beginning of PLUME sampling 6.
06/05/2021	15:19	Isabel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.628	1699	Sampling of bacterial mats in PBT3
06/05/2021	15:26	Isabel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.629	1692	Beginning of transit to Y3.
06/05/2021	15:40	Y3	N 37 17,494	W 032 16.667	1723	Arrival on Y3.
06/05/2021	15:54	Y3	N 37 17.515	W 032 16.684	1733	Nautile and laser positioning for start of data acquisition on Y3.
06/05/2021	16:06	Y3	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.682	1731	End of data acquisition on Y3 after passing through 3 of the 4 sides of the chimney. Soda lime problem to be changed a third time. Decision taken to reassemble Nautile.
06/05/2021	16:06	Lucky strike	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.686	1729	End of the dive. Release of Nautile in preparation for a release to go up.

7.10.3. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/05/2021	10:58	Montsegur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1702	PLUME 2 pocket sampling on molding mold. TNaut probe = 6.23 ° C.
06/05/2021	11:11	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.523	1707	Collection of mussels in PBT4.
06/05/2021	11:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.529	1705	PLUME 3 sampling on a mold bed.
06/05/2021	11:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.522	1708	ELFES 1 sample on mussel bed.
06/05/2021	12:12	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.521	1707	Suction in ELFES 3 on the mussel bed.
06/05/2021	12:23	Montsegur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.526	1708	Suction molds in Aspi bowl 1.
06/05/2021	13:13	Lucky strike	N 37 17.305	W 032 16.526	1707	Core sampler blade CL6 to PA1.

06/05/2021	14:18	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.539	1699	PLUME sampling 4.
06/05/2021	14:27	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.539	1699	Mussel sample in Aspi bowl 2.
06/05/2021	14:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.539	1700	Collection of shrimps in Aspi bowl 3.
06/05/2021	14:35	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.538	1700	Collection of shrimps in Aspi bowl 4.
06/05/2021	14:41	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.540	1699	Collection of shrimps in Aspi bowl 5.
06/05/2021	15:09	Isabel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.634	1703	PLUME sampling 6.
06/05/2021	15:19	Isabel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.628	1699	Sampling of bacterial mats in PBT3

7.10.4. TEMPERATURE and VIDEO measurements

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/05/2021	10:56	Montsegur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1703	TNaut probe measurement: 5.8 ° C on a mold mold.
06/05/2021	11:31	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.527	1706	TNaut probe measurement = 5.400 ° C on molds.
06/05/2021	13:50	Lucky strike	N 37 17.257	W 032 16.705	1648	TNaut probe measurement = 4.620 ° C. For setting with a reversal thermometer on the ASC.
06/05/2021	14:17	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.538	1699	TNaut probe measurement = 4.610 ° C on molds.
06/05/2021	15:08	Isabel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.633	1704	TNaut probe measurement = 4.600 ° C.
06/05/2021	15:54	Y3	N 37 17.515	W 032 16.684	1733	Nautilie and laser positioning for start of data acquisition on Y3.

7.10.5. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1998-10	20210605T101325.788	00:00:03	Lucky strike
PL1998-10	20210605T105111.784	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1998-10	20210605T112111.809	00:17:10	Montsegur
PL1998-10	20210605T114459.443	00:18:40	Montsegur
PL1998-10	20210605T130711.299	00:17:42	Montsegur
PL1998-10	20210605T140821.526	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL1998-10	20210605T143821.543	00:00:07	Eiffel Tower
PL1998-10	20210605T150409.869	00:12:53	Isabel
PL1998-10	20210605T154047.05	00:10:10	Y3
PL1998-10	20210605T155240.851	00:13:31	Y3

7.10.6. Navigation

7.11. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 1999-11

Sunday June 6, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.4833	W32 ° 17.1383	WHERE IS
Launch time	10:51	Time of arrival at the bottom	11:48
Time of departure from the bottom	17:29	Nautile time on board	18:21
Pilot	Olivier Fauvin	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h41
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Souradeep Mahato		

7.11.1. Objectives

Objectives: CIMENDEF probe recovery, South crystal probes, Cypress, White castle, CL in Montsegur

Useful contact details:

Cypress	N 37 17,436	W32 16.936	1720	
South crystal	N 37 17.286	W32 16.546	1700	
LSCY06 colonize	N37 ° 17.443	W32 ° 16.864	1736	
White castle lost probe	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.555	1697	
Cimendef HTWN013	N 37 17.287	W32 ° 16.538	1700	
Montsegur HTNKE29012	N 37 17,458	W32 ° 16.857	1738	
CL PA4	N 37 17.408	W32 ° 16.974	1719	Two corers in the same place
TE probes is ltgrad4	N37 ° 17.444	W32 ° 16.927	1704	At the base of the Eiffel Tower site along the Hydroctopus cable
TE probes is ltgrad8	N37 ° 17.444	W32 ° 16.926	1704	
TE probes is degraded	N37 ° 17.342	W32 ° 16.545	1703	
TE probes is ltgrad7	N37 ° 17.340	W32 ° 16.522	1698	At the base of the building
Eiffel Tower N LTgrad11	N 37 17.331	W32 ° 16.540	1696	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

PBT1	3 medium probes (HTNKE)	1 large (HTW)	1 LTW (small)
5 Rod probes in basket	3 tis	2 blade corers	marker pen

Mounted basket

PBT1	5 stakes (LTgrad)	3 HTNKE medium probes	2 medium / large HTWN
2 blade corers	3 tis	1 LTW	

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls			
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7.11.2. DIVE schedule:

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/06/2021	11:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.372	W 032 17.032	1733	Arrived to the bottom
06/06/2021	12:08	Cypress	N 37 17,462	W 032 16.852	1741	Visual of the vent site, where the coloniser LSCY6 was located.
06/06/2021	12:14	Cypress	N 37 17,442	W 032 16.858	1744	Recovery of colonizing LSCY6 in PBT2.
06/06/2021	12:35	Cypress	N 37 17,456	W 032 16.848	1744	Recovery of HTNKE29020 temperature probe

06/06/2021	12:41	Cypress	N 37 17,456	W 032 16.848	1744	installation of HTNKE29016 probe
06/06/2021	12:53	White castle	N 37 17,401	W 032 16.861	1726	Recovery of the lost probe HTWN021
06/06/2021	13:07	South crystal	N 37 17,437	W 032 16.917	1725	Visual of PA4 and south crystal
06/06/2021	13:18	South crystal	N 37 17,431	W 032 16.931	1726	TNaut probe -> starting of temperature measurement
06/06/2021	13:19	South crystal	N 37 17,434	W 032 16.927	1726	TNaut-> end of temperature measurement probe
06/06/2021	13:20	South crystal	N 37 17,434	W 032 16.927	1726	326 ° C is the max temperature recorded.
06/06/2021	13:23	South crystal	N 37 17,439	W 032 16.927	1726	Ti 3 triggering time 13:23:33
06/06/2021	13:25	South crystal	N 37 17,439	W 032 16.927	1726	Ti 2 triggering time 13:25:43
06/06/2021	13:27	South crystal	N 37 17,437	W 032 16.927	1725	Ti 1 triggering time 13:27:21
06/06/2021	13:38	South crystal	N 37 17,435	W 032 16.925	1726	HTW08 installation on South Crystal
06/06/2021	13:40	South crystal	N 37 17,435	W 032 16.933	1724	Visual of PA4 at South Crystal
06/06/2021	13:44	South crystal	N 37 17,440	W 032 16.935	1724	Corer blade: CL6 during coring
06/06/2021	13:52	South crystal	N 37 17,437	W 032 16.929	1726	Coring blade: CL7 during coring
06/06/2021	14:15	South crystal	N 37 17,447	W 032 16.906	1730	Pick-up TCM3-3
06/06/2021	14:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17,287	W 032 16.548	1698	Arrived at Cimendef
06/06/2021	14:43	Cimendef	N 37 17,287	W 032 16.558	1703	Recovery of HTWN013 from Cimendef
06/06/2021	14:52	Montsegur	N 37 17,291	W 032 16.553	1705	Arrived at Montsegur
06/06/2021	14:58	Montsegur	N 37 17,291	W 032 16.542	1707	TCM3-3 dropped
06/06/2021	15:10	Montsegur	N 37 17,292	W 032 16.534	1706	Recovery of HTNKE29012 probe and a piece white gray chimney sample at the tip of the recovered temperature probe
06/06/2021	15:17	Montsegur	N 37 17,296	W 032 16.532	1706	Montsegur: Installation of HTNKE29006 at the same place
06/06/2021	15:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,330	W 032 16.522	1706	Eiffel Tower East: recovery of HTNKE38001
06/06/2021	15:35	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,331	W 032 16.516	1706	Eiffel Tower East: installation of HTNKE30001
06/06/2021	15:38	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,328	W 032 16.518	1707	Eiffel Tower East: recovery of LTGrad4
06/06/2021	15:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,322	W 032 16.518	1708	Eiffel Tower East: installation of LTGrad1
06/06/2021	15:47	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,322	W 032 16.514	1707	Eiffel Tower East: Recovery of LTGrad8
06/06/2021	15:50	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,322	W 032 16.515	1706	Eiffel Tower East: installation of LTGrad2
06/06/2021	15:51	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,324	W 032 16.512	1707	Eiffel Tower East: installation of a marker
06/06/2021	15:55	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,335	W 032 16.509	1707	Eiffel Tower East: recovery of LTGrad6
06/06/2021	15:58	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,337	W 032 16.510	1707	Eiffel Tower East: installation of LTGrad3
06/06/2021	16:00	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,339	W 032 16.509	1707	Tour Eiffel East: LTGrad3 is broken during installation process
06/06/2021	16:10	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,347	W 032 16.518	1695	Eiffel Tower East: recovery of LTW040
06/06/2021	16:13	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,344	W 032 16.517	1695	Tour Eiffel East: installation of LTW018 at the same place
06/06/2021	16:13	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,345	W 032 16.518	1694	Eiffel Tower East: recovery of LTGrad7
06/06/2021	16:15	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,347	W 032 16.519	1693	Eiffel Tower East upper slope: installation of LTGrad5
06/06/2021	16:32	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,350	W 032 16.530	1694	Eiffel Tower North: Installation of LTGrad9
06/06/2021	16:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,350	W 032 16.533	1694	Eiffel Tower North: recovery of LTGrad11

7.11.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/06/2021	12:14	Cypress	N 37 17,442	W 032 16.858	1744	Recovery of colonizing LSCY6 in PBT2.
06/06/2021	12:35	Cypress	N 37 17,456	W 032 16.848	1744	Recovery of HTNKE29020
06/06/2021	12:41	Cypress	N 37 17,456	W 032 16.848	1744	installation of HTNKE29016
06/06/2021	12:53	White castle	N 37 17,401	W 032 16.861	1726	Recovery of the lost probe HTWN021
06/06/2021	13:38	South crystal	N 37 17,435	W 032 16.925	1726	HTW08 installation on South Crystal
06/06/2021	14:15	South crystal	N 37 17,447	W 032 16.906	1730	Pick-up TCM3-3
06/06/2021	14:43	Cimendef	N 37 17,287	W 032 16.558	1703	Recovery of HTWN013
06/06/2021	15:10	Montsegur	N 37 17,292	W 032 16.534	1744	Recovery of HTNKE29012
06/06/2021	15:17	Montsegur	N 37 17,296	W 032 16.532	1744	Installation of HTNKE29006
06/06/2021	15:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,330	W 032 16.522	1706	Recovery of HTNKE38001
06/06/2021	15:35	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,331	W 032 16.516	1706	Installation of HTNKE30001

06/06/2021	15:38	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.518	1707	Recovery of LTGrad4
06/06/2021	15:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.518	1708	Installation of LTGrad1
06/06/2021	15:47	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.514	1707	Recovery of LTGrad8
06/06/2021	15:50	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.515	1706	Installation of LTGrad2
06/06/2021	15:51	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.512	1707	Installation of a marker
06/06/2021	15:55	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.509	1707	Recovery of LTGrad6
06/06/2021	15:58	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.510	1707	Installation of LTGrad3
06/06/2021	16:10	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.518	1695	Recovery of LTW040
06/06/2021	16:13	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.517	1695	Installation of LTW018 at the same place
06/06/2021	16:13	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.518	1694	Recovery of LTGrad7
06/06/2021	16:15	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.519	1693	Installation of LTGrad5
06/06/2021	16:32	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.530	1694	Installation of LTGrad9
06/06/2021	16:33	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.533	1694	Recovery of LTGrad11

7.11.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/06/2021	13:23	South crystal	N 37 17,439	W 032 16.927	1726	Ti 3 triggering time 13:23:33
06/06/2021	13:25	South crystal	N 37 17,439	W 032 16.927	1726	Ti 2 triggering time 13:25:43
06/06/2021	13:27	South crystal	N 37 17,437	W 032 16.927	1725	Ti 1 triggering time 13:27:21
06/06/2021	13:44	South crystal	N 37 17,440	W 032 16.935	1724	Corer blade CL6
06/06/2021	13:52	South crystal	N 37 17,437	W 032 16.929	1726	Corer blade CL7

7.11.5. Temperature measurements

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/06/2021	13:18	South crystal	N 37 17,431	W 032 16.931	1726	TNaut probe temperature measurement

7.11.6. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL1999-11	20210606T120947.809	00:06:20	Cypress
PL1999-11	20210606T123136.006	00:11:44	
PL1999-11	20210606T124335.787	00:01:04	
PL1999-11	20210606T130836.904	00:29:59	South crystal
PL1999-11	20210606T133836.908	00:29:59	Cimendef?
PL1999-11	20210606T140836.911	00:29:59	Lucky strike
PL1999-11	20210606T143836.914	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1999-11	20210606T150836.934	00:29:59	Montsegur
PL1999-11	20210606T153836.948	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL1999-11	20210606T160836.951	00:29:58	Eiffel Tower
PL1999-11	20210606T163836.944	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL1999-11	20210606T170836.96	00:21:55	Eiffel Tower

7.11.7. Navigation

7.12. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2000-12

Tuesday, June 8, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.4833	W32 ° 17.1383	WHERE IS
ASC mooring position	N37 ° 17.3085	W32 ° 16.4845	
Launch time	9:30	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:27
Time of departure from the bottom	16:31	Nautile time on board	17:25
Pilot	Franck Rosazza	Duration of operations on the bottom	6:04
Co-pilot	Julien Fenouil		
Observer	Adrien chauvet		

7.12.1. Objectives

Objectives: Seamon W installation + WIFI test

Useful contact details:

SEAMON W	N 37 ° 17.4786	W 32 ° 16.8002	1742	
Lava lake	N 37 ° 17.541	W 32 ° 16.796	1738	
Montségur –DEAFS - TCM3-3	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1700	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

Niskin	PBT1 (LSLL1)	WIRELESS	3 tis
1 LTI and 1 LTnke (small)	1 HTNKE (averages)	3 Ltgrad (stakes)	

Mounted basket

Niskin	PBT1	WIRELESS	Piece of basalt
3 tis			

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls			
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ASC8 configuration

Basket 1 descent: DEAFS and duckboards	Basket 2 descent: DEAFS reel
Basket 1 ascent:	Basket 2 ascent:

7.12.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/08/2021	10:27	Lucky strike	N 37 17,481	W 032 17.043		Arrival at the bottom
06/08/2021	10:48	Seamon West	N 37 17,490	W 032 16.790	1731	Arrival at the level of the displacement float
06/08/2021	10:51	Seamon West	N 37 17,482	W 032 16.777	1735	Arrival on SEAMon West
06/08/2021	10:56	Seamon West	N 37 17,482	W 032 16.785	1739	Removing a shot bag
06/08/2021	10:57	Seamon West	N 37 17,484	W 032 16.786	1740	Descent weight release clip safety removal
06/08/2021	10:57	Seamon West	N 37 17,482	W 032 16.785	1739	Descent ballast release
06/08/2021	11:00	Seamon West	N 37 17,481	W 032 16.786	1738	Lockpicking of the SEAMon West station for its movement
06/08/2021	11:08	Seamon West	N 37 17,473	W 032 16.791	1739	SEAMon West asked
06/08/2021	11:16	Seamon West	N 37 17,470	W 032 16.789	1735	Ballast 1 deposited on the station
06/08/2021	11:21	Seamon West	N 37 17,478	W 032 16.790	1743	Removal of a second bag of shot. This one is almost empty
06/08/2021	11:25	Seamon West	N 37 17,478	W 032 16.784	1747	Removal of the third ballast bag on the station

06/08/2021	11:30	Seamon West	N 37 17,483	W 032 16.783	1744	The earthquake cable got stuck in the left latch of the earthquake (bad placement when preparing the station)
06/08/2021	11:33	Seamon West	N 37 17,482	W 032 16.780	1743	Earthquake removal: general view of the station + earthquake
06/08/2021	11:40	Seamon West	N 37 17,475	W 032 16.775	1747	Heading of the machine facing the earthquake: 278 °
06/08/2021	11:47	Seamon West	N 37 17,475	W 032 16.780	1745	Removal of the 2000th Nautile panel
06/08/2021	11:51	Seamon West	N 37 17,474	W 032 16.777	1746	Sampling of pieces of basalt glass
06/08/2021	12:06	Seamon West	N 37 17,482	W 032 16.789	1746	Stick wifi in place
06/08/2021	12:07	Seamon West	N 37 17,480	W 032 16.789	1746	Start of checking the station parameters
06/08/2021	12:32	Seamon West	N 37 17,478	W 032 16.785	1743	Drop float displacement
06/08/2021	12:41	Seamon West	N 37 17,479	W 032 16.782	1743	Niskin trigger
06/08/2021	12:44	Lucky strike	N 37 17,478	W 032 16.781	1738	Beginning of transit to the lava lake
06/08/2021	12:56	Lava lake	N 37 17,549	W 032 16.785	1744	Arrival at the LSL1 colonizer drop site
06/08/2021	13:01	Lava lake	N 37 17,545	W 032 16.784	1748	LSL1 deployment
06/08/2021	13:05	Lava lake	N 37 17,545	W 032 16.785	1746	PLUME temperature measurement
06/08/2021	13:05	Lava lake	N 37 17,546	W 032 16.784	1745	PLUME temperature measurement 4.6 ° C
06/08/2021	13:07	Lava lake	N 37 17,545	W 032 16.786	1744	Beginning of FEED 3 sampling
06/08/2021	13:13	Lava lake	N 37 17,549	W 032 16.790	1741	Start picking iron mat in PBT
06/08/2021	13:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17,292	W 032 16.653	1678	Arrival in sight of the elevator
06/08/2021	13:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.650	1674	Exiting the DEAFS reel from the elevator
06/08/2021	14:06	Montsegur	N 37 17,281	W 032 16.542	1701	Arrival in sight of the new DEAFS site
06/08/2021	14:12	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.536	1705	DEAFS cable drum installed
06/08/2021	14:16	Montsegur	N 37 17,285	W 032 16.537	1707	Ballast the grating of the DEAFS cable drum with the previously seized bag of shot.
06/08/2021	14:16	Montsegur	N 37 17,283	W 032 16.536	1706	Seized of a second ballast bag
06/08/2021	14:17	Montsegur	N 37 17,284	W 032 16.536	1707	Removal of the second ballast bag on the grating of the DEAFS reel
06/08/2021	14:18	Montsegur	N 37 17,283	W 032 16.535	1707	Addition of the third bag on the slatted floor
06/08/2021	14:22	Montsegur	N 37 17,283	W 032 16.539	1706	Start unwinding the DEAFS cable
06/08/2021	14:23	Montsegur	N 37 17,285	W 032 16.538	1707	Removal of the reel near the grating
06/08/2021	14:26	Montsegur	N 37 17,287	W 032 16.540	1707	TCM3-3 recovery
06/08/2021	14:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17,285	W 032 16.641	1681	Arrival at ASC
06/08/2021	15:01	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.547	1699	Arrival on the new DEAFS site
06/08/2021	15:26	Montsegur	N 37 17,281	W 032 16.535	1705	Depositing the ODI on the grating of the DEAFS reel
06/08/2021	15:28	Montsegur	N 37 17,285	W 032 16.539	1702	General view of the new DEAFS site with the grating of the reel in the foreground and the DEAFS in the second
06/08/2021	15:31	Montsegur	N 37 17,286	W 032 16.533	1704	Arrival on the new DEAFS site for titanium samples
06/08/2021	15:33	Montsegur	N 37 17,286	W 032 16.534	1704	Beginning of temperature measurements for titanium sampling
06/08/2021	15:34	Montsegur	N 37 17,286	W 032 16.533	1704	Temperature read 300 ° C
06/08/2021	15:42	Montsegur	N 37 17,286	W 032 16.535	1704	Percussion of the sample bottle 3
06/08/2021	15:46	Montsegur	N 37 17,287	W 032 16.535	1704	Percussion T12
06/08/2021	15:48	Montsegur	N 37 17,286	W 032 16.532	1704	Percussion T11
06/08/2021	15:54	Lucky strike	N 37 17,285	W 032 16.535	1704	DEAFS reel unwinding start
06/08/2021	16:09	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,326	W 032 16.533	1695	Arrival at Hydroctopus station
06/08/2021	16:13	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,324	W 032 16.533	1698	Removal of the DEAFS cable drum near the Hydroctopus station
06/08/2021	16:13	Lucky strike	N 37 17,324	W 032 16.532	1698	End of dive start of clearing transit

7.12.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/08/2021	11:08	Seamon West	N 37 17,473	W 032 16.791	1739	SEAMon West asked
06/08/2021	11:33	Seamon West	N 37 17,482	W 032 16.780	1743	OBS posed
06/08/2021	13:01	Lava lake	N 37 17,545	W 032 16.784	1748	LSL1 deployment

7.12.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/08/2021	13:07	Lava lake	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.786	1744	Beginning of FEED 3 sampling
06/08/2021	13:13	Lava lake	N 37 17.549	W 032 16.790	1741	Start picking iron mat in PBT
06/08/2021	15:42	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1704	Ti3 trigger
06/08/2021	15:46	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.535	1704	Ti2 trip
06/08/2021	15:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.532	1704	Ti1 trip

7.12.5. Temperature measurements

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/08/2021	13:05	Lava lake	N 37 17.546	W 032 16.784	1745	PLUME temperature measurement 4.6 ° C
06/08/2021	15:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.534	1704	Start of temperature measurement for titanium sampling

7.12.6. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2000-12	20210608T104932.169	00:06:20	Seamon W
PL2000-12	20210608T133320.079	00:00:02	Lucky strike
PL2000-12	20210608T133322.89	00:10:11	Lift
PL2000-12	20210608T134418.798	00:03:10	Lift
PL2000-12	20210608T140626.034	00:26:39	Montsegur
PL2000-12	20210608T144707.317	00:04:06	Lift
PL2000-12	20210608T150540.122	00:21:19	Montsegur
PL2000-12	20210608T155107.254	00:00:02	Montsegur
PL2000-12	20210608T155110.368	00:24:16	Montsegur

7.12.7. Navigation

7.13. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2001-13

Wednesday, June 9, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
Mooring position Asc	N37 ° 17.287	W32 ° 16.6627	Eiffel Tower
Launch time	10:20	Time of arrival at the bottom	11:15
Time of departure from the bottom	17:09	Nautile time on board	18:08
Pilot	Olivier Fauvin	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h54
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Marjolaine Matabos		

7.13.1. Objectives

Objectives: Seamon W installation + WIFI test

Useful contact details:

TEMPO	N 37 17.329	W 32 16.533	1697	
CLs PA3	N37 ° 17.344	W32 ° 16.556	1697	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

Niskin	2 blade corers	1 HTWN	1 HTNKE (average)
3 button chains	1 LTI and 1 LTnke (small)	4LTgrad (stakes) basket	

Mounted basket

Niskin	2 blade corers		

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls	Chemini / PIF	PLUME	
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ASC9 configuration

Basket 1 descent: 2 APPLES + 2 streams	Basket 2 descent: mesocosm
Basket 1 ascent:	Basket 2 ascent:

7.13.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/09/2021	11:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17,117	W 032 16.583	1653	Arrival at the bottom, CHEMINI Fe and S calibration at 11:09
06/09/2021	11:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.158	W 032 16.603	1648	Transit lift
06/09/2021	11:36	Lucky strike	N 37 17,245	W 032 16.657	1659	Two APPLES recovered, transit to Montségur
06/09/2021	11:53	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.530	1706	APPLE C2bcg posed
06/09/2021	12:01	Montsegur	N 37 17,291	W 032 16.525	1707	APPLE placed on C1acg
06/09/2021	12:12	Lucky strike	N 37 17,241	W 032 16.653	1654	Arrival elevator
06/09/2021	12:17	Lucky strike	N 37 17,252	W 032 16.661	1658	Mesocosm recovery
06/09/2021	12:28	Montsegur	N 37 17,280	W 032 16.541	1701	Arrival in Montségur
06/09/2021	12:32	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.537	1705	Mesocosm posed
06/09/2021	12:41	Lucky strike	N 37 17,245	W 032 16.646	1656	Arrival elevator
06/09/2021	12:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17,243	W 032 16.658	1658	Triggering reversal thermometer
06/09/2021	12:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17,245	W 032 16.656	1659	Tap the thermometer to spin it
06/09/2021	12:47	Lucky strike	N 37 17,244	W 032 16.658	1659	Current recovery TCM3-A and TCM3-B in basket II elevator

06/09/2021	13:03	Montsegur	N 37 17.312	W 032 16.538	1704	Arrival Montségur
06/09/2021	13:17	Lucky strike	N 37 17.316	W 032 16.528	1705	TCM3-A and TCM3-B current meter installed next to Hydroctopus
06/09/2021	13:22	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.532	1696	Arrival in the TEMPO area
06/09/2021	13:36	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	BT13 chain laid
06/09/2021	13:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.536	1697	BT12 placed on stones on the left
06/09/2021	13:52	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	BT11 asked
06/09/2021	14:05	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.535	1697	Measuring zone one in the diffuser
06/09/2021	14:05	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.532	1698	Temperature around 16 ° C
06/09/2021	14:06	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	Beginning of Chemini Fe and S on point 1 diffuser
06/09/2021	14:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.529	1697	End Chemini point 1 diffuser, beginning Chemini point 2 molds
06/09/2021	14:15	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.532	1699	End Chemini point 2 molds from the center (6.62 ° C)
06/09/2021	14:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.536	1699	Chemini start point 3 molds from the top (13.15 ° C)
06/09/2021	14:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.534	1698	End Chemini point 3, start Chemini point 4 on barite (8.06 ° C)
06/09/2021	14:23	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1699	End Chemini point 4 Barite
06/09/2021	14:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.536	1696	Chemini start point 5 on BT13-33, microbial mattes, T ° C = 4.96 ° C
06/09/2021	14:29	Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.529	1697	Measuring point n ° 6, temperature 4.96 ° C
06/09/2021	14:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.537	1696	Chemini end point 5 mattes, beginning point 6 small molds of the big pebble at the top
06/09/2021	14:32	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.531	1697	Focus on channels: BT11
06/09/2021	14:34	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.530	1697	Channel zoom: BT12
06/09/2021	14:34	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.533	1697	End Chemini point 6 (small mussels on large pebble at the top)
06/09/2021	14:36	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.536	1697	Focus on channels: BT13
06/09/2021	14:41	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.534	1696	Three lonely buttons recovered
06/09/2021	14:41	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.534	1695	Beginning of grating
06/09/2021	15:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.540	1697	Grating in place
06/09/2021	15:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.542	1697	BT10 recovered
06/09/2021	15:18	Lucky strike	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.542	1697	Niskin triggered at Seamon East
06/09/2021	15:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.543	1704	Sampling of mussels to put in the mesocosm
06/09/2021	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17,293	W 032 16.533	1707	Mesocosm in place
06/09/2021	16:03	Montsegur	N 37 17.295	W 032 16.534	1702	End of mesocosm manipulation
06/09/2021	16:09	Montsegur	N 37 17,293	W 032 16.527	1708	APPLE in place on C1bcg (instead of C1acg)
06/09/2021	16:40	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.534	1703	HTWN013 probe in place
06/09/2021	16:55	Montsegur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.540	1701	DEAFS connected
06/09/2021	16:55	Lucky strike	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.540	1701	Transit to the release point, end of the dive

7.13.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/09/2021	11:53	Montsegur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.530	1706	APPLE C2bcg posed
06/09/2021	13:36	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	BT13 chain laid
06/09/2021	13:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.536	1697	BT12 chain laid
06/09/2021	13:52	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	BT11 chain laid
06/09/2021	15:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.542	1697	BT10 recovered
06/09/2021	16:01	Montsegur	N 37 17,293	W 032 16.533	1707	Mesocosm in place
06/09/2021	16:09	Montsegur	N 37 17,293	W 032 16.527	1708	APPLE in place on C1bcg
06/09/2021	16:40	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.534	1703	HTWN013 probe in place

7.13.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/09/2021	15:33	Montsegur	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.543	1704	Sampling of mussels to put in the mesocosm

7.13.5. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/09/2021	14:06	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	Chemini S on point 1 diffuser
06/09/2021	14:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.529	1697	Chemini point 2 molds
06/09/2021	14:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.536	1699	Chemini point 3 molds from the top
06/09/2021	14:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.534	1698	Chemini point 4 on barite (8.06 ° C)
06/09/2021	14:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.536	1696	Chemini point 5 on BT13-33, microbial mattes, T ° C = 4.96 ° C
06/09/2021	14:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.537	1696	Chemini point 6 small mussels from the big pebbles at the top

7.13.6. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2001-13	20210609T133505.089	00:27:36	Eiffel Tower
PL2001-13	20210609T140241.801	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL2001-13	20210609T143241.791	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower
PL2001-13	20210609T150241.797	00:12:06	Eiffel Tower
PL2001-13	20210609T151824.805	00:00:56	Eiffel Tower
PL2001-13	20210609T152713.843	00:06:16	Montsegur
PL2001-13	20210609T153854.096	00:03:01	Montsegur
PL2001-13	20210609T155119.499	00:04:21	Montsegur
PL2001-13	20210609T160224.905	00:00:28	Montsegur
PL2001-13	20210609T164338.487	00:13:17	Montsegur

7.13.7. Navigation

7.14. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2002-14

Thursday, June 10, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
Launch time	10:23	Time of arrival at the bottom	11:15
Time of departure from the bottom	17:10	Nautile time on board	18:08
Pilot	Franck Rosazza		
Co-pilot	Julien Fenouil		
Observer	Laurent Gautier		

7.14.1. Objectives

Objectives: TEMPO installation, DEAFS, hydroctopus Seamon E + WIFI test, TE probes

Useful contact details:

New DEAFS	N 37 17.283	W 32 16.539	1697	Former DEAFS contact details
TEMPO	N 37 17.329	W 32 16.533	1697	
Seamon E	No. 37 ° 17.306	W 32 ° 16.539	1705	
AISICS (CISICS)	N 37 ° 17.338	W 32 ° 16.531	1692	
Core barrels south reference	N37 17,220	W32 16.503		

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

2 core barrels	WIRELESS	1 HTNKE (average)	
1 LTI and 1 LTnke (small)	4LTgrad (stakes) basket		

Mounted basket

2 core barrels	WIRELESS		

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls			
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7.14.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/10/2021	11:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.046	W 032 16.659	1608	Arrival at the bottom
06/10/2021	11:16	Lucky strike	N 37 17.048	W 032 16.657	1608	Transit to Seamon East
06/10/2021	11:43	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.318	W 032 16.549	1701	Seamon East Station
06/10/2021	11:45	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.552	1706	We remove the TCM currents from the station
06/10/2021	11:54	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.554	1706	Descent ballast release
06/10/2021	11:57	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.554	1706	Two bags of granules removed
06/10/2021	12:03	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.316	W 032 16.559	1705	We remove a 3rd bag of granules
06/10/2021	12:05	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.317	W 032 16.559	1705	Relocation of the station
06/10/2021	12:42	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.320	W 032 16.531	1700	Deposit of the 1st bag of granules at the station
06/10/2021	12:55	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.530	1695	Deposit of the 2nd bag of shot
06/10/2021	13:34	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.527	1701	Deposit of a 3rd bag of granules on the station
06/10/2021	13:49	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.529	1700	Deposit of the 4th bag of granules at the station

06/10/2021	13:57	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.529	1698	Release of the float from the East Seamon station by the Nautilie
06/10/2021	14:00	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.532	1696	Seamon East station in place
06/10/2021	14:09	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.539	1700	Wifi connected
06/10/2021	14:15	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17,176	W 032 16.434	1700	Wifi disconnection
06/10/2021	14:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.531	1695	Retrieving TEMPO on the station
06/10/2021	14:48	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.537	1699	TEMPO in place
06/10/2021	15:09	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.537	1700	TEMPO WIFI return camera test
06/10/2021	15:28	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	1701	EAFS ODI protection cap removal
06/10/2021	15:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.535	1701	WiFi re-connection
06/10/2021	15:57	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.323	W 032 16.531	1700	Hydroctopus connected
06/10/2021	16:08	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.525	1704	Nautilie unwinds the cable from the DEAFS reel
06/10/2021	16:46	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.534	1702	DEAFS connection to East Seamon station
06/10/2021	16:46	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	1702	Connector in place
06/10/2021	16:51	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.531	1702	Wifi test
06/10/2021	16:58	Lucky strike	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.539	1694	End of dive
06/10/2021	16:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.541	1679	Nautilie in open water

7.14.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/10/2021	14:00	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.532	1696	Seamon East station in place
06/10/2021	14:48	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.537	1699	TEMPO in place

7.14.4. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2002-14	20210610T130749.57	00:00:01	Seamon East
PL2002-14	20210610T130751.727	00:00:59	Seamon East
PL2002-14	20210610T132741.346	00:05:41	Seamon East
PL2002-14	20210610T135608.396	00:26:26	Seamon East
PL2002-14	20210610T154608.045	00:15:40	Seamon East
PL2002-14	20210610T164244.927	00:23:21	Seamon East

7.14.5. Navigation

7.15. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2003-15

Friday 11 June 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
Mooring position asc	N37 ° 17.287	W32 ° 16.6627	IS
Launch time	09:27	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:21
Time of departure from the bottom	16:19	Nautile time on board	17:15
Pilot	Olivier Fauvin	Duration of operations on the bottom	5h58
Co-pilot	Loïc Bonnet		
Observer	Françoise Lesongeur		

7.15.1. Objectives

Objectives: CISICS installation, White Castle chimney

Useful contact details:

Seamon E	N 37 ° 17.306	W 32 ° 16.539	1705	
AISICS (CISICS)	N 37 ° 17.338	W 32 ° 16.531	1692	
Cypress	N 37 17.436	W32 16.936	1720	
South crystal	N 37 17.286	W32 16.546	1700	
Cimendef	N 37 17.287	W32 ° 16.538	1700	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

PBT1 (LSTE9) + PBT2	3 tis	Average probe HTWN021	Big probe HTW04

Mounted basket

PBT1 + PBT2	3 tis		

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls			
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ASC10 configuration

Basket 1 descent: 3 tis	Basket 2 descent: 1 current (TCM3-3)
Basket 1 ascent:	Basket 2 ascent:

7.15.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/11/2021	10:23	Lucky strike	N 37 17.130	W 032 16.663	1620	Arrival at the bottom
06/11/2021	10:42	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.523	1694	AISICS fireplace
06/11/2021	10:47	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.524	1695	Start of AISICS chimney sampling in PBT4
06/11/2021	11:08	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.525	1701	CISICS exit
06/11/2021	11:26	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.329	W 032 16.525	1698	Nautile climbs to unwind the CISICS cable
06/11/2021	13:02	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.531	1694	CISICS and its colonizer on AISICS
06/11/2021	13:10	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.526	1693	Installation temperature probe HTWN021
06/11/2021	13:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.530	1694	LSTE9 colonizer deployed
06/11/2021	13:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.531	1691	ASPI bowl suction start 1
06/11/2021	13:23	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.448	1692	ASPI bowl suction start 2
06/11/2021	13:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.525	1692	ASPI bowl suction start 3
06/11/2021	13:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.523	1687	Installation of the HTW04 probe
06/11/2021	13:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.520	1687	Transit to CIMENDEF

06/11/2021	13:37	Lucky strike	N 37 17.211	W 032 16.335	1704	DEAFS cable view
06/11/2021	13:45	Cimendef	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.557	1702	TNaut probe for temperature measurement start. 300 ° C
06/11/2021	13:50	Cimendef	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.554	1700	Titanium Ti 3 syringe impacted
06/11/2021	13:52	Cimendef	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.556	1700	Trigger Ti 2 titanium syringes
06/11/2021	13:53	Cimendef	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.556	1701	Ti titanium syringe trigger 1
06/11/2021	14:09	Lucky strike	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.704	1642	Arrival on ASC
06/11/2021	14:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17,266	W 032 16.709	1643	Flip-over thermometer
06/11/2021	14:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.709	1643	TNaut probe 4.5 ° C
06/11/2021	14:36	Lucky strike	N 37 17,266	W 032 16.706	1643	TCM 3-3 in BMP output of UPS
06/11/2021	14:37	Lucky strike	N 37 17.265	W 032 16.702	1643	Transit to South Crystal
06/11/2021	15:09	South crystal	N 37 17,447	W 032 16.898	1730	TCM 3-3 installed
06/11/2021	15:11	Lucky strike	N 37 17,448	W 032 16.891	1727	Transit to CYPRES
06/11/2021	15:33	Cypress	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.854	1739	Start of chimney sampling in PBT4
06/11/2021	15:38	Cypress	N 37 17,446	W 032 16.860	1740	TNaut probe start of temperature measurement in the smoker of the sampled chimney 295 ° C
06/11/2021	15:39	Cypress	N 37 17,448	W 032 16.859	1740	Temperature measurement on another fluid outlet
06/11/2021	15:42	Cypress	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.862	1741	Probe TNaut start of temperature measurement 264 ° C
06/11/2021	15:44	Cypress	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.859	1740	Tnaut probe start of temperature measurement in the first fluid outlet 295 ° C
06/11/2021	15:52	Cypress	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.861	1740	Triggering syringe Titanium Ti4
06/11/2021	15:55	Cypress	N 37 17,454	W 032 16.864	1740	Triggering syringe Titanium Ti5
06/11/2021	15:57	Cypress	N 37 17.534	W 032 16.655	1742	Titanium Ti 6 Syringe Trigger
06/11/2021	16:00	Cypress	N 37 17.619	W 032 16.618	1741	Suction start ASPI bowl 4
06/11/2021	16:02	Cypress	N 37 17.611	W 032 16.611	1740	Suction start ASPI bowl 5
06/11/2021	16:06	Lucky strike	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.857	1736	End of Dive

7.15.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/11/2021	13:02	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.531	1694	CISICS and its colonizer on AISICS
06/11/2021	13:10	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.526	1693	Installation temperature probe HTWN021
06/11/2021	13:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.530	1694	LSTE9 colonizer deployed
06/11/2021	13:31	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.523	1687	Installation of the HTW04 probe
06/11/2021	15:09	South crystal	N 37 17,447	W 032 16.898	1730	TCM 3-3 installed

7.15.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/11/2021	10:47	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.524	1695	AISICS chimney sampling in PBT4
06/11/2021	13:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.531	1691	ASPI bowl suction 1
06/11/2021	13:23	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.448	1692	ASPI bowl suction 2
06/11/2021	13:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.525	1692	ASPI bowl suction 3
06/11/2021	13:50	Cimendef	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.554	1700	Ti3 titanium syringe trigger
06/11/2021	13:52	Cimendef	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.556	1700	Trigger Ti2 titanium syringes
06/11/2021	13:53	Cimendef	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.556	1701	Triggering titanium syringe Ti1
06/11/2021	15:33	Cypress	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.854	1739	Chimney sampling in PBT4
06/11/2021	15:52	Cypress	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.861	1740	Triggering syringe Titanium Ti4
06/11/2021	15:55	Cypress	N 37 17,454	W 032 16.864	1740	Triggering syringe Titanium Ti5
06/11/2021	15:57	Cypress	N 37 17.534	W 032 16.655	1741	Titanium Ti6 Syringe Trigger
06/11/2021	16:00	Cypress	N 37 17.619	W 032 16.618	1741	Aspiration bowl ASPI 4
06/11/2021	16:02	Cypress	N 37 17.611	W 032 16.611	1740	Aspiration bowl ASPI 5

7.15.5. Temperature measurements - CHEMINI - optode

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/11/2021	13:45	Cimendef	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.557	1702	TNaut probe for temperature measurement start. 300 ° C
06/11/2021	14:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17,266	W 032 16.709	1643	Flip-over thermometer
06/11/2021	14:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.709	1643	TNaut probe 4.5 ° C
06/11/2021	15:38	Cypress	N 37 17,446	W 032 16.860	1740	TNaut probe start of temperature measurement in the smoker of the sampled chimney 295 ° C
06/11/2021	15:39	Cypress	N 37 17,448	W 032 16.859	1740	Temperature measurement on another fluid outlet
06/11/2021	15:42	Cypress	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.862	1741	Probe TNaut start of temperature measurement 264 ° C
06/11/2021	15:44	Cypress	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.859	1740	Tnaut probe start of temperature measurement in the first fluid outlet 295 ° C

7.15.6. 4K video sequences

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2003-15	20210611T100251.446	00:00:04	Lucky strike
PL2003-15	20210611T104422.423	00:03:19	Montsegur

7.15.7. Navigation

7.16. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2004-16

Saturday June 12, 2021

Nautilie mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
Mooring position asc	N37 ° 17.287	W32 ° 16.6627	IS
Launch time	09:48	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:39
Time of departure from the bottom	16:38	Nautilie time on board	17:48
Pilot	Julien Fenouil		
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Loïc Drigo		

7.16.1. Objectives

Objectives: DEAFS installation + titanium + Biolucky, currentometers and Seamon E probes

Useful contact details:

New DEAFS	N 37 17.283	W 32 16.539	1697	Former DEAFS contact details
Isabel	N 37 17.379	W 32 16.636	1697	
PA3 corers	N37 ° 17.344	W32 ° 16.556	1697	

Nautilie configuration

Descent basket

PBT1 (Biolucky)	3 tis	2 blade corers	1 stake (basket)
4 HTNKE (averages)			

Mounted basket

PBT1	3 tis	2 blade corers	

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls	PLUME 1 x 2L		
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ASC11 configuration

Basket 1 descent: 3 tis	Basket 2 descent: 1 currento + 1 APPLE
Basket 1 ascent: 3 tis	Basket 2 ascent:

7.16.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/12/2021	10:58	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1702	Arrival at Montségur site: view of DEAFS
06/12/2021	11:09	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1703	DEAFS set up on his new smoker
06/12/2021	11:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1703	Placement of the bell on the smoker
06/12/2021	11:26	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Installation of Biolucky on the back of DEAFS
06/12/2021	11:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1704	Sampling of the Ex-DEAFS site chimney
06/12/2021	11:40	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Nautilie temperature probe ex-DEAFS site
06/12/2021	11:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Titanium syringe withdrawal 3 Ex-DEAFS site
06/12/2021	11:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1704	Ex-DEAFS Titanium 1 syringe withdrawal
06/12/2021	12:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.537	1704	POMME on quadra R1 (Montségur)
06/12/2021	13:11	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.538	1704	Installation of the TCM3-1 current meter on the TCM3-2 site
06/12/2021	13:50	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.547	1694	Current meter installation TCM3-B (Est TE)
06/12/2021	13:51	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.511	1693	TCM3-A fell into a hole; it is unusable (2:03 p.m.)

06/12/2021	14:29	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1702	Installation of HTNKE30014 probe on SOLEIL
06/12/2021	14:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	Installation LTGRAD15 and HTNKE30007 near SEAMON East (2:38 p.m.)
06/12/2021	15:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.531	1691	Pose HTNKE30005 tempo west (2:53 pm)
06/12/2021	15:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1693	TCM3-C setup
06/12/2021	15:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1692	TCM3-D setup
06/12/2021	15:29	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.541	1693	HTNKE29012 probe installation
06/12/2021	15:32	Lucky strike	N 37 17.360	W 032 16.546	1685	Transit to ISABEL
06/12/2021	15:39	Isabel	N 37 17.377	W 032 16.637	1684	Arrival on ISABEL
06/12/2021	15:52	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1690	Temperature probe: 293 ° C
06/12/2021	15:57	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1689	Titanium 4 sample in ISABEL smoker
06/12/2021	16:02	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1687	Titanium 6 sample in ISABEL smoker
06/12/2021	16:15	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.556	1699	Arrival on site PA3
06/12/2021	16:22	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.555	1701	CoreCL6 blade
06/12/2021	16:23	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.555	1699	CoreCL7 blade

7.16.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/12/2021	11:15	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1703	Installation of the DEAFS bell
06/12/2021	11:26	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Installation of Biolucky on the back of DEAFS
06/12/2021	12:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.537	1704	POMME on quadra R1 (Montségur)
06/12/2021	13:11	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.538	1704	Installation of the TCM3-1 current meter on the TCM3-2 site
06/12/2021	13:50	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.547	1694	Current meter installation TCM3-B (Est TE)
06/12/2021	13:51	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.511	1693	TCM3-A fell into a hole; it is unusable (2:03 p.m.)
06/12/2021	14:29	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1702	Installation of probe HTNKE30014
06/12/2021	14:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	Installation LTGRAD15
06/12/2021	14:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	Installation HTNKE30007
06/12/2021	15:14	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.531	1691	Pose HTNKE30005 tempo west (2:53 pm)
06/12/2021	15:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1693	TCM3-C setup
06/12/2021	15:24	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1692	TCM3-D setup
06/12/2021	15:29	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.541	1693	HTNKE29012 probe installation

7.16.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/12/2021	11:30	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1704	Chimney sampling from the ex-DEAFS site
06/12/2021	11:45	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Titanium 3 trigger ex-DEAFS site
06/12/2021	11:52	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1704	Ex-DEAFS Titanium 1 syringe withdrawal
06/12/2021	15:57	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1689	Titanium 4 sample in ISABEL smoker
06/12/2021	16:02	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1687	Titanium 6 sample in ISABEL smoker
06/12/2021	16:22	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.555	1701	CoreCL6 blade
06/12/2021	16:23	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.555	1699	CoreCL7 blade

7.16.5. Measures

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/12/2021	11:40	Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Nautilé T probe ex-DEAFS site
06/12/2021	15:52	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1691	Temperature probe: 293 ° C

7.16.6. 4K video footage

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2004-16	20210612T105954.108	00: 04: 19	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T110859.967	00: 07: 28	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T112018.178	00:05:11	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T112619.576	00: 00: 27	Montsegur

PL2004-16	20210612T112813.962	00: 00: 03	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T113026.107	00:01:05	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T114004.454	00: 04: 05	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T114410.825	00: 00: 02	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T114424.173	00: 09: 13	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T115813.973	00: 00: 07	Lucky strike
PL2004-16	20210612T122813.985	00: 00: 15	Lucky strike
PL2004-16	20210612T125052.568	00: 09: 42	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T131051.733	00: 13: 01	Montsegur
PL2004-16	20210612T134940.431	00: 29: 59	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T141940.447	00: 08: 28	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T142840.404	00: 04: 25	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T150331.233	00: 00: 01	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T150333.436	00: 09: 17	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T151359.897	00: 13: 27	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T152938.128	00:01:24	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T154512.384	00: 09: 31	Eiffel Tower
PL2004-16	20210612T155448.406	00: 09: 47	Isabel
PL2004-16	20210612T161638.436	00: 07: 26	Eiffel Tower

7.16.7. Navigation

7.17. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2005-17

Sunday June 13, 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
Mooring position asc	N37 ° 17.287	W32 ° 16.6627	IS
Launch time	10:08	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:59
Time of departure from the bottom	17:01	Scheduled time Nautile on board	17:52
Pilot	Franck Rosazza	Duration of underground operations	6:02
Co-pilot	Loïc Bonnet		
Observer	Nicolas gayet		

7.17.1. Objectives

Objectives: MERCES periphery, current recovery, West Eiffel Tower probes, Crystal titanium

Useful contact details:

MERCES P1 & P2	N 37 ° 17.280	W 32 ° 16.518	1702 m	
Reference corers	N 37 ° 17.220	W 32 ° 16.503		Montsegur
Mesocosm	N 37 ° 17.2926	W 32 ° 16.534		
Crystal	N 37 ° 17.4572	W 32 ° 16.916	1727 m	
LTgrad12 and HTnke 29008 probes	N 37 17.343	W 32 16.546	1702	
LTgrad13 + LTI-1 probes	N 37 17.341	W 32 16.549	1720	
LTgrad14 + LTnke26004	N 37 17.339	W 32 16.552	1694	
Broken ltgrad	N37 17.337	W 32 16.512		

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

2 blade corers	Niskin	3 tis	4 stakes in basket
1 HTNKE (average)	1 LTI (small - basket)	1 LTNKE	1 LTW

Mounted basket

2 blade corers	Niskin	3 tis	

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls	PIF / Chemini	PLUME	
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ASC12 configuration

Basket 1 descent: 2 APPLES	Basket 2 descent:
Basket 1 ascent: mesocosm	Basket 2 ascent: DEAFS reel

7.17.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/13/2021	10:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.106	W 032 16.666		Arrival at the bottom
06/13/2021	11:02	Lucky strike	N 37 17.105	W 032 16.668	1621	Beginning of Nautile pyrotechnics tests
06/13/2021	11:20	Lucky strike	N 37 17.106	W 032 16.666	1620	Transit to ASC
06/13/2021	11:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17,147	W 032 16.669	1611	PLUME # 3 Sampling
06/13/2021	11:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.209	W 032 16.677	1629	Arrival on ASC
06/13/2021	11:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17.211	W 032 16.690	1640	Beginning of transit to Hydroctopus
06/13/2021	12:03	Lucky strike	N 37 17.310	W 032 16.535	1706	APPLES placed on the ground
06/13/2021	12:05	Lucky strike	N 37 17.309	W 032 16.537	1707	NISKIN Direct Debit
06/13/2021	12:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.523	1700	Arrived at the Merces periphery point
06/13/2021	12:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.520	1707	Start of chemini POINT1 measurement on Merces P

06/13/2021	12:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.522	1706	PIF Sampling Unfiltered Syringe # 7
06/13/2021	12:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.520	1707	PIF sampling Unfiltered syringe # 9 because the cannula has moved
06/13/2021	12:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.521	1706	Start of Chemini point 2 sampling on Merces P
06/13/2021	12:42	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.521	1707	Beginning of PIF sampling Filtered syringe # 8
06/13/2021	12:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.521	1706	Start of chemini point 3 measurement on Merces P
06/13/2021	12:48	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.520	1707	POMME I1 deployment on the PIF / Chemini sampling area at the Merces P point
06/13/2021	12:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.519	1705	Beginning of transit to the core blade core area south of Montségur PA-REF
06/13/2021	13:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17,236	W 032 16.505	1718	CL # 6 trigger
06/13/2021	13:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17,236	W 032 16.505	1718	CL # 7 trigger
06/13/2021	13:21	Montsegur	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.539	1700	Arrival on the mesocosm zone
06/13/2021	13:38	Montsegur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.538	1705	MESOCOSM 4K photos
06/13/2021	13:48	Montsegur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.539	1706	Entering the mesocosm with BMP
06/13/2021	13:49	Lucky strike	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.540	1704	Beginning of transit to ASC
06/13/2021	14:05	Lucky strike	N 37 17.209	W 032 16.690	1628	Arrival on ASC
06/13/2021	14:20	Lucky strike	N 37 17.211	W 032 16.689	1627	Start CHIMNEY CALIBRATION
06/13/2021	14:20	Lucky strike	N 37 17.212	W 032 16.687	1626	ASC dropped
06/13/2021	14:21	Lucky strike	N 37 17.212	W 032 16.686	1626	Beginning of transit to the Eiffel Tower west to install temperature probes
06/13/2021	14:59	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.544	1696	Laying LTGrad 12 near the highest marker on the slope (LTGrad2 zone on the map)
06/13/2021	15:09	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1696	Place the HTnke 29008 probe approximately 50cm from the LTGrad 12 probe, near the highest (northernmost) marker on the slope
06/13/2021	15:19	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.543	1698	Installation of the LTGrad 13 probe
06/13/2021	15:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.546	1701	Installation of the LTI1 temperature probe
06/13/2021	15:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.550	1699	Installation of the temperature sensor LTGrad 14
06/13/2021	15:47	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1697	Place the LTnke 26004 temperature probe next to the LTGrad 14 probe on the 3rd marker
06/13/2021	16:10	Crystal	N 37 17,440	W 032 16.910	1725	Arrival on Crystal
06/13/2021	16:19	Crystal	N 37 17,449	W 032 16.913	1727	TN probe Maximum measurement = 315 ° C
06/13/2021	16:23	Crystal	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.913	1727	Triggering of the Ti Syringe # 3 (for 10s)
06/13/2021	16:26	Crystal	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.912	1726	Triggering the Ti Syringe # 2
06/13/2021	16:30	Crystal	N 37 17,448	W 032 16.915	1726	Triggering the Ti Syringe # 1
06/13/2021	16:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17,449	W 032 16.912	1725	Start survey in search of zoanthaires
06/13/2021	16:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.415	W 032 16.959	1705	End of dive

7.17.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/13/2021	12:48	Montsegur	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.520	1707	POMME deployment at Merces P point
06/13/2021	14:59	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.544	1696	Installation of the LTGrad 12 probe
06/13/2021	15:09	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1696	Installation of the HTnke 29008 probe
06/13/2021	15:19	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.543	1698	Installation of the LTGrad 13 probe
06/13/2021	15:21	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.546	1701	Installation of the LTI1 temperature probe
06/13/2021	15:30	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.550	1699	Installation of the LTGrad 14 probe
06/13/2021	15:47	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1697	Installation of the LTnke 26004 probe

7.17.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/13/2021	11:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17,147	W 032 16.669	1611	PLUME # 3 Sampling
06/13/2021	12:05	Lucky strike	N 37 17.309	W 032 16.537	1707	NISKIN Direct Debit
06/13/2021	12:38	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.522	1706	PIF Sampling Unfiltered Syringe # 7
06/13/2021	12:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.520	1707	PIF sampling Unfiltered syringe # 9
06/13/2021	12:42	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.521	1707	PIF sampling Filtered syringe # 8
06/13/2021	13:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17,236	W 032 16.505	1718	CL # 6 trigger
06/13/2021	13:01	Lucky strike	N 37 17,236	W 032 16.505	1718	CL # 7 trigger
06/13/2021	16:23	Crystal	N 37 17,450	W 032 16.913	1727	Triggering the Ti Syringe # 3
06/13/2021	16:26	Crystal	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.912	1726	Triggering the Ti Syringe # 2
06/13/2021	16:30	Crystal	N 37 17,448	W 032 16.915	1726	Triggering the Ti Syringe # 1

7.17.5. CHEMINI measurements - temperature

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/13/2021	12:33	Lucky strike	N 37 17,282	W 032 16.520	1707	Chemini POINT1 measurements on Merces P
06/13/2021	12:39	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.521	1706	Chemini point 2 measurements on Merces P
06/13/2021	12:46	Lucky strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.521	1706	Chemini point 3 measurements on Merces P
06/13/2021	16:19	Crystal	N 37 17,449	W 032 16.913	1727	TN probe Maximum measurement = 315 ° C

7.17.6. 4K video footage

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2005-17	20210613T121956.778	00:00:47	Montsegur
PL2005-17	20210613T122602.608	00:05:20	Montségur periphery
PL2005-17	20210613T130038.195	00:16:55	Reference site Montségur
PL2005-17	20210613T133853.508	00:00:48	Montsegur
PL2005-17	20210613T134441.993	00:01:48	Montsegur
PL2005-17	20210613T161251.166	00:07:42	Crystal
PL2005-17	20210613T162146.177	00:19:23	Crystal
PL2005-17	20210613T164708.48	00:02:34	Crystal

7.17.7. Navigation

7.18. MoMARSAT 2021 DIVE 2006-18

Friday 11 June 2021

Nautile mooring position	N37 ° 17.1377	W32 ° 16.6309	IS
Mooring position asc	N37 ° 17.287	W32 ° 16.6627	IS
Launch time	9:37	Time of arrival at the bottom	10:34
Time of departure from the bottom	16:38	Nautile time on board	17:32
Pilot	Olivier Fauvin	Duration of underground operations	6:04
Co-pilot	Guillaume De Parseval		
Observer	Laurent Gautier		

7.18.1. Objectives

Objectives: DEAFS installation + titanium + Biolucky, currentometers and Seamon E probes

Useful contact details:

New DEAFS	N 37 17.283	W 32 16.539	1697	Former DEAFS contact details
Isabel	N 37 17.379	W 32 16.636	1697	
PA3 corers	N37 ° 17.344	W32 ° 16.556	1697	

Nautile configuration

Descent basket

PBT1 (Biolucky)	3 tis	2 blade corers	1 stake (basket)
4 HTNKE (averages)			

Mounted basket

PBT1	3 tis	2 blade corers	

Instrumentation

Aspi Bowls	PLUME 1 x 2L		
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7.18.2. Dive summary

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/14/2021	10:35	Lucky strike	N 37 17.086	W 032 16.703	1586	Arrival at the bottom
06/14/2021	10:57	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.327	W 032 16.539	1699	Wifi in place
06/14/2021	12:03	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.535	1700	Wifi removed
06/14/2021	12:52	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.548	1696	LTW40 probe placed in a fault near the mussel and bacterial mat
06/14/2021	12:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	1704	Mold sampling for PBT4
06/14/2021	13:14	Cimendef	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.542	1702	Arrival on Cimendef
06/14/2021	13:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.550	1701	Temperature measurement with the TNaut probe
06/14/2021	13:23	Lucky strike	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.546	1702	Titanium Ti6 sampling
06/14/2021	13:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.545	1702	Ti5 titanium sample
06/14/2021	13:27	Lucky strike	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.547	1702	Titanium Ti4 sampling
06/14/2021	13:51	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.522	1703	LTRAD3 in shopping cart
06/14/2021	14:04	Lucky strike	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.519	1704	LTGRAD10 planted after several tries
06/14/2021	14:09	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.518	1700	Beginning of transit to Sintra inactive
06/14/2021	15:12	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.543	1653	Temperature probe in place in I2 for first Chemini measurement
06/14/2021	15:18	Sintra	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.539	1655	Temperature rise in corner probe for 2nd Chemini measurement
06/14/2021	15:23	Sintra	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.535	1657	T probe Temperature rise in corner of I2 for 3rd Chemini measurement
06/14/2021	15:31	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.540	1655	APPLE placed on quadrat I2

06/14/2021	15:38	Sintra	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.545	1655	TNaut probe in the middle of the I1 quadrat for the first Chemini measurement
06/14/2021	15:44	Sintra	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.543	1667	TNaut probe in corner of quadrat I1 for second Chemini measurement
06/14/2021	15:49	Sintra	N 37 17.519	W 032 16.543	1667	TNaut probe in place in I1 quadrat for third Chemini measurement
06/14/2021	15:59	Lucky strike	N 37 17.515	W 032 16.546	1654	Rapid transit to Seamon West
06/14/2021	16:14	Lucky strike	N 37 17,479	W 032 16.779	1742	Arrival on SEAmon West
06/14/2021	16:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17,479	W 032 16.782	1744	Niskin bottle outlet
06/14/2021	16:25	Lucky strike	N 37 17,476	W 032 16.776	1740	Ballast bags x5, Nautile lift, end of dive

7.18.3. Moorings

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/14/2021	12:52	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.548	1696	Installation of the LTW40 probe
06/14/2021	13:51	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.522	1703	Retrieving the LTGRAD3 probe
06/14/2021	14:04	Eiffel Tower	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.519	1704	Installation of the LTGRAD10 probe
06/14/2021	15:31	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.540	1655	APPLE placed on MERCES I2 quadrat

7.18.4. Samples

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/14/2021	12:57	Lucky strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	1704	Mold sampling for PBT4
06/14/2021	13:23	Lucky strike	N 37 17,277	W 032 16.546	1702	Titanium Ti6 sampling
06/14/2021	13:26	Lucky strike	N 37 17,279	W 032 16.545	1702	Ti5 titanium sample
06/14/2021	13:27	Lucky strike	N 37 17,278	W 032 16.547	1702	Titanium Ti4 sampling
06/14/2021	16:15	Lucky strike	N 37 17,479	W 032 16.782	1744	Niskin Bottle Trigger

7.18.5. Measures

Dated	Time	Site	Lat.	Long.	Imm.	Operations
06/14/2021	13:19	Lucky strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.550	1701	Temperature measurement with the TNaut probe
06/14/2021	15:12	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.543	1653	Chemini measurement FE + S middle MERCES I2
06/14/2021	15:18	Sintra	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.539	1655	Chimney measure FE + S corner 1 MERCES I2
06/14/2021	15:23	Sintra	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.535	1657	Chimney measure FE + S corner 2 MERCES I2
06/14/2021	15:38	Sintra	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.545	1655	Chemini measurement FE + S middle MERCES I1
06/14/2021	15:44	Sintra	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.543	1667	Chimney measure FE + S corner 1 MERCES I1
06/14/2021	15:49	Sintra	N 37 17.519	W 032 16.543	1667	Chimney measure FE + S corner 2 MERCES I1

7.18.6. 4K video footage

DIVE	File name	Duration	Site
PL2006-18	20210614T105344.097	00:00:06	Lucky strike
PL2006-18	20210614T112344.104	00:15:16	Seamon East
PL2006-18	20210614T115230.708	00:01:12	Seamon East
PL2006-18	20210614T115344.115	00:00:48	Seamon East
PL2006-18	20210614T121009.552	00:00:14	Seamon East
PL2006-18	20210614T122344.132	00:03:56	Seamon East
PL2006-18	20210614T125344.129	00:02:08	Eiffel Tower
PL2006-18	20210614T131713.094	00:02:50	Cimendef
PL2006-18	20210614T132134.493	00:02:09	Cimendef
PL2006-18	20210614T132344.137	00:00:17	Cimendef
PL2006-18	20210614T132713.23	00:01:41	Cimendef
PL2006-18	20210614T135344.152	00:29:59	Eiffel Tower

PL2006-18	20210614T142344.161	00:29:59	Lucky strike
PL2006-18	20210614T145344.165	00:29:59	Sintra inactive
PL2006-18	20210614T152344.176	00:29:59	Sintra inactive
PL2006-18	20210614T155344.185	00:05:07	Sintra inactive
PL2006-18	20210614T161527.439	00:02:14	West Seamon
PL2006-18	20210614T162344.194	00:00:03	West Seamon

7.18.7. Navigation

8. List of operations

8.1. List of surface operations and moorings

Date	Heure	Latitude	Longitude	Nom instrument	Observations	Correspondant
24/05/2021	21:12:00	N 37 17.724	W 032 16.768	Deployment microRIO	Déploiement du Deployment	S. Leizour
25/05/2021	05:41:00	N 37 17.793	W 032 19.450	OBS autonome	Recovery OBS LSVVN	T. Dumouch
25/05/2021	09:47:00	N 37 17.933	W 032 19.510	OBS autonome	Deployment OBS LSVWO par le treuil hydro	T. Dumouch
25/05/2021	12:46:00	N 37 15.874	W 032 17.667	OBS autonome	Recovery OBS LSVSN	T. Dumouch
25/05/2021	15:22:00	N 37 15.643	W 032 17.881	OBS autonome	Deployment OBS LSVSO par le treuil hydro	T. Dumouch
25/05/2021	19:24:00	N 37 16.866	W 032 14.277	OBS autonome	Recovery OBS LSVEN	T. Dumouch
26/05/2021	07:00:00	N 37 17.431	W 032 16.753	Flottabilité SEAMON W	DEPLOYMENT flotta Seamon W par le TGF	C. Podeur
27/05/2021	13:27:00	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.773	SEAMON Ouest	Recovery Seamon W	C. Podeur
28/05/2021	07:29:00	N 37 17.299	W 032 16.428	Flottabilité SEAMON E	DEPLOYMENT flotta Seamon E par le TGF	C. Podeur
28/05/2021	20:32:00	N 37 16.790	W 032 14.518	OBS autonome	Deployment OBS LSVEO par le treuil hydro	T. Dumouch
29/05/2021	13:53:00	N 37 17.953	W 032 15.978	BOREL	Recovery BOREL	C. Podeur
30/05/2021	07:41:00	N 37 18.284	W 032 16.375	Deployment océano	Recovery Deployment océano	S. Leizour
30/05/2021	16:05:00	N 37 18.186	W 032 17.849	SEAMON Est	Recovery Seamon E	C. Podeur
31/05/2021	06:03:00	N 37 19.077	W 032 16.737	OBS autonome	Recovery OBS LSVNN	T. Dumouch
31/05/2021	20:38:00	N 37 19.154	W 032 16.848	OBS autonome	Deployment OBS LSVNO	T. Dumouch
03/06/2021	16:22:00	N 37 16.025	W 032 15.506	Deployment Océano	Deployment océano	S. Leizour
06/06/2021	07:19:00	N 37 17.785	W 032 16.413	Deployment microRIO	Recovery Deployment microryo	S. Leizour
07/06/2021	07:20:00	N 37 17.624	W 032 16.436	SEAMON Ouest	Deployment of Seamon W	C. Podeur
07/06/2021	09:23:00	N 37 17.472	W 032 16.826	SEAMON Ouest	Seamon W bottom release	C. Podeur
07/06/2021	14:33:02	N 37 18.165	W 032 16.130	Deployment Océano	Triangulation Deployment oceano	B. Ferron
07/06/2021	18:23:00	N 37 18.204	W 032 14.850	BOREL	mooring BOREL	C. Podeur
10/06/2021	06:51:00	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.175	SEAMON Est	Seamon E deployment by deep cable	C. Podeur
10/06/2021	09:00:00	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.594	SEAMON Est	Seamon E bottom release	C. Podeur

8.2. List of CTD-LADCP and VMP mooring

Correspondant B. Ferron, CNRS-LOPS

Date	# sta	Time	Latitude	Longitude	Depth	Device	Observation
26/05	1	18:16	37°17.579'N	32°17.213'W		CTD	600 m south of @ MRY - SBE3F failed
27/05	1	20:19 surfaced at 21:36	37°17.801'N	32°16.779'W	1667	VMP	VMP @ 140 m N of MRY Lests 18 cm + Supp. 1 (+ 2 petites feuilles de plomb scotchées anneau de récup.)
27/05	2	20:49	37°17.538'N	32°16.720'W		CTD	CTD @ 354 m S-SE of MRY
29/05	2	29/05 20:25 surfaced at 02:48 on May 30	37°17.821'N	32°16.861'W	1646	VMP	Lests 18 cm + Supp. 1 VMP @ 228 m N of MRY VMP resurfaced only @02:48 on May 30. Release problem. Galvanic released the weights about 6 hours after deployment. max_pressure = 1566 in setup file and max(P)=1674 dbar reached
29/05	3	20:44	37°17.562'N	32°16.771'W		CTD	CTD @ 304 m S of MRY
31/05	3	20:11	37°17.717'N	32°16.776'W	1720	VMP	Lests 18 cm + Supp. 1

							VMP @ 25 m SW of MRY (instead of 100 m SE)
31/05	4	20:44	37°17.578'N	32°16.751'W		CTD	CTD @ 275 m S of MRY sbt failure, one more time. Cleaning F2 contact + grease once again!
01/06	5	20:07	37°17.506'N	32°16.848'W		CTD	CTD test RBR pallier à 600 m
01/06	6	21:03	37°17.506'N	32°16.854'W		CTD	CTD normale 15 m du fond à la suite de station CTD#5. RBR en place sauf le duet T-P qui ne peut aller au dela de 1000 m.
02/06	4	18:03	37°17.739'N	32°16.790'W	1722	VMP	Lests de 16 cm + Supp. 1 pour tests processing vibrations - Pas de CTD
02/06	5	20:35	37°17.554'N	32°16.846'W	1720	VMP	Lests de 18 cm + Supp. 1 Répétition station 4 à plus grand vitesse de descente
02/06	7	20 :54	37°17.559'N	32°16.860'W		CTD	
03/06	6	13:43	37°17.736'N	32°16.791'W	~1700	VMP	Lests 18 cm + Supp. 1
03/06	7	20:43	37°17.771'N	32°16.786'W		VMP	Lests 18 cm + Supp. 1
03/06	8	21:13	37°17.548'N	32°16.810'W		CTD	
04/06	8	20:07	37°17.738'N	32°16.815'W	1689	VMP	Lests 18 cm + Supp. 1
04/06	9	20:23	37°17.543'N	32°16.773'W		CTD	
05/06	9	18:09	37°17.726'N	32°16.809'W	~1700	VMP	Lests 16 cm avec Supp.1 enlevé
05/06	10	20:35	37°17.697'N	32°16.834'W	~1700	VMP	Lests 18 cm + Supp.2 (=Olive 400 g + Supp1)
05/06	10	20:48	37°17.559'N	32°16.799'W		CTD	
06/06	11	20:07	37°17.733'N	32°16.808'W	~1700	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2
06/06	11	20:22	37°17.538'N	32°16.775'W		CTD	
08/06	12	20:06	37°17.555'N	32°16.828'W	1727	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2 VMP dans lac de lave, CTD au point MicroRiYo
08/06	12	20:22	37°17.751'N	32°16.768'W		CTD	
09/06	13	20:01	37°17.548'N	32°16.873'W	1731	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2 VMP dans lac de lave, CTD au point MicroRiYo
09/06	13	20:15	37°17.744'N	32°16.740'W		CTD	
10/06	14	20:04	37°19.207'N	32°19.461'W	2065	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2 point sur transect#13
10/06	14	20:21	37°19.190'N	32°19.610'W		CTD	
11/06	15	20:05	37°19.200'N	32°19.455'W	2065	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2 - point sur transect#13 Pas de LACP cause traque du bruit à 1 Hz sur SBE3F. Conclusion: rien à voir avec le ping du LADCP
11/06	15	20:16	37°19.158'N	32°19.643'W		CTD	
12/06	16	19:56	37°17.540'N	32°16.852'W	1732	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2 - proche centre lac de lave
12/06	16	20:15	37°17.505'N	32°16.588'W		CTD	
13/06	17	20:03	37°17.540'N	32°16.882'W	1736	VMP	Lests 18 + Supp. 2 - proche centre lac de lave
13/06	17	20:15	37°17.744'N	32°16.740'W		CTD	

8.3. Moorings deployed or recovered during the cruise with the HOV NAUTILE

NOM	Date_pose	PL_pose	Date_récup	PL_récup	Site	Latitude	Longitude	Profondeur	Correspondant
Biolucky	24/09/2018	708-13	28/05/2021	1991	Lucky strike	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.533	1689	C. Rommevaux
Biolucky	12/06/2021	2004			Montsegur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	C. Rommevaux
BT10-TEMPO	16/09/2020	755-3	09/06/2021	2001	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.542	1697	M. Matabos
BT11	09/06/2021	2001			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	M. Matabos
BT11-TEMPO	16/09/2020	755-3	26/05/2021	1989	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.324	W 032 16.536	1694	M. Matabos
BT12	09/06/2021	2001			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.536	1697	M. Matabos
BT13	09/06/2021	2001			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	M. Matabos
BT5-TEMPO	20/06/2019	1946-8	26/05/2021	1989	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1693	M. Matabos
BT6-TEMPO	16/09/2020	755-3	26/05/2021	1989	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.532	1692	M. Matabos
BT7-TEMPO	16/09/2020	755-3	26/05/2021	1989	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.325	W 032 16.533	1693	M. Matabos
DEEP-SEEDS_2021	02/06/2021	1996			Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.832	1669	J. Sarrazin
HTNKE29008	13/09/2020	753-1			White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
HTNKE29016	06/06/2021	1999			Cyprès	N 37 17.456	W 032 16.848	1744	M. Cannat
HTNKE29006	06/06/2021	1999			Montsegur	N 37 17.296	W 032 16.532	1744	M. Cannat
HTNKE29006	20/09/2020	758-6	30/05/2021	1993	South Crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
HTNKE29008	13/06/2021	2005			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.539	1696	M. Cannat
HTNKE29009	30/05/2021	1993			White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 32 15.930		M. Cannat
HTNKE29012	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.359	W 032 16.541	1693	M. Cannat
HTNKE29012	17/09/2020	757-5	06/06/2021	1999	Montsegur	N 37 17.292	W 032 16.534	1744	M. Cannat
HTNke29017	13/09/2020	753-1	30/05/2021	1993	South Crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930	0.0	M. Cannat
HTNKE29017	20/09/2020	758-6	30/05/2021	1993	South Crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930	0.0	M. Cannat
HTNKE29020	21/09/2020	759-7	06/06/2021	1999	Cyprès	N 37 17.456	W 032 16.848	1744	M. Cannat
HTNKE30001	06/06/2021	1999			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.516	1706	M. Cannat
HTNKE30014	22/09/2020	761-9	01/06/2021	1995	Seamon E	N 37 17.321	W 032 16.543	1699	M. Cannat
HTNKE30002	30/05/2021	1993			South Crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat

HTNKE30005	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.531	1691	M. Cannat
HTNKE30005	22/09/2020	761-9	30/05/2021	1993	Tour Eiffel	N 37 15.990	W 32 15.930		M. Cannat
HTNKE30006	23/09/2020	761-9			Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.506	1622	M. Cannat
HTNKE30007	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	M. Cannat
HTNKE30011	22/09/2020	760-8	04/06/2021	1997	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.506	1622	M. Cannat
HTNKE30012	01/06/2021			1995	Seamon E	N 37 17.326	W 032 16.540	1697	M. Cannat
HTNKE30014	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1702	M. Cannat
HTNKE30015	04/06/2021	1997			Sintra	N 37 17.532	W 032 16.496	1620	M. Cannat
HTNKE38001	18/09/2020	757-5	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.330	W 032 16.522	1706	M. Cannat
HTNKE38002	30/05/2021	1993			White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
HTNKE38003	30/05/2021	1993			White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
HTNKE38003	17/09/2020	757-5	26/05/2021	1989	Montsegur	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.552	1700	M. Cannat
HTW004	17/09/2020	757-5	02/06/2021	1996	Capelinhos	N 37 17.364	W 032 15.832	1663	M. Cannat
HTW04	11/06/2021	2003			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.523	1687	M. Cannat
HTW005	30/05/2021	1993			White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
HTW008	16/09/2020	755-3	31/05/2021	1994	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.526	1687	M. Cannat
HTW019	02/06/2021	1996			Capelinhos	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.832	1663	M. Cannat
HTW019	22/09/2020	761-9			Lucky strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930	1719.0	M. Cannat
HTW08	06/06/2021	1999			South Crystal	N 37 17.435	W 032 16.925	1726	M. Cannat
HTWN011	25/09/2020	763-11	28/05/2021	1991	AISICS	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.527	1686	M. Cannat
HTWN013	09/06/2021	2001			Montségur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.534	1703	M. Cannat
HTWN013	18/09/2020	757-5	06/06/2021	1999	Cimendef	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.558	1703	M. Cannat
HTWN019	30/05/2021	1993			White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
HTWN019	17/09/2020	757-5	26/05/2021	1989	Montsegur	N 37 17.273	W 032 16.539	1700	M. Cannat
HTWN021	11/06/2021	2003			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.341	W 032 16.526	1693	M. Cannat
HTWN021	13/09/2020	753-1	06/06/2021	1999	White Castle	N 37 17.401	W 032 16.861	1726	M. Cannat
HTW010	13/09/2020	753-1	30/05/2021	1993	White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
LSCAP4	17/09/2020	757-5	02/06/2021	1996	Capelinhos	N 37 17.371	W 032 15.830	1671	M. Cannat
LSCAP5	02/06/2021	1996			Capelinhos	N 37 17.372	W 032 15.829	1670	M. Cannat
LSCY5	04/09/2016	631-8			Cypress hill	37.290757	-32.281087	1739.0	M. Cannat

LSCy6	13/08/2018	698-3	06/06/2021	1999	Cyprès	N 37 17.442	W 032 16.858	1744	M. Cannat
LSEV5	31/08/2016	628-5			Lucky strike	37.2916665	-32.2783335	1961.0	M. Cannat
LSNTE1	24/08/2018	708-13			Tour Eiffel	37.289067	-32.27555	0.0	M. Cannat
LSLL&	08/06/2021	2000			Lac de lave	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.784	1748	M. Cannat
LSTE8-2020	24/09/2020	762-10	27/05/2021	1990	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.533	1694	M. Cannat
LTgrad-10	18/09/2020	757-5	31/05/2021	1994	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.552	1702	M. Cannat
LTgrad-11	20/09/2020	758-6	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.533	1694	M. Cannat
LTgrad-12	23/09/2020	762-10	30/05/2021	1993	Seamon E	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
LTgrad-2	18/09/2020	757-5	31/05/2021	1994	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.546	1696	M. Cannat
LTgrad-4	18/09/2020	757-5	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.328	W 032 16.518	1707	M. Cannat
LTgrad-6	20/09/2020	758-6	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.509	1707	M. Cannat
LTgrad-7	20/09/2020	758-6	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.345	W 032 16.518	1694	M. Cannat
LTgrad-8	18/09/2020	757-5	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.514	1707	M. Cannat
LTgrad-9	18/09/2020	757-5	31/05/2021	1994	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1700	M. Cannat
LTgrad1	06/06/2021	1999			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.518	1708	M. Cannat
LTgrad10	14/06/2021	2006			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.519	1704	M. Cannat
LTGrad12	13/06/2021	2005			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.544	1696	M. Cannat
LTGrad13	13/06/2021	2005			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.543	1698	M. Cannat
LTGrad14	13/06/2021	2005			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.550	1699	M. Cannat
LTGrad15	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.531	1705	M. Cannat
LTgrad2	06/06/2021	1999			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.322	W 032 16.515	1706	M. Cannat
LTgrad5	06/06/2021	1999			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.519	1693	M. Cannat
LTgrad9	06/06/2021	1999			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.350	W 032 16.530	1694	M. Cannat
LTi1	13/06/2021	2005			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.546	1701	M. Cannat
LTNKE26004	13/06/2021	2005			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.549	1697	M. Cannat
LTNKE26004	18/09/2020	757-5	31/05/2021	1994	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.554	1701	M. Cannat
LTW013	22/09/2020	761-9	30/05/2021	1993	South Crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930	1720.0	M. Cannat
LTW017	30/05/2021	1993			South Crystal	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		M. Cannat
LTW018	06/06/2021	1999			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.517	1695	M. Cannat
LTW018	18/09/2020	757-5	31/05/2021	1994	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.545	1696	M. Cannat

LTW040	20/09/2020	758-6	06/06/2021	1999	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.518	1695	M. Cannat
LTW40	14/06/2021	2006			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.548	1696	M. Cannat
Mésocosme	09/06/2021	2001			Montségur	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.533	1707	M. Matabos
Pyramide I2	25/08/2018	708-13			Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.540	1655	M. Matabos/J. Sarrazin
Pyramide POMME R1	12/06/2021	2004			Montsegur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.537	1704	M. Matabos/J. Sarrazin
Pyramide POMME P1	13/06/2021	2005			Montsegur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.520	1707	M. Matabos/J. Sarrazin
Pyramide POMME C1bcg	09/06/2021	2001			Montségur	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.527	1708	M. Matabos/J. Sarrazin
Pyramide POMME C2bcg	09/06/2021	2001			Montségur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.530	1706	M. Matabos/J. Sarrazin
TCM3-1	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.538	1704	M. Cannat
TCM3-1	01/07/2019	1956-18	27/05/2021	1990	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.378	W 032 16.555	1692	M. Cannat
TCM3-2	22/09/2020	761-9	01/06/2021	1995	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.300	W 032 16.542	1701	M. Cannat
TCM3-3	11/06/2021	2003			South Crystal	N 37 17.447	W 032 16.898	1730	M. Cannat
TCM3-3	20/09/2020	758-6	07/06/2021	1999	South Crystal	N 37 17.447	W 032 16.906	1730	M. Cannat
TCM3-A	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.511	1693	M. Matabos
TCM3-A-2020	22/09/2020	760-8	01/06/2021	1995	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.544	1692	M. Matabos
TCM3-B	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.342	W 032 16.547	1694	M. Matabos
TCM3-B-2020	20/09/2020	758-6	01/06/2021	1995	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.538	1691	M. Matabos
TCM3-C	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1693	M. Matabos
TCM3-D	12/06/2021	2004			Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.351	W 032 16.538	1692	M. Matabos
TCM3-D-2020	22/09/2020	760-8	27/05/2021	1990	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.343	W 032 16.529	1695	M. Matabos

8.4. List of samples

8.4.1. Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing (ABS)

Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing (ABS)

An e-mail has been sent (20/01/21) to Paulo Carmo (Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas, IP, Chefe da Divisão de Aplicação de Normativos) to obtain an update on the actual regulation in the Azores regarding the access to genetic resources in Portugal within the framework of the Nagoya Protocol (Convention on Biological Diversity). The Azores authorities (aida.mc.medeiros@azores.gov.pt ; Joao.MR.Gregorio@azores.gov.pt) were copied in the email exchange (see emails in annex)

Paulo Carmo replied similarly to 2020 indicating the absence of progress in Portugal regarding the Nagoya protocol

“Sujet : RE: Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources - EMSO Azores project

Date : Wed, 21 Apr 2021 13:09:24 +0000

De : Paulo Carmo <Paulo.Carmo@icnf.pt>

Pour : Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr <Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr>

Copie à : Teresa Leonardo <Teresa.Leonardo@icnf.pt>, Vanessa Quico <Vanessa.Quico@icnf.pt>

Dear Marjolaine Matabos

First of all please let me apologise for the late reply. Your message from the January 20th arrived exactly in the first days of my period of Covid-19 illness and many of the emails I received during that period are still waiting that I have the chance to revise and reply, if it is the case.

Regarding your question below, I just have to inform you that there aren't any changes yet to the information I sent to your colleague Pierre-Marie Sarradin back in October 2019 (in attachment).

Sorry again for the delay

Best regards

Paulo Carmo

Chefe da Divisão de Aplicação de Normativos / DAN

Departamento de Conservação da Natureza e da Biodiversidade

Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e das Florestas, IP

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Uma imagem com texto Descrição gerada automaticamente

logo_icnf”

The authorization for access to the natural resources of the Azores and collection of samples for scientific purposes will be requested as every year prior the cruise on the following website:

- Request for Authorization to Access / Sampling for Scientific Purposes in (http://www.formstack.com/forms/GRA-Request_Access_Sampling_Scientific_Purposes) -

Anyhow, the biological samples that will be collected during the cruise will be used only to acquire fundamental knowledge on the temporal dynamics, the functioning and the resilience of hydrothermal ecosystems of the Lucky Strike area.

The list of these samples, the associated metadata, and the researchers responsible are compiled in a specific table below.

The samples will not be shared to any other team without the authorization of the chief scientist.

Any modification in the use of the samples (e.g. study on their economic valorization) will be reported.

8.4.2. Liste of samples

Date	Plongée	Heure	Site	Lat.	Long.	Prof.	Opérations
26/05/2021	1989-1	11:26	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.469	W 032 16.782	1700	PLUME 1 – bottom water
26/05/2021	1989-1	11:32	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.469	W 032 16.782	1700	PLUME 2 – bottom water
26/05/2021	1989-1	11:40	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.469	W 032 16.782	1693	PLUME 3 – bottom water
26/05/2021	1989-1	11:53	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.469	W 032 16.782	1700	PLUME 4 – bottom water
26/05/2021	1989-1	14:49	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.639	1700	PIF Syringe 1 start non-filtered
26/05/2021	1989-1	14:52	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.709	1693	PIF Syringe 2 non-filtered
28/05/2021	1991-3	13:50	AISICS	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.519	1686	Sample chimney 13h54 PBT4
28/05/2021	1991-3	14:03	AISICS	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.526	1694	Sample old chimney PBT3
28/05/2021	1991-3	16:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.534	1692	Sample PLUME bag 5 for 4 min
28/05/2021	1991-3	16:56	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.347	W 032 16.529	1693	Sample NTE-FeOx mats PBT2
30/05/2021	1993-5	12:43	White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti1 triggered
30/05/2021	1993-5	12:54	White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti2 triggered
30/05/2021	1993-5	13:00	White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Ti3 released
31/05/2021	1994-6	12:35	Montségur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.534	1705	Syringe Ti n°3: M21FLU07
31/05/2021	1994-6	13:14	Montségur	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.538	1705	Syringe Ti n°2: M21FLU08
31/05/2021	1994-6	13:19	Montségur	N 37 17.275	W 032 16.536	1706	Syringe Ti n°1 M21FLU09
31/05/2021	1994-6	15:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.525	1686	Syringe Ti n°5: M21FLU10
31/05/2021	1994-6	15:29	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.529	1685	Syringe Ti n°6: M21FLU11
31/05/2021	1994-6	15:33	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.335	W 032 16.529	1684	Syringe Ti n°4: M21FLU12
31/05/2021	1994-6	12:51	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.534	1704	Top of chimney PBT1.
31/05/2021	1994-6	13:00	Montségur	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.537	1705	Bottom of chimney PBT2.
01/06/2021	1995-7	11:08	Seamon E	N 37 17.319	W 032 16.535	1697	Niskin sample
01/06/2021	1995-7	12:57	Montségur	N 37 17.254	W 032 16.527	1702	Sample PIF middle C2a - 4,690°C
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:14	Montségur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.536	1702	Sample PIF middle C2bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:30	Montségur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.532	1702	Sample PIF middle R0
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:46	Montségur	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.531	1702	Sample PIF middle R1
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:06	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.531	1702	Sample PIF middle R2cg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:21	Montségur	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.532	1702	Sample PIF middle C2acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:32	Montségur	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.530	1702	Sample PIF middle C2b
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:51	Montségur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.532	1702	Sample PIF middle C1b
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:09	Montségur	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.535	1702	Sample PIF middle C1bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:21	Montségur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.529	1702	Sample PIF middle C1acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:40	Montségur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.538	1702	Sample PIF middle C1a

01/06/2021	1995-7	16:03	Montségur	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.540	1702	PLUME 2 A. LAES
01/06/2021	1995-7	16:20	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.540	1702	PLUME3
02/06/2021	1996-8	10:29	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.192	W 032 15.899	1691	PLUME, channel 2. T°C 4.5
02/06/2021	1996-8	10:33	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.230	W 032 15.895	1691	PLUME, channel 3. T°C 4.5.
02/06/2021	1996-8	10:58	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.831	1663	Sample chimney PBT2
02/06/2021	1996-8	11:18	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.833	1663	Trigger TI3 at 11H18
02/06/2021	1996-8	11:20	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.833	1663	Trigger Ti2
02/06/2021	1996-8	11:24	Capelinhos	N 37 17.360	W 032 15.828	1663	Trigger Ti1
02/06/2021	1996-8	11:36	Capelinhos	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.831	1664	Sample small « flange » covered with anhydrite in PBT1
02/06/2021	1996-8	12:51	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 15.812	1689	Blade-core CL7
02/06/2021	1996-8	12:51	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.414	W 032 15.812	1689	Blade-core CL6
02/06/2021	1996-8	14:32	Capelinhos	N 37 17.368	W 032 15.828	1672	Sample iron mats in PBT3
02/06/2021	1996-8	16:11	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.839	1660	Suction sample jar 1 shrimp
02/06/2021	1996-8	16:11	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.363	W 032 15.840	1660	Suction sample jar 2
02/06/2021	1996-8	16:12	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.839	1660	Suction sample jar 3
04/06/2021	1997-9	11:16	Y3	N 37 17.507	W 032 16.662	1733	Sample top of chimney Y3
04/06/2021	1997-9	11:33	Y3	N 37 17.505	W 032 16.663	1731	Sample bottom part/sulfide of chimney Y3
04/06/2021	1997-9	11:52	Y3	N 37 17.506	W 032 16.666	1732	Trigger Syringe Ti n°1 at 11:52:17
04/06/2021	1997-9	12:03	Y3	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.674	1729	Trigger Syringe Ti n°2 at 12:03:23
04/06/2021	1997-9	12:07	Y3	N 37 17.516	W 032 16.668	1731	Trigger Syringe Ti n°3 at 12:07:18
04/06/2021	1997-9	12:40	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.665	1730	Sample Chemini at 12:40:15
04/06/2021	1997-9	12:44	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.666	1731	Sample PLUME 2 - 4.940°C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	12:51	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.673	1735	Sample microbial mats Y3 in PBT3
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:25	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.544	1655	Sample PIF Syringe n°1 filtered on middle point I1. Temperature = 4,670 °C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:29	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.542	1656	Sample PIF Syringe n°2 non filtered on middle point I1.
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:43	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.540	1653	Sample PIF sur Syringe n°3 filtered on middle point I2. Temperature = 4.630 °C. Start chemini Fe/ S measurements.
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:46	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.541	1653	Sample PIF Syringe n°4 non filtered on middle point I2. Temperature = 4.620°C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	15:40	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.496	1621	Trigger Syringe Ti n°4.
04/06/2021	1997-9	15:41	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1620	Trigger Sample Syringe Ti n°5
04/06/2021	1997-9	15:43	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Déclanchement Syringe Ti n°6 à 15:43:47.
04/06/2021	1997-9	15:52	Sintra	N 37 17.531	W 032 16.498	1619	Suction sampler jar 1 shrimp
04/06/2021	1997-9	16:20	Sintra	N 37 17.499	W 032 16.571	1667	Start Sample bag PLUME 4 - 5.160 °C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	16:29	Sintra	N 37 17.500	W 032 16.570	1669	Sample microbial mats in PBT4.

05/06/2021	1998-10	10:58	Montségur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1702	Sample bag PLUME 2 on mussel bed. Probe TNaut = 6,23 °C.
05/06/2021	1998-10	11:11	Montségur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.523	1707	Sample mussels in PBT4.
05/06/2021	1998-10	11:33	Montségur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.529	1705	Sample PLUME 3 on musselbed.
05/06/2021	1998-10	11:45	Montségur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.522	1708	Sample ELFES 1 on musselbed.
05/06/2021	1998-10	12:12	Montségur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.521	1707	Suction in ELFES 3 on musselbed.
05/06/2021	1998-10	12:23	Montségur	N 37 17.288	W 032 16.526	1708	Suction mussels in suction sampler jar 1.
05/06/2021	1998-10	13:13	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.305	W 032 16.526	1707	Sample carottier lame CL6 à PA1.
05/06/2021	1998-10	14:18	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.539	1699	Sample PLUME 4.
05/06/2021	1998-10	14:27	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.539	1699	Suction mussels in suction sampler jar 2.
05/06/2021	1998-10	14:33	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.539	1700	Suction shrimp in suction sampler jar 3.
05/06/2021	1998-10	14:35	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.337	W 032 16.538	1700	Suction shrimp in suction sampler jar 4
05/06/2021	1998-10	14:41	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.540	1699	Suction shrimp in suction sampler jar 5.
05/06/2021	1998-10	15:09	Isabel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.634	1703	Sample PLUME 6.
05/06/2021	1998-10	15:19	Isabel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.628	1699	Sample microbial mats in PBT3
06/06/2021	1999-11	13:23	South Crystal	N 37 17.439	W 032 16.927	1726	Ti 3 triggered
06/06/2021	1999-11	13:25	South Crystal	N 37 17.439	W 032 16.927	1726	Ti 2 triggered
06/06/2021	1999-11	13:27	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.927	1725	Ti 1 triggered 21
06/06/2021	1999-11	13:44	South Crystal	N 37 17.440	W 032 16.935	1724	Corer blade CL6
06/06/2021	1999-11	13:52	South Crystal	N 37 17.437	W 032 16.929	1726	Corer blade CL7
08/06/2021	2000-12	13:07	Lac de lave	N 37 17.545	W 032 16.786	1744	Start Sample PLUME 3
08/06/2021	2000-12	13:13	Lac de lave	N 37 17.549	W 032 16.790	1741	Start Sample iron mat PBT
08/06/2021	2000-12	15:42	Montségur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1704	Trigger Ti3
08/06/2021	2000-12	15:46	Montségur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.535	1704	Trigger Ti2
08/06/2021	2000-12	15:48	Montségur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.532	1704	Trigger Ti1
09/06/2021	2001-13	15:33	Montségur	N 37 17.303	W 032 16.543	1704	Mussel sampling for mesocosme
11/06/2021	2003-15	10:47	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.524	1695	Sample chimney AISICS in PBT4
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:21	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.531	1691	Suction jar ASPI 1
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.448	1692	Suction jar ASPI 2
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:24	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.340	W 032 16.525	1692	Suction jar ASPI 3
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:50	Cimendef	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.554	1700	Trigger Syringe titanium syringe Ti3
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:52	Cimendef	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.556	1700	Trigger Syringes titanium syringe Ti2
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:53	Cimendef	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.556	1701	Trigger Syringe titanium syringes Ti1
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:33	Cyprès	N 37 17.450	W 032 16.854	1739	Sample de la cheminée dans PBT4
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:52	Cyprès	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.861	1740	Trigger Syringe Titanium syringe Ti4
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:55	Cyprès	N 37 17.454	W 032 16.864	1740	Trigger Syringe Titanium syringe Ti5
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:57	Cyprès	N 37 17.534	W 032 16.655	1741	Trigger Syringe Titanium syringe Ti6
11/06/2021	2003-15	16:00	Cyprès	N 37 17.619	W 032 16.618	1741	Suction jar ASPI 4
11/06/2021	2003-15	16:02	Cyprès	N 37 17.611	W 032 16.611	1740	Suction jar ASPI 5

12/06/2021	2004-16	11:30	Montségur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1704	Sample chimney at ex-DEAFS
12/06/2021	2004-16	11:45	Montségur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Trigger Titanium syringe 3 site ex-DEAFS
12/06/2021	2004-16	11:52	Montségur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1704	Sample Syringe Titanium syringe 1 ex-DEAFS
12/06/2021	2004-16	15:57	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1689	Sample titanium syringe 4 in smoker ISABEL
12/06/2021	2004-16	16:02	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1687	Sample titanium syringe 6 in smoker ISABEL
12/06/2021	2004-16	16:22	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.555	1701	Blade corer CL6
12/06/2021	2004-16	16:23	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.348	W 032 16.555	1699	Blade corer CL7
13/06/2021	2005-17	11:25	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.147	W 032 16.669	1611	PLUME#3 Sample
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:05	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.309	W 032 16.537	1707	NISKIN Sample
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:38	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.522	1706	Sample PIF Syringe non-filtered #7
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:39	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.520	1707	Sample PIF Syringe non-filtered #9
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:42	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.521	1707	Sample PIF Syringe filtered #8
13/06/2021	2005-17	13:01	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.236	W 032 16.505	1718	Trigger of CL#6
13/06/2021	2005-17	13:01	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.236	W 032 16.505	1718	Trigger of CL#7
13/06/2021	2005-17	16:23	Crystal	N 37 17.450	W 032 16.913	1727	Trigger of la Syringe Ti#3
13/06/2021	2005-17	16:26	Crystal	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.912	1726	Trigger of la Syringe Ti#2
13/06/2021	2005-17	16:30	Crystal	N 37 17.448	W 032 16.915	1726	Trigger of la Syringe Ti#1
14/06/2021	2006-18	12:57	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.539	1704	Sample mussels in PBT4
14/06/2021	2006-18	13:23	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.546	1702	Sample titanium syringe Ti6
14/06/2021	2006-18	13:26	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.545	1702	Sample titanium syringe Ti5
14/06/2021	2006-18	13:27	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.547	1702	Sample titanium syringe Ti4
14/06/2021	2006-18	16:15	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.479	W 032 16.782	1744	Trigger Niskin

8.5. List of continuous measurements

Equipment operated by NAUTILE : Temperature sensor, CHEMINI Fe(II), CHEMINI Sulfides, Optode

Date	Plongée	Heure	Site	Lat.	Long.	Prof.	Opérations
28/05/2021	1991-3	16:45	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.349	W 032 16.533	1692	Measure of temperature 4,70°C
30/05/2021	1993-5	12:33	White Castle	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Measurement temperature Nautile
30/05/2021	1993-5	15:24	Lucky Strike	N 37 15.990	W 032 15.930		Prise T NAUT 5.3°C
31/05/2021	1994-6	12:30	Montségur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.533	1705	Measurement Temperature with Probe TNaut.
31/05/2021	1994-6	13:07	Montségur	N 37 17.276	W 032 16.537	1706	Measurement temperature with Probe TNaut sur exDEAFS
31/05/2021	1994-6	15:21	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.529	1685	Temperature measured: 320°C.
01/06/2021	1995-7	12:57	Montségur	N 37 17.254	W 032 16.527	1707	Chemini middle C2a
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:05	Montségur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.534	1706	Chemini corner 1 C2a
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:09	Montségur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.535	1706	Chemini corner 2 C2a
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:14	Montségur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.536	1705	Chemini middle C2bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:20	Montségur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.536	1706	Chemini corner 1 C2bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:24	Montségur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.534	1703	Chemini corner 2 C2bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:30	Montségur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.532	1707	Chemini middle R0
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:34	Montségur	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.524	1706	Chemini corner 1 R0
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:39	Montségur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.535	1706	Chemini corner 2 R0
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:47	Montségur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.530	1707	Chemini middle R1
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:52	Montségur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.528	1708	Chemini corner 1 R1
01/06/2021	1995-7	13:56	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.534	1709	Chemini corner 2 R1
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:06	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.531	1705	Chemini middle R2cg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:11	Montségur	N 37 17.268	W 032 16.520	1704	Chemini corner 1 R2cg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:15	Montségur	N 37 17.279	W 032 16.532	1705	Chemini corner 2 R2cg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:21	Montségur	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.532	1705	Chemini middle C2acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:26	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.534	1704	Chemini corner 1 C2acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:30	Montségur	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.533	1703	Chemini corner 2 C2acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:34	Montségur	N 37 17.277	W 032 16.529	1705	Chemini C2b
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:39	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.531	1704	Chemini corner 1 C2b
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:43	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.531	1704	Chemini corner 2 C2b
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:52	Montségur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.532	1702	Chemini middle C1b
01/06/2021	1995-7	14:57	Montségur	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.531	1702	Chemini corner 1 C1b
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:01	Montségur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.533	1702	Chemini corner 2 C1b
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:09	Montségur	N 37 17.293	W 032 16.535	1703	Chemini middle C1bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:13	Montségur	N 37 17.295	W 032 16.530	1701	Chemini corner 1 C1bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:17	Montségur	N 37 17.285	W 032 16.526	1704	Chemini corner 2 C1bcg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:23	Montségur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.528	1707	Chemini middle C1acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:27	Montségur	N 37 17.287	W 032 16.528	1707	Chemini corner 1 C1acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:31	Montségur	N 37 17.299	W 032 16.528	1706	Chemini corner 2 C1acg
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:40	Montségur	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.538	1704	Chemini middle C1a
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:44	Montségur	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.546	1705	Chemini corner 1 C1a
01/06/2021	1995-7	15:48	Montségur	N 37 17.278	W 032 16.540	1706	Chemini corner 2 C1a
01/06/2021	1995-7	16:01	Montségur	N 37 17.280	W 032 16.538	1705	Chemini pour PLUME A.LAES
02/06/2021	1996-8	11:13	Capelinhos	N 37 17.362	W 032 15.829	1663	Measure of temperature in small smoker. 102.9°C
02/06/2021	1996-8	13:25	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.286	W 032 15.737	1680	Start reversing thermometer. T°C du fond 4.57
04/06/2021	1997-9	11:41	Y3	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.673	1729	Measurement of temperature with Nautile temperature probe
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:26	Sintra	N 37 17.512	W 032 16.543	1655	Chemini Fe & S on middle point i1.
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:31	Sintra	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.541	1657	Chemini Fe & S on corner 1 de i1
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:35	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.541	1656	Chemini point corner 2 I1- 4.660°C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:43	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.540	1653	Chemini Fe & S on middle point i2 - 4.630 °C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:47	Sintra	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.539	1651	Chemini on corner 1 of I2
04/06/2021	1997-9	14:52	Sintra	N 37 17.517	W 032 16.537	1650	Chemini on corner 2 of I2 - 4.640 °C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	15:24	Sintra	N 37 17.527	W 032 16.502	1620	Measurement of temperature on probe HTNKE 30011. Temperature = 5.9°C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	15:37	Sintra	N 37 17.533	W 032 16.494	1622	Measurement of temperature with Probe T Naut. Mac temperature measured = 221 °C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	16:16	Sintra	N 37 17.498	W 032 16.571	1668	Measurement temperature with probe TNaut. Temperature max = 7.160 °C.
04/06/2021	1997-9	16:18	Sintra	N 37 17.499	W 032 16.571	1668	Start Measurements Cheminis Fe & S
05/06/2021	1998-10	10:56	Montségur	N 37 17.284	W 032 16.533	1703	Measurement probe TNaut : 5,8°C on musselbed

05/06/2021	1998-10	11:31	Montségur	N 37 17.289	W 032 16.527	1706	Measurement Probe TNaut = 5,400 °C on mussels
05/06/2021	1998-10	13:50	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.257	W 032 16.705	1648	Measurement Probe TNaut = 4,620 °C. to calibrate reversing thermometer on elevator
05/06/2021	1998-10	14:17	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.334	W 032 16.538	1699	Measurement Probe TNaut = 4,610 °C on mussels
05/06/2021	1998-10	15:08	Isabel	N 37 17.336	W 032 16.633	1704	Measurement Probe TNaut = 4,600 °C.
05/06/2021	1998-10	15:54	Y3	N 37 17.515	W 032 16.684	1733	Positionning Nautilie and lasers to start acquisition on Y3.
06/06/2021	1999-11	13:18	South Crystal	N 37 17.431	W 032 16.931	1726	Measurement temperature probe TNaut
08/06/2021	2000-12	13:05	Lac ofve	N 37 17.546	W 032 16.784	1745	Measurement de temperature PLUME 4.6 °C
08/06/2021	2000-12	15:33	Montségur	N 37 17.286	W 032 16.534	1704	Start Measurement of temperature for syringe sampling
09/06/2021	2001-13	14:06	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.532	1698	Chemini S on point 1 diffusing smoker
09/06/2021	2001-13	14:11	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.331	W 032 16.529	1697	Chemini point 2 mussels
09/06/2021	2001-13	14:16	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.344	W 032 16.536	1699	Chemini point 3 top mussels
09/06/2021	2001-13	14:19	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.332	W 032 16.534	1698	Chemini point 4 on barytine (8,06°C)
09/06/2021	2001-13	14:26	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.338	W 032 16.536	1696	Chemini point 5 on BT13-33, microbial mats, T°C = 4,96°C
09/06/2021	2001-13	14:30	Tour Eiffel	N 37 17.333	W 032 16.537	1696	Chemini point 6 top small mussels on rock
11/06/2021	2003-15	13:45	Cimendef	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.557	1702	Probe TNaut start Measurement of temperature. 300°C
11/06/2021	2003-15	14:35	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.266	W 032 16.709	1643	Reversing thermometer triggered
11/06/2021	2003-15	14:35	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.267	W 032 16.709	1643	Probe TNaut 4.5°C
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:38	Cyprès	N 37 17.446	W 032 16.860	1740	Probe TNaut start Measurement of temperature inthe smoker of the sampled chimney 295°C
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:39	Cyprès	N 37 17.448	W 032 16.859	1740	Measurement of temperature on anotehr fluid exit
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:42	Cyprès	N 37 17.450	W 032 16.862	1741	Probe TNaut start temperature 264°C
11/06/2021	2003-15	15:44	Cyprès	N 37 17.451	W 032 16.859	1740	Probe Tnaut start in first fluid exit 295°C
12/06/2021	2004-16	11:40	Montségur	N 37 17.261	W 032 16.554	1705	Probe T Nautilie site ex-DEAFS
12/06/2021	2004-16	15:52	Isabel	N 37 17.380	W 032 16.642	1691	Probe TNaut : 293°C
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:33	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.282	W 032 16.520	1707	Measurements chemini POINT1 on Merces P
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:39	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.521	1706	Measurements Chemini point 2 on Merces P
13/06/2021	2005-17	12:46	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.283	W 032 16.521	1706	Measurements chemini point 3 on Merces P
13/06/2021	2005-17	16:19	Crystal	N 37 17.449	W 032 16.913	1727	Probe TNaut Measurement max = 315°C
14/06/2021	2006-18	13:19	Lucky Strike	N 37 17.281	W 032 16.550	1701	Measurement of temperature with TNaut probe
14/06/2021	2006-18	15:12	Sintra	N 37 17.514	W 032 16.543	1653	Measurement chemini FE + S middle MERCES I2
14/06/2021	2006-18	15:18	Sintra	N 37 17.511	W 032 16.539	1655	Measurement chemini FE + S corner 1 MERCES I2
14/06/2021	2006-18	15:23	Sintra	N 37 17.513	W 032 16.535	1657	Measurement chemini FE + S corner 2 MERCES I2
14/06/2021	2006-18	15:38	Sintra	N 37 17.509	W 032 16.545	1655	Measurement chemini FE + S middle MERCES I1
14/06/2021	2006-18	15:44	Sintra	N 37 17.518	W 032 16.543	1667	Measurement chemini FE + S corner 1 MERCES I1
14/06/2021	2006-18	15:49	Sintra	N 37 17.519	W 032 16.543	1667	Measurement chemini FE + S corner 2 MERCES I1

8.6. List of 4K video sequences

Date	Plongée	Nom de fichier	Durée	Site
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T114217.013	00:00:21	Seamon W
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T114248.403	00:00:41	Seamon W
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T114329.987	00:00:11	Seamon W
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T115122.522	00:00:57	Seamon W
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T120350.801	00:01:00	Seamon W
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T125628.933	00:00:09	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T125827.598	00:04:11	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T132309.317	00:02:10	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T132631.541	00:02:02	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T133034.164	00:00:21	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T133714.941	00:00:51	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T134053.493	00:00:51	TEMPO
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T140424.085	00:01:39	Fumeur DEAFs
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T141204.934	00:00:18	Montsegur
26/05/2021	PL1989-1	20210526T141425.67	00:04:05	Montsegur
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T102512.851	00:16:26	Lucky Strike
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T110317.916	00:03:23	Seamon W
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T120925.053	00:00:09	Seamon W
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T123818.181	00:21:19	Tour Eiffel
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T140618.213	00:29:59	Seamon E
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T143618.219	00:29:59	Tour Eiffel
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T150618.227	00:29:58	Tour Eiffel
27/05/2021	PL1990-2	20210527T153618.224	00:27:22	Tour Eiffel
28/05/2021	PL1991-3	20210528T114141.81	00:00:05	Colonne d'eau
28/05/2021	PL1991-3	20210528T124804.312	00:01:16	AISICS
28/05/2021	PL1991-3	20210528T134705.531	00:00:51	AISICS
28/05/2021	PL1991-3	20210528T164748.141	01:00:08	Tapis de fer TE Nord
28/05/2021	PL1991-3	20210528T170618.172	00:00:36	Tour Eiffel Nord
28/05/2021	PL1991-3	20210528T171045.025	00:01:25	Tour Eiffel Nord
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T112350.321	00:08:50	Seamon E
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T113505.267	00:20:04	Tour Eiffel
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T120721.459	00:29:59	Lucky Strike ouest
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T123721.46	00:13:04	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T125155.261	00:03:25	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T130003.152	00:03:51	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T130837.204	00:10:49	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T132402.348	00:17:00	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T134106.364	00:10:41	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T142152.63	00:11:18	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T143319.296	00:29:59	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T150319.304	00:05:52	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T151051.655	00:12:27	White Castle
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T152322.741	00:14:59	Lucky Strike
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T153955.556	00:16:57	Lucky Strike
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T155700.199	00:24:59	South Crystal
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T162202.247	00:01:21	South Crystal
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T162332.344	00:01:24	South Crystal

30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T162625.689	00:02:04	South Crystal
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T163306.432	00:07:52	South Crystal
30/05/2021	PL1993-5	20210530T164858.387	00:09:52	South Crystal
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T111914.529	00:18:46	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T113809.44	00:00:08	Ascenseur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T115609.247	00:13:19	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T121027.186	00:09:22	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T122721.022	00:29:59	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T125721.043	00:29:59	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T132721.05	00:29:59	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T135721.053	00:29:59	Montségur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T142721.06	00:23:23	Ascenseur
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T145716.573	00:05:32	Tour Eiffel
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T151627.628	00:01:25	Tour Eiffel
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T154327.137	00:29:59	Tour Eiffel
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T161327.144	00:29:58	Tour Eiffel
31/05/2021	PL1994-6	20210531T164327.157	00:04:57	Nautile
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T110521.396	00:00:25	Seamon E
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T110649.199	00:02:45	Seamon E
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T114859.82	00:00:06	Transit
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T122911.909	00:00:40	Montségur
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T123437.012	00:00:56	Montségur
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T123618.067	00:27:33	Montségur
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01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T131803.57	00:08:55	Montségur
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01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T135805.638	00:00:10	Montségur
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T140550.86	00:11:24	Montségur
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T145444.081	00:12:22	Montségur
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T153328.103	00:00:01	Montségur
01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T153330.561	00:29:56	Montségur
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01/06/2021	PL1995-7	20210601T161335.185	00:29:59	Montségur
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T101004.997	00:00:04	Pompe
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T104140.236	00:29:59	Transit
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T111140.241	00:29:59	Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T114140.259	00:01:04	Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T114250.531	00:28:32	Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T135835.19	00:29:59	Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T142835.192	00:21:12	Tapis de fer Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T152443.592	00:04:57	Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T153224.149	00:29:59	Capelinhos
02/06/2021	PL1996-8	20210602T160224.162	00:08:05	Capelinhos
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T110806.962	00 :01 :22	Y3
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T110956.13	00 :01 :09	Y3
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T111412.548	00 :04 :01	Y3
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04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T122703.6	00 :04 :04	Tapis de fer Isabel
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T124059.408	00 :02 :29	Tapis de fer Isabel
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T125202.409	00 :01 :34	Tapis de fer Isabel
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T125400.517	00 :01 :21	Tapis de fer Isabel

04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T125709.46	00 :01 :30	Tapis de fer Isabel
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T141331.464	00 :20 :39	Sintra inactif
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T153455.925	00 :03 :34	Sintra
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T153929.286	00 :05 :36	Sintra
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T154547.868	00 :01 :48	Sintra
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T155129.157	00 :01 :38	Sintra
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T161042.207	00 :00 :48	Tapis de fer Sintra
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T161222.289	00 :07 :04	Tapis de fer Sintra
04/06/2021	PL1997-9	20210604T162931.328	00 :02 :43	Tapis de fer Sintra
05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T101325.788	00:00:03	Lucky Strike
05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T105111.784	00:29:59	Montségur
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05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T114459.443	00:18:40	Montségur
05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T130711.299	00:17:42	Montségur
05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T140821.526	00:29:59	Tour Eiffel
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05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T154047.05	00:10:10	Y3
05/06/2021	PL1998-10	20210605T155240.851	00:13:31	Y3
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06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T123136.006	00:11:44	
06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T124335.787	00:01:04	
06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T130836.904	00:29:59	South Crystal
06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T133836.908	00:29:59	Cimendef ?
06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T140836.911	00:29:59	Lucky Strike
06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T143836.914	00:29:59	Montségur
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06/06/2021	PL1999-11	20210606T170836.96	00:21:55	Tour Eiffel
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T104932.169	00:06:20	Seamon W
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T133320.079	00:00:02	Lucky Strike
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08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T134418.798	00:03:10	Ascenseur
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T140626.034	00:26:39	Montségur
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T144707.317	00:04:06	Ascenseur
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T150540.122	00:21:19	Montségur
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T155107.254	00:00:02	Montségur
08/06/2021	PL2000-12	20210608T155110.368	00:24:16	Montségur
09/06/2021	PL2001-13	20210609T133505.089	00:27:36	Tour Eiffel
09/06/2021	PL2001-13	20210609T140241.801	00:29:59	Tour Eiffel
09/06/2021	PL2001-13	20210609T143241.791	00:29:59	Tour Eiffel
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09/06/2021	PL2001-13	20210609T153854.096	00:03:01	Montségur
09/06/2021	PL2001-13	20210609T155119.499	00:04:21	Montségur
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09/06/2021	PL2001-13	20210609T164338.487	00:13:17	Montségur
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10/06/2021	PL2002-14	20210610T130751.727	00:00:59	Seamon Est
10/06/2021	PL2002-14	20210610T132741.346	00:05:41	Seamon Est

10/06/2021	PL2002-14	20210610T135608.396	00:26:26	Seamon Est
10/06/2021	PL2002-14	20210610T154608.045	00:15:40	Seamon Est
10/06/2021	PL2002-14	20210610T164244.927	00:23:21	Seamon Est
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12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T105954.108	00 :04 :19	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T110859.967	00 :07 :28	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T112018.178	00 :05 :11	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T112619.576	00 :00 :27	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T112813.962	00 :00 :03	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T113026.107	00 :01 :05	Montsegur
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12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T114424.173	00 :09 :13	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T115813.973	00 :00 :07	Lucky Strike
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12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T125052.568	00 :09 :42	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T131051.733	00 :13 :01	Montsegur
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T134940.431	00 :29 :59	Tour Eiffel
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T141940.447	00 :08 :28	Tour Eiffel
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12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T152938.128	00 :01 :24	Tour Eiffel
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T154512.384	00 :09 :31	Tour Eiffel
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T155448.406	00 :09 :47	Isabel
12/06/2021	PL2004-16	20210612T161638.436	00 :07 :26	Tour Eiffel
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T121956.778	00:00:47	Montségur
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T122602.608	00:05:20	Montségur périphérie
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T130038.195	00:16:55	Site référence Montségur
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T133853.508	00:00:48	Montségur
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T134441.993	00:01:48	Montségur
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T161251.166	00:07:42	Crystal
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T162146.177	00:19:23	Crystal
13/06/2021	PL2005-17	20210613T164708.48	00:02:34	Crystal
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T105344.097	00:00 :06	Lucky Strike
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T112344.104	00:15:16	Seamon Est
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T115230.708	00:01:12	Seamon Est
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T115344.115	00:00:48	Seamon Est
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T121009.552	00:00:14	Seamon Est
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T122344.132	00:03:56	Seamon Est
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T125344.129	00:02:08	Tour Eiffel
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14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T132134.493	00:02:09	Cimendef
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T132344.137	00:00:17	Cimendef
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T132713.23	00:01:41	Cimendef
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T135344.152	00:29:59	Tour Eiffel
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T142344.161	00:29:59	Lucky Strike
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T145344.165	00:29:59	Sintra inactif
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T152344.176	00:29:59	Sintra inactif
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T155344.185	00:05:07	Sintra inactif
14/06/2021	PL2006-18	20210614T161527.439	00:02:14	Seamon ouest

9. Annexes

 S. R.		
MINISTÉRIO DOS NEGÓCIOS ESTRANGEIROS Direção-Geral de Política Externa		
<hr/>		
Ref.ª 52109/2021 Proc.º DGPE/USEN-22/2021 26/04/2021		
NOTA VERBAL		
<p>O Ministério dos Negócios Estrangeiros apresenta os seus melhores cumprimentos à Embaixada de França em Lisboa e, em referência à Nota Verbal nº 2021-0045845, de 29.01.2021, tem a honra de informar que é autorizada a entrada na ZEE portuguesa, subárea dos Açores, do navio oceanográfico "ATALANTE" bem como a campanha de investigação "MOMASART2021" a realizar no período de 01 de maio a 20 de junho de 2021, no pressuposto de que serão cumpridos todos os formalismos constantes do Anexo I.</p> <p>Considerando esta missão de grande interesse científico, o Ministério dos Negócios Estrangeiros muito agradece que lhe sejam enviados os dados processados, assim que terminar a campanha, para atualização da informação, acompanhados posteriormente do respetivo Relatório, preferencialmente em suporte eletrónico.</p> <p>O Ministério dos Negócios Estrangeiros aproveita a oportunidade para reiterar à Embaixada de França os protestos da sua mais elevada consideração.</p>		
<p>À Embaixada de França em Lisboa</p>		
<hr/>		
Largo do Rivas 1399-030 Lisboa	1 Telefona: (351) 213946000	E-mail: dgpe@mne.pt

ANEXO I

- 1.0 NAVIO DE FRANÇA "ATALANTE" PRETENDE EFETUAR A CAMPANHA OCEANOGRÁFICA "MOMASART 2021", NA ZEE PORTUGUESA SUB ÁREA DOS ACORES, NO PERÍODO DE 01 DE MAIO A 20 DE JUNHO DE 2021.
2. CONSIDERA-SE QUE A ÁREA DE OPERAÇÕES INTERFERE COM AS ÁREAS DE PASSAGEM HABITUAL DE SUBMARINOS.
3. NÃO OBSTANTE NÃO ESTAR NENHUMA NAVEGAÇÃO SUBMARINA NO PERÍODO CONSIDERADO, TORNA-SE NECESSÁRIO TER CONHECIMENTO COM 72 HORAS DE ANTECEDÊNCIA DAS INTENÇÕES DE MOVIMENTOS E POSIÇÕES DE TRABALHO DO NAVIO "ATALANTE" POR FORMA ASSEGURAR SEGURANÇA NAVEGAÇÃO SUBMARINA NACIONAL E ESTRANGEIRA.
4. PARA ESTE EFEITO O NAVIO DEVERÁ MANTER O AIS SEMPRE EM FUNCIONAMENTO E EFETUAR UM COMUNICADO DIÁRIO, DIRIGIDO AO CENTRO DE OPERAÇÕES MARÍTIMAS (COMAR), COM SEGUINTE INFORMAÇÃO:
 - A. IDENTIFICAÇÃO DO NAVIO.
 - B. POSIÇÃO/RUMO/VELOCIDADE REFERIDA ÀS 1200Z.
 - C. ACTIVIDADE EM CURSO/POSIÇÕES DE EQUIPAMENTOS FUNDEADOS.
 - D. INTENÇÕES PROXIMAS 24, 48 E 72 HORAS.
 - E. NR. TELEX / INMARSAT FAX E TELEFONE / EMAIL NAVIO.
5. SOLICITA-SE AINDA QUE SEMPRE QUE HAJA ALTERAÇÃO AOS DADOS DO PLANEAMENTO, ESTA SEJA COMUNICADA COM A MÁXIMA ANTECEDÊNCIA POSSÍVEL, DESEJAVELMENTE COM 72 HORAS E NUNCA MENOS DE 24 HORAS.
6. PARA PASSAGEM DA INFORMAÇÃO ACIMA REFERIDA, PODERÃO SER UTILIZADOS SEGUINTE MEIOS:
 - A. TELEFONE :00 210 984 451;
 - B. E-MAIL: COMAR.SUPERVISOR@MARINHA.PT
 - E. E-MAIL: CZMA.EM.CSINF@MARINHA.PT
7. NO DECURSO DOS TRABALHOS DE INVESTIGAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA, DESIGNADAMENTE DURANTE AS OPERAÇÕES DE MANUSEAMENTO DOS EQUIPAMENTOS, OUTROS MATERIAIS SUBMERSOS E BÓIAS DE SINALIZAÇÃO, BEM COMO NAS MANOBRAS A QUE O NAVIO ESTIVER SUJEITO, DEVEM SER SALVAGUARDADAS AS DISTÂNCIAS MÍNIMAS DE SEGURANÇA QUER AOS CABOS SUBMARINOS (1/4 MILHA) IDENTIFICADOS NAS CARTAS NÁUTICAS OFICIAIS, QUER AOS NAVIOS (1 MILHA) ENVOLVIDOS EM REPARAÇÕES OU LANÇAMENTO DE CABOS. DE FORMA A EMITIR ATEMPADAMENTE OS AVISOS À NAVEGAÇÃO, COMAR DEVERÁ SER INFORMADO DOS MOVIMENTOS E LIMITAÇÕES DE MANOBRAS DO NAVIO COM 72H DE ANTECEDÊNCIA, ATRAVÉS DO SEGUINTE E-MAIL: COMAR.SEGMAR@MARINHA.PT
9. O CENTRO DE CONTROLO DE TRÁFEGO MARÍTIMO DO CONTINENTE (CCTMC), DEVE SER TAMBÉM INFORMADO DIARIAMENTE SOBRE O PLANEAMENTO DOS MOVIMENTOS DO NAVIO PARA AS 24 HORAS SEGUINTE, BEM COMO QUALQUER ALTERAÇÃO AO PLANEAMENTO OU QUAISQUER INCIDENTES/ACIDENTES QUE INTERFERAM COM OS TRABALHOS, PARA PASSAGEM DESTA INFORMAÇÃO DEVERÃO SER USADOS OS SEGUINTE MEIOS:
 - EMAIL: OPER.VTS@DGRM.MM.GOV.PT
 - FAX: + 351 214464839
 - TEL: + 351 244648389
 - VHF: CANAIS 22 OU 79.

AUTORIZAÇÃO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA EM ÁREA MARINHA PROTEGIDA
AUTHORIZATION AREA FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN MARINE PROTECTED AREA

1. Local onde se desenvolverá o trabalho / Area of the Study:

Parque Marinho dos Açores / Azores Marine Park DLR n.º 13/2016/A Reserva Natural Marinha do Campo Hidrotermal Lucky Strike (PMA03)

2. Titular da Licença / License Holder :

Nome / Name: Pierre Marie Sarradin
Nr. Identi Civil / ID Number : 15DD40606
Instituição / Institution: IFREMER - Institut français de recherche pour l'exploitation de la mer
E-mail : [Pierre.Marie.Sarradin@ifremer.fr](mailto: Pierre.Marie.Sarradin@ifremer.fr)

3. Nome do Projeto / Project Name :

MoMARSAT 2021

4. Objetivo / Purpose :

Manutenção anual do observatório EMSO-Açores no Lucky Strike (MAR).

Yearly maintenance of the EMSO-Azores observatory at lucky Strike (Mid-Atlantic Ridge).

5. Métodos / Equipamentos a Usar / Methods / Equipments :

Infraestrutura de investigação marinha EMSO.

ROV, submarino.

Marine Research Infrastructure EMSO.

ROV, submarine.

6. Recolha de Amostras / Sample Recolection :

Recolha de amostras de fluidos hidrotermais, organismos (incluindo *Bathymodiolus azoricus*, *Segonzacia mesatlantica* e *Mirocaris fortunata*) e microorganismos de profundidade, rochas, sedimentos e água do mar.

Collection of samples of hydrothermal fluids, deep-sea organisms (including Bathymodiolus azoricus, Segonzacia mesatlantica e Mirocaris fortunata) and micro-organisms, rocks and sea water.

7. Duração / Duration:

De 1 de maio e 20 de junho de 2021.

May 1 to June 20, 2020.

8. Condicionantes / Conditions:

Findo o estudo, o titular deve entregar à DRAM um relatório resultante do estudo.

A presente licença não inibe do cumprimento de qualquer outra legislação aplicável à ação em curso.

Upon completion of the study, the holder shall submit to DRAM a report resulting from this study.

This authorization does not prevent the fulfillment of any other legislation applicable to the current action.

Data de emissão / Date of issue :

Dia / Day
Mês / Month
Ano / Year

O DIRETOR REGIONAL DOS ASSUNTOS DO MAR,
THE REGIONAL DIRECTOR FOR SEA AFFAIRS,

Assinado por: PEDRO MANUEL MENDONÇA DAS
NEVES
Num. de Identificação: B1095737235
Data: 2021.03.29 17:39:53+00'00'

REGIÃO AUTÓNOMA DOS AÇORES
SECRETARIA REGIONAL DA CULTURA, DA CIÊNCIA E TRANSIÇÃO DIGITAL
Direção Regional da Ciência e Transição Digital

Acesso e utilização de recursos naturais para fins científicos / Access and use of natural resources for scientific purposes

Certificado de Conformidade Internacionalmente Reconhecido
Internationally Recognized Compliance Certificate

13 /2021/DRCTD

A TODO O TEMPO O TITULAR PODE FICAR OBRIGADO A: / THE HOLDER MAY AT ANY TIME BE OBLIGED TO:

- a) **Depositar ou remeter duplicado da amostra**, ou parte dela, no prazo e local a determinar pela entidade emissora da declaração, nos termos do disposto no n.º 1 do artigo 11.º do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Deposit or send a duplicate of the sample, or part of it, within the time and place to be determined by the entity issuing the declaration; pursuant to paragraph 1 of article 11 of the Regional Legislative Decree No. 9/2012 / A, of March 20th, with the changes introduced by Regional Legislative Decree No. 17/2020 / A, of July 15th;*
- b) **Enviar o relatório** a que se refere o n.º 2 do artigo 11.º do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Submit the report referred to in paragraph 2 of article 11 of the Regional Legislative Decree no. 9/2012 / A, of March 20, with the changes introduced by Regional Legislative Decree no. 17/2020 / A, of July 15;*
- c) **Contratualizar mecanismos de cooperação com a RAA**, nos termos do disposto no artigo 17.º-B do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Contract cooperation mechanisms with the RAA, pursuant to article 17-B of the Regional Legislative Decree No. 9/2012 / A, of March 20, with the changes introduced by Regional Legislative Decree No. 17/2020 / A, of July 15;*
- d) **Realizar um contrato de partilha justa e equitativa de benefícios** nos termos do disposto no artigo 17.º-C do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho; *Carry out a fair agreement for the just and equitable sharing of benefits; Enter into a fair and equitable benefit sharing agreement under the terms of article 17;*
- e) **Não permitir a utilização da amostra, ou de parte dela, por terceiros**, exceto nos casos de procedimento de transferência previstos no capítulo III do Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 9/2012/A, de 20 de março, com as alterações introduzidas pelo Decreto Legislativo Regional n.º 17/2020/A, de 15 de julho. *Do not allow the use of the sample, or part of it, by third parties, except in cases of transfer procedure provided for in Chapter III of Regional Legislative Decree No. 9/2012 / A, of March 20, with the changes introduced by Regional Legislative Decree No. 17/2020 / A, of July 15.*

TITULAR DO CCIR / DECLARATION OWNER

CRUISE: L'ATALANTE – Campanha MOMARSAT 2020 - Ifremer
CIENTISTA CHEFE DO CRUZEIRO - Pierre Marie SARRADIN /M.MATABOS

Nº de Identificação Civil/Passaporte | *National Identity Card/Passport: N/A*

Endereço/Address:

Ifremer Brest, REM/EEP, Ifremer - Centre de Bretagne, ZI de la pointe du diable, CS10070,

Código Postal/Zip code | País/Country: F-29280 PLOUZANE, France

Instituição/Institution :

Ifremer/Direction de la Flotte Oceanographique

EQUIPA ENVOLVIDA NAS ATIVIDADES DE ACESSO/ IDENTIFICATION OF THE TEAM INVOLVED IN ACCESS ACTIVITIES:

Colaborador/Investigador <i>Collaborator/Researcher</i>	Atividade profissional/ Occupation	Instituição/ <i>Institution</i>
Pierre Marie Sarradin	Chief scientist	Ifremer (Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer)
M. Matabos	Chief scientist	Ifremer (Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer)
Mathilde Cannat	Coordination Geophysics	IPGP-Equipe Géosciences Marines Géologie/Géophysique
Laurent Gautier	Coordination Infrastructure	Ifremer
Jozée Sarrazin	Coordination Ecology	Ifremer
Participação Portuguesa no Projeto		Instituição
Ana Colaço	Researcher	IMAR - Departamento de Oceanografia e Pescas – OKEANOS UAç- Écologie

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Participantes da Campanha	Atividade profissional/ Occupation	Instituição/Institution
Alain Castillo	Fluid geochemistry	
Valérie Chavagnac	Fluid geochemistry	
Christine Destrigneville	Fluid geochemistry	
Simon Besançon	Instrumentation, Geophysics	
Fabrice Fontaine	Geophysics	
Benjamin Wheeler	Geophysics	
Céline Rommevaux	Geomicrobiology	
Anne Godfroy	Microbiology	
Agathe Laes	Chemistry, instrumentation infrastructure	
Morgane Hubert	Habitat biogeochemistry	
Laurent Gautier	Electronics/coordination	
Nicolas Mertz	Electronics/infrastructure	
Bertrand Moreau	Electronics/infrastructure	
Jean Pierre Lafontaine	Mechanics/infrastructure	
Christian Podeur	Mechanics/infrastructure	
Loïc Michel	Ecology	
Loïc Van Audenhaege	Ecology	
Bruno Ferron	Physical oceanography	

RECURSO NATURAL A ACEDER / NATURAL RESOURCE SAMPLE

Identificação do tipo de amostra/ Sample type identification:

Recolha de dados geofísicos, oceanográficos, fluidos hidrotermais, organismos e microrganismos de profundidade, rochas, sedimentos e água do mar. Haverá uma recolha dirigida *Bathymodiolus azoricus* (moluscos bivalves-mexilhões) e ainda ao caranguejo *Segonzacia mesatlantica* e camarões *Mirocaris fortunata*, que serão mantidos vivos em aquários e transportados para o Oceanopolis em Brest, para a exposição "Abyss box" (colaboração entre o Oceanopolis, a Universidade de Paris Sorbonne (UPMC) e o IFREMER, envolvendo o IMAR-DOP desde 2012).

Nome científico (quando aplicável) /Scientific name (when applicable):

Bathymodiolus azoricus
Segonzacia mesatlantica
Mirocaris fortunata

Forma, quantidade e tamanho exetável (com recurso a descritores de peso e dimensões físicas sempre que justificável):

Expected shape, quantity and size (including weight and size whenever justified):

Indeterminado (constar em relatório).

Métodos a utilizar/Methods to be used:

Durante o cruzeiro serão utilizados vários instrumentos e metodologias de amostragem através do submersível ROV, nomeadamente coletores de água, pinças, draga, caixas de amostragem e módulos de colonização; Instrumentos autónomos como 4 OBS, uma amarração oceanográfica, CDT, uma matriz de sondas de temperatura e operação de um VMP (microprofiler vertical).

DETALHES DA AMOSTRAGEM/ SAMPLING DETAILS

Data de início de recolha (mês e ano) e fim de recolha/ Starting collection date and Ending collection date:

01 de maio 2021 a 20 de junho de 2021.

Locais de recolha/ Sampling Locations:

Campo hidrotermal LUCKY STRIKE; Coordenadas: N37.25 ° N37.33 °W32.18 ° - W32.38 ° a 1700 m de profundidade

USOS A QUE SE DESTINA/INTENDED USES:

A missão MOMARSAT 2021, levada a cabo pelo IFREMER (Instituto francês de investigação e exploração do mar), na continuação das realizadas em anos anteriores, tem por objetivo a manutenção da infraestrutura do mar profundo EMSO e a vigilância sísmica da dorsal médio atlântica, a análise e exploração da dinâmica espacial e da circulação hidrotermal na zona Lucky Strike).

O projeto MoMAR (Monitoring the Mid-Atlantic Ridge) iniciou-se há 20 anos atrás, com o programa InterRidge, para promover e coordenar o estudo multidisciplinar a longo prazo dos campos hidrotermais da Crista Médio-Atlântica (MAR). Tem como objetivos estudar a dinâmica dos campos hidrotermais, desde a sua geofísica até à microbiologia. A infraestrutura de investigação marinha EMSO (marine Research Infrastructure EMSO) foi instalada no Lucky Strike em 2010. É em primeiro lugar destinada a estudar o sistema de fontes hidrotermais, a câmara magmática subjacente, os microhabitats e fauna

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hidrotermal que abriga e as características da pluma hidrotermal. A manutenção anual é feita recorrendo a um ROV. Inclui a recuperação de instrumentos e amarrações, reparação e check-up de cada componente da estação e recolocação no local. Adicionalmente são recolhidas amostras de fauna e fluidos, feitos vídeos das fontes hidrotermais e habitats, que permitem monitorizar o local ao longo do tempo.

A missão MoMARSAT tem como objetivo a manutenção anual do observatório EMSO-Açores no Lucky Strike (MAR). Após a missão de manutenção de 2020, a infraestrutura EMSO é composta por dois equipamentos de monitorização (SEAMON), ligados acusticamente com uma boia à superfície (BOREL), possibilitando a comunicação por satélite para a estação terrestre em Brest. A boia retransmissora está equipada com uma estação meteorológica, um GPS geodésico, e um AIS.

Parte da amostragem será feita no âmbito do projeto da UE Mercês (WP4 liderado por Telmo Morato - IMAR-Pt e Andrew Sweetman -HWU-UK) e do projeto ECOREF (PI M. Matabos, financiamento da Equinor). O objetivo específico é avaliar a capacidade de resiliência das comunidades de mexilhões após a sua retirada e o papel dos grandes predadores nos processos de recolonização na região Meso-Atlântica onde será avaliada a taxa e o sucesso da recuperação não assistida de comunidades de fontes hidrotermais ativas após distúrbios significativos usando uma experiência in situ de 3 anos.

Também a amostragem será feita no âmbito do projeto TENSE (Transfer of ENergy in hydrothermal vents – an in Situ Experiment) é uma colaboração entre o Ifremer (FR), the University of Western Brittany (FR) o CHIMAR (PT, Dr. Teresa Amaro), e é financiado pelo ISblue (Interdisciplinary graduate School for the BLUE planet, FR). Em que o seu objetivo é estudar como *Bathymodiolus azoricus* (moluscos bivalves-mexilhões) influencia a taxa e as formas de fixação do carbono nas cadeias alimentares das fontes hidrotermais. Seis pequenos dispositivos (0.07 m²) serão instalados nas agregações de mexilhões e bicarbonato marcado com 13C será adicionado. O surgimento deste carbono marcado será seguido nos tecidos dos mexilhões e fauna associada após 3 e 7 dias. Este projeto irá contribuir para o conhecimento sobre os processos que condicionam o papel do *Bathymodiolus azoricus* como uma espécie fundadora, e irá complementar o trabalho anterior, permitindo apreender as interações tróficas que ocorrem em leitos hidrotermais de mexilhões com resolução sem precedentes. Ao fazer isso, este projeto aumentará o conhecimento sobre o funcionamento dos ecossistemas hidrotérmicos e ajudará a definir as melhores recomendações para a sua conservação.

Este projeto está relacionado com os seguintes projetos Europeus:

- MERCES (Marine Ecosystem Restoration in Changing European Seas, Coordinator Roberto Danovaro Università Politecnica delle Marche, Italy);- -EMSO (European Multidisciplinary Sea Observatory) coordination P. Favali – INGV);
- ECOREF (PI M. Matabos, Funding from EQUINOR);
- iAtlantic (Integrated assessment of the Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in space and time).

As amostras recolhidas destinam-se a estudos para compreender o funcionamento e as dinâmicas dos sistemas dos campos hidrotermais e à publicação de artigos científicos.

INTENÇÃO DE TRANSFERÊNCIA DA AMOSTRA PARA TERCEIROS/ TRANSFER INTENT:

- Não/No
 Sim/Yes
 Não Determinado/Not determined

**NO CASO DE HAVER INTENÇÃO DE TRANSFERÊNCIA/IN CASE OF TRANSFER INTENTION:
IDENTIFICAÇÃO COMPLETA DE TERCEIROS/COMPLETE THIRD PARTY IDENTIFICATION:**

Nome/Name:

Oceanopolis em Brest, para a exposição “Abyss box” (colaboração entre o Oceanopolis, a Universidade de Paris Sorbonne (UPMC) e o IFREMER, envolvendo o IMAR-DOP desde 2012).

A transferência das amostras (nome científico das amostras) no âmbito do projeto (nome do projeto) /

The transfer of samples (scientific name of the samples) within the project (project name):

Caranguejo *Segonzacia mesatlantica* e camarões *Mirocaris fortunata*, (serão mantidos vivos em aquários e transportados)

O titular fica adstrito aos cumprimentos de todas as obrigações a que o anterior titular se encontrava vinculado/

The holder of the declaration is bound to comply with all obligations to which the previous holder was bound to.

Ponta Delgada, 5 de março de 2021

O Diretor Regional da Ciência e Transição Digital

Sérgio Ávila

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----- Message transféré -----

Sujet : Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources - EMSO Azores project

Date : Wed, 20 Jan 2021 09:57:50 +0100

De : Marjolaine MATABOS <Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr>

Organisation : IFREMER

Pour : Paulo.Carmo@icnf.pt

Copie à : jozee SARRAZIN <jozee.sarrazin@ifremer.fr>, aida.mc.medeiros@azores.gov.pt, Joao.MR.Gregorio@azores.gov.pt

Dear Paulo Carmo,

I am a researcher working for Ifremer, a French public scientific research institute.

I will be leading a research oceanographic cruise in May and June this year for the maintenance of the EMSO Azores deep-sea observatory, within the framework of the European Infrastructure EMSO ERIC (<http://emso.eu/> <<http://emso.eu/>>). This research infrastructure has been deployed in 2010 at the Lucky Strike vent field and is maintained during the yearly Momarsat oceanographic cruises (<http://www.emso-fr.org/fr/EMSO-Azores> <<http://www.emso-fr.org/fr/EMSO-Azores>>). I got your contact through my colleague Pierre-Marie Sarradin who was the chief scientist of the Momarsat cruises the previous years.

I contact you today regarding the access to genetic resources in Portugal within the framework of the Nagoya Protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization (Convention on Biological Diversity).

In this context, the Regulation (EU) No 511/2014 and the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1866 both regulate access to genetic resources for a research project taking place in the European Union. They require all users of genetic resources and traditional knowledge associated with genetic resources to exercise due diligence to ascertain whether they have been accessed in accordance with applicable legal or regulatory requirements and to ensure that, where relevant, benefits are fairly and equitably shared.

The next maintenance cruise of the observatory will be held from May 10th to June 5th 2020 and will involve the sampling of some of the biological resources present in your jurisdiction (only for fundamental research purposes).

During your last exchanges with Pierre-Marie you indicated that "*there is no national legislation nor any regulatory requirements drawing from the Nagoya Protocol for *_access to_* genetic resources in ***mainland Portugal****".

Do you have any updated information regarding the procedure to follow to comply with your national legislation in force?

Could you please indicate which form are needed to be granted access and to comply with international, European and national legislations ? I filled the online form specific to the request for the collection of natural resources for scientific purposes in the Autonomous Region of Azores (GRA-Request_Access_Sampling_Scientific_Purposes>).

Thank you in advance for the time granted to my request.

If you require any further information please do not hesitate to contact me.

Looking forward to hearing from you shortly

Best regards

Marjolaine Matabos

--

Marjolaine Matabos, PhD
Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la MER
Unité Etude des Ecosystèmes Profonds
Laboratoire Environnement Profond

Centre de Bretagne
ZI de la pointe du Diable, CS 10070
29280 PLOUZANE
FRANCE

e-mail : Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr
Tel: +33 (0)2 98 22 43 05
Site WEB : <http://wvz.ifremer.fr/deep>
www.deepseaspy.com

Email envoyé le 2 avril

----- Message transféré -----

Sujet :Fwd: Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources - EMSO Azores project

Date :Fri, 2 Apr 2021 08:11:08 +0200

De :Marjolaine MATABOS <Marjolaine.Matabos@ifremer.fr>

Pour :abs@icnf.pt, secretariado.cd@icnf.pt

Copie à :marco.rebelo@icnf.pt, jozee SARRAZIN <jozee.sarrazin@ifremer.fr>

Hello,

Please find below a message sent in January to Paulo Carmo regarding the Momarsat 2021 cruise that will be held from May 20th to June 15th at the Lucky Strike vent field. Paulo is the one who provided answers at the time of our 2020 cruise. I will be leading the expedition which is dedicated to the maintenance of the EMSO-Azores observatory.

I contact you regarding the access to genetic resources in Portugal within the framework of the Nagoya Protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization (Convention on Biological Diversity). Do you have any updated information regarding the procedure to follow to comply with your national legislation in force? We are most particularly looking for the PIC and MAT forms.

Thank you in advance for your response,
All the best,
Marjolaine Matabos

MINISTÈRE DES AFFAIRES ÉTRANGÈRES
Direction générale de la Politique Étrangère

Réf. 52109/2021

Dossier DGPE/USEN-22/2021

26/04/2021

NOTE VERBALE

Le ministère des Affaires étrangères présente ses meilleures salutations à l'ambassade de France à Lisbonne et, en référence à la Note Verbale n° 2021-0045845, du 29.01.2021, a l'honneur de l'informer que l'entrée du navire océanographique « **ATALANTE** » dans la ZEE portugaise, sous-zone des Açores, est autorisée, ainsi que la campagne de recherche « **MOMASART2021** », qui sera menée au cours de la période allant du 1^{er} mai au 20 juin 2020, sous réserve que l'ensemble des formalités visées à l'Annexe I soient remplies.

Compte tenu du grand intérêt scientifique que présente cette mission, le ministère des Affaires étrangères vous remercie par avance de bien vouloir lui communiquer les données qui auront été traitées et lui signaler la fin de la campagne, pour la mise à jour des informations, accompagnées, ultérieurement, du Rapport correspondant, de préférence sous format électronique.

Le ministère des Affaires étrangères prie l'ambassade de France d'agréer l'expression de sa considération distinguée

L'ambassade de
France à Lisbonne

Largo do Rílvas
1399- 030 LISBONNE

1
TÉLÉPHONE (351) 213946000

E-mail : dgpe@mne.pt

ANNEXE I :

1. LE NAVIRE FRANÇAIS « ATALANTE » SOUHAITE MENER LA CAMPAGNE OCÉANOGRAPHIQUE « MOMASART 2021 » DANS LA ZEE PORTUGAISE SOUS-ZONE DES AÇORES, AU COURS DE LA PÉRIODE DU 01 MAI AU 20 JUIN 2021.
2. IL APPARAÎT QUE LA ZONE DES OPÉRATIONS INTERFÈRE AVEC LES ZONES DE PASSAGE HABITUELLES DE SOUS-MARINS.
3. AINSI, ET SANS PRÉJUDICE DU FAIT QU'AUCUNE NAVIGATION DE SOUS-MARINS N'EST PRÉVUE PENDANT LA PÉRIODE VISÉE, IL SERA NÉCESSAIRE DE COMMUNIQUER 72 HEURES À L'AVANCE LES DÉPLACEMENTS ET LES POSITIONS DE TRAVAIL PRÉVUS DU NAVIRE « ATALANTE » AEND D'ASSURER LA SÉCURITÉ DE LA NAVIGATION SOUS-MARINE NATIONALE ET ÉTRANGÈRE.
4. À CET EFFET, LE NAVIRE DEVRA MAINTENIR SON SYSTÈME D'IDENTIFICATION AUTOMATIQUE (AIS) EN FONCTIONNEMENT PERMANENT ET ENVOYER UN COMMUNIQUÉ QUOTIDIEN AU CENTRE DES OPÉRATIONS MARITIMES (COMAR), COMPRENANT LES INFORMATIONS SUIVANTES :
 - A. IDENTIFICATION DU NAVIRE.
 - B. POSITION/CAP/VITESSE VISÉE AHS 1200Z
 - C. ACTIVITÉ EN COURS/POSITIONS DES ÉQUIPEMENTS DE DEPLOYMENT
 - D. PROCHAINES POSITIONS PRÉVUES DANS LES 24, 48 ET 72 HEURES
 - E. NR. TELEX/INMARSAT FAX ET TÉLÉPHONE/E-MAIL DU NAVIRE
5. MERCI DE COMMUNIQUER TOUTE MODIFICATION DES DONNÉES DU PLANNING DANS LES MEILLEURS DÉLAIS, ET SI POSSIBLE 72 HEURES À L'AVANCE ET AU PLUS TARD 24 HEURES À L'AVANCE.
6. POUR LA COMMUNICATION DES INFORMATIONS CI-DESSUS, LES MOYENS SUIVANTS PEUVENT ÊTRE UTILISÉS :
 - A. TÉLÉPHONE : 00 210 984 451 ;
 - B. E-MAIL: COMAR.SUPERVISOR@ MARINHA.PT ;
 - E. E-MAIL : CZMA.EM.CSINF@MARINHA.PT

7. AU COURS DES TRAVAUX DE RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE, ET NOTAMMENT PENDANT LES OPÉRATIONS DE MANUTENTION DES ÉQUIPEMENTS, DE TOUS MATÉRIELS SUBMERGÉS ET BALISES DE SIGNALISATION, ET PENDANT LES MANŒUVRES DU NAVIRE, LES DISTANCES MINIMUM DE SÉCURITÉ DOIVENT ÊTRE RESPECTÉES, TANT VIS-À-VIS DES CÂBLES SOUS-MARINS (1/4 MILE) IDENTIFIÉS SUR LES CARTES NAUTIQUES OFFICIELLES, QUE DES NAVIRES CÂBLIERS (1 MILLE) IMPLIQUÉS DANS LA RÉPARATION OU L'INSTALLATION DE CÂBLES
8. POUR POUVOIR ÉMETTRE LES AVIS DE NAVIGATION EN TEMPS VOULUS, LE COMAR DOIT ÊTRE INFORMÉ DES MOUVEMENTS ET DES LIMITES DE MANŒUVRE DU NAVIRE 72H À L'AVANCE, À L'ADRESSE EMAIL SUIVANTE :
E-MAIL: COMAR.SEGMAR@MARINHA.PT
9. LE CENTRE DE CONTRÔLE DU TRAFIC MARITIME DU CONTINENT (CCTMC) DOIT ÉGALEMENT ÊTRE INFORMÉ QUOTIDIENNEMENT DU PLANNING DES MOUVEMENTS DU NAVIRE AU COURS DES 24 HEURES SUIVANTES, AINSI QUE DE TOUTE MODIFICATION DU PLANNING OU DE TOUS INCIDENTS/ACCIDENTS QUI INTERFÉRERAIENT AVEC LE TRAVAIL, POUR LA COMMUNICATION DE CES INFORMATIONS, IL CONVIENDRA D'AVOIR RECOURS AUX MOYENS DE COMMUNICATION SUIVANTS :
EMAIL : OPER.VTS@DGRM.MM.GOV.PT
FAX : + 351 214464839
TEL. : + 351 244648389
VHF : CANAUX 22 OU 79.